

Achieving optimal laser-proton acceleration through multi-parameter interaction control

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Für Axel, meine Eltern und meine Schwestern

Abstract

Relativistic laser-driven plasmas can be the source of energetic proton beams and have received increasing attention due to their high potential as compact and cost-efficient medical particle accelerators for radiation therapy. As such, exploring viable routes to scale the maximum proton energy to the medically relevant regime remains the subject of ongoing efforts in the field. This endeavor is inherently linked to the discernment and control of seminal aspects of the acceleration process, ranging on vast temporal and spatial ranges due to highly variable plasma densities and laser intensities within one single interaction. This thesis investigates laser-proton acceleration on various physical scales and the influence of realistic laser pulse parameters, to ultimately find an optimum regime for stable proton beam production with highest particle energies. Experimental studies following this objective were primarily conducted at the high-power titanium:sapphire laser system Draco 150 TW at Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf (HZDR). Efficient on-demand control of the temporal laser pulse history was established in the form of a plasma mirror filter combined with on-shot temporal pulse contrast characterization based on an advanced spectral interferometry diagnostic. This allowed for experiments with variable pulse contrast, thus providing additional handles for proton source optimization and additionally, extending the selection of applicable interaction targets to lower thicknesses and densities. Studies with novel target technologies such as ultra-thin liquid crystal films and solid hydrogen jets were performed, each at optimized acceleration conditions, resulting in excellent proton beams with high energies and particle numbers that promise to be highly scalable with increasing laser intensities. Elaborate diagnostic suites in combination with numerical simulations delivered an improved picture of the acceleration process, which generally remains difficult to assess experimentally on the microscopic spatial and ultrafast temporal scale. As an important result, the onset of relativistic target transparency was observed for ultra-thin liquid crystal films, an operation regime that may deliver increased proton energies when optimized. Proton acceleration results from the hydrogen jet agreed well with predictive particle-in-cell simulations, thus establishing a test bed for closely linked experimental and numerical studies into advanced acceleration mechanisms, as are for example associated with target transparency. Furthermore, an unexpected proton beam structuring effect was discovered that can play a significant role in experiments with transparent or very small targets. Formerly unrecognized by the community, this effect leads to the extension of spatial and temporal interaction scales beyond the initial proton acceleration in the laser focus, that need to be considered for appropriate interpretation of proton profile signatures.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Relativistic laser-driven plasmas can sustain electric field gradients in the order of GV m^{-1} to TV m^{-1} . This capability has led to their increasing popularity for novel particle accelerator concepts. Conventional accelerator technology, most impressively implemented in the Large Hadron Collider (LHC), is inherently limited in the maximum field gradient achievable to about 100 MV m^{-1} . The vacuum breaks down at electric fields exceeding this limit, that is, electrons are extracted from solid surfaces and induce cascading effects that ultimately lead to electric field disruption.^[1,2] At three to six orders of magnitude higher accelerating gradients, relativistic laser plasmas can generate brilliant and energetic particle beams over substantially shorter acceleration lengths than conventional accelerators.^[3-8] Therefore, laser-driven plasmas offer the possibility of a significant downsizing of accelerator machines not least regarding their financial cost, leading to higher accessibility to such particle and radiation sources for research and industrial applications.

Establishing the necessary plasma conditions for efficient particle acceleration requires extremely high laser intensities. Those can be provided by table-top laser systems based on the chirped pulse amplification technique,^[9] generating laser powers reaching 1 PW on a laboratory area of only few ten square meters by compressing the laser energy to ultra-short pulses.^[10-12] Focusing to a spot size in the order of μm leads to relativistic laser intensities, meaning that electrons in the laser focus acquire relativistic energies within the first half-wave of the laser pulse. In general, plasma-based particle acceleration results from charge separation fields that are established during laser-plasma interaction. The most prominent acceleration schemes are laser wake field acceleration (LWFA) of electrons^[13,14] and target normal sheath acceleration (TNSA) of protons and ions.^[15] LWFA is conducted with gas targets that are quickly ionized by the leading laser pulse edge, followed by the formation of collective plasma oscillations in the wake of the pulse as it propagates through the transparent plasma. Free electrons are accelerated up to GeV energies in dynamic electric fields associated with the resulting plasma wave.^[16,17] If optimized, monoenergetic electron bunches with high peak current

Fig. 1.1. Schematic depiction of laser-driven proton acceleration. The emitted proton beam properties crucially depend on microscopic ultra-fast processes unfolding during the laser-target interaction. The intensity distribution along the temporal pulse shape (left, 1) and in the high-power laser focus (left, 2) define the absorption of laser energy into plasma electrons. Quasi-static accelerating fields at the target surfaces are the result of electron propagation and recirculation through the target (center, 3, from ref.^[38]). The proton cutoff energy (right, 4) is defined by maximum accelerating fields, while the angular emission (right, 5) is not only influenced by the sheath field structure, but may become subject to further beam deflection during propagation.

can be generated.^[18] TNSA is generally pursued with solid targets, most commonly in the form of few μm thick metal or plastic foils that are opaque for the laser light. Figure 1.1 schematically displays the interaction principle. Equally ionized by the lead edge of the laser pulse, the laser peak intensity interacts with free electrons in a pre-formed plasma layer at the target surface. Electrons gain energy in the laser field, circulate through the target core and expand beyond the predominantly fixed ion distribution at the target surfaces. The resulting quasi-static charge separation fields are in the order of TV m^{-1} and lead to the acceleration of protons and ions to $> 10 \text{ MeV}$ energies, emitted along the target normal with a beam divergence of roughly $\pm 20^\circ$.^[6,19] The generated particle beams are of high flux (up to 10^{13} particles per pulse) and feature broad exponential energy spectra up to the characteristic cutoff energy.^[20-22] Their high laminarity, point-source characteristic and initially short bunch duration^[7] render TNSA proton beams attractive for a number of multidisciplinary applications, ranging from high dose-rate radio-biology^[23-27] and translational research in radiation oncology^[28,29] over time-resolved radiography of transient plasma phenomena^[30-33] to inertial confinement fusion,^[34,35] materials^[36] and warm dense matter research.^[37]

While most of these applications are already pursued in a laboratory environment, transferring laser-driven proton sources to a reliable technology comparable to conventional accelerators like synchrotrons and cyclotrons remains the subject of ongoing efforts in the field. In particular, preparing laser-driven proton beams for radiation therapy and translating laser-driven proton sources into clinically applicable machines is a core endeavor pursued at the PW-class laser Draco*

*Dresden laser acceleration source

at Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf (HZDR), where the research for this thesis was performed. Initially embedded in the interdisciplinary project onCOOPtics* that united clinical-based institutions (OncoRay[†]) and laser-plasma research (HZDR and Friedrich-Schiller-Universität Jena), translative research performed in this continuing collaboration covers the entire task chain from optimizing the laser-plasma accelerator,^[39–41] via designing and implementing beam delivery systems and treatment plans based on pulsed magnets,^[28,42–44] to studying the radiobiological response of tumor cells to laser-accelerated protons.^[25,45,46]

Two critical challenges towards providing medical laser-driven proton accelerators remain open at the current stage and thus receive high attention and exertion in the field. First, scaling the delivered proton energies to the medically relevant regime of 200 – 250 MeV is yet to be demonstrated.^[47] The current energy record is held by the work of *Higginson* and colleagues^[48] who achieved 94 MeV at the Vulcan laser[‡]. Second, the proton beam parameters like maximum energy, particle number, spectral shape and transverse emission distribution have to be fully on-demand to allow for reproducible control over the accelerator performance for applications. Both requirements reveal the need for an improved knowledge over fundamental processes unfolding during the acceleration, that directly influence the resulting proton beam properties. Approaching 20 years after their initial discovery, laser-generation of protons in its full complexity still lacks a quantitative microscopic description and hence remains a highly unexplored field of research. Thus, developing a detailed picture of the interaction including the influence of realistic laser pulse parameters gains increasing momentum in the community.[§] The following core tasks form the basis of this endeavor and are in parts addressed in this thesis.

The acceleration process is initiated and hence strongly governed by the laser pulse impinging on the target. In particular, the spatio-temporal laser pulse energy distribution in the laser focus directly influences the shape of the target plasma prior to and during the interaction. Even though the main pulse is only few 10 fs long, background radiation may arise during pulse amplification and precede the main pulse on timescales of nanoseconds. If sufficiently intense, this background radiation ionizes the target surface and leads to early plasma formation and expansion. This was found to have significant implications on the absorption efficiency of laser energy into the free plasma electrons,^[49] their transport through the target^[50] and the formation of plasma instabilities,^[40,51] all of which have a strong impact on the proton acceleration performance. Pre-expansion of the target rear is considered to reduce accelerating field strengths, which directly affects maximum proton energies.^[52,53] Hence, diagnostic capabilities of the microscopic laser-plasma interaction are a primary prerequisite in optimizing laser-driven proton sources at given laser parameters. This is rendered challenging by ultra-fast (fs) and very small ($< \mu\text{m}$)

*Zentren für Innovationskompetenz-Verbundprojekt: "onCOOPtics - Hochintensitätslaser für die Radioonkologie"

[†]National Center for Radiation Research in Oncology, Technische Universität Dresden

[‡]Rutherford Appleton Laboratory, Oxfordshire, United Kingdom

[§]This is for example reflected in successful research proposals, e.g. the funding of the *future subject* "Plasma Accelerators: Probing the femto-scale dynamics of relativistic plasmas" by the Impuls- und Vernetzungsfond of the Helmholtz Society.

scales of plasma processes unfolding in the high-power laser focus that need to be resolved. The high opacity of solid-density target plasmas to optical and infrared laser radiation further complicates this effort. Probing these plasmas with x-ray free electron lasers (XFEL) has seen tremendous development in recent years,^[54] but is currently only possible in three* laboratories worldwide, a fact that reflects the large infrastructure necessary for these highly complex studies. Therefore, assessment of the acceleration performance is often based on macroscopic observables, like the general properties of the laser-accelerated particle beams. Parallel attempts pursued in the community to assess the full spatio-temporal intensity distribution of a high-power laser focus equally struggle with the necessary resolution capabilities. This effort is further complicated by the demands towards intensity dynamic, ideally reaching from the ionization threshold of the target material at $\sim 10^{13} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$ to nominal peak intensities exceeding $10^{21} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$.

The link between macroscopic observables and ultra-fast, microscopic plasma processes is currently only provided by numerical simulations, thus representing indispensable tools in interpreting experimental results. Particle-in-cell (PIC) simulations allow modeling of the entire interaction and provide a high-resolution picture of plasma processes unfolding in the target, by computing particles and fields self-consistently on a discretized grid. While having undergone tremendous development over the recent years, PIC simulations remain computationally expensive when it comes to accurately modeling the complex physical processes involved. Limited computational resources therefore demand simplifications in simulation setups, mostly realized by reducing the number of spatial dimensions, assuming lower target densities or decreasing the simulation size. As such, the credibility of simulation results strongly depends on the capability of the simplified numerical setup to authentically represent the fundamental physics involved in the interaction.^[55] In particular, initial simulation conditions need to be derived as precisely as possible from the experiment, ideally via aforementioned methodical laser- and plasma characterization diagnostics, to improve the interplay between experiments and simulations.

Accurate representation of experiments in predictive simulations would provide key control handles to further develop TNSA and potential alternative acceleration mechanisms. Promising approaches include radiation pressure acceleration (RPA)^[56-60] and improved acceleration conditions resulting from relativistic induced transparency (RIT) of the target plasma.^[48,61-65] Reaching ultra-high intensities in a minimum volume to maximize the energy transfer to a limited number of particles ultimately leads to the superposition and interplay of many effects and mechanisms. Identifying these mechanisms and optimizing their distinct contributions to the resulting proton beam represents a central challenge for the field of laser-proton acceleration.

*The combined operation of XFELs and relativistic optical lasers are currently available at the matter in extreme conditions (MEC) instrument of the Linac coherent light Source (LCLS) at Stanford linear accelerator center (SLAC) in the USA, at SPring-8 Angstrom Compact free electron LASer (SACLA) of the Riken institute in Japan and at the Helmholtz International Beamline for Extreme Fields at the European XFEL (HiBEF) in Germany.

1.2 Content of the thesis

The presented thesis contributes in various aspects to the above outlined road map towards a deeper understanding of fundamental processes during the interaction, to ultimately advance the performance of laser-driven proton beams to the medical regime. Special emphasis is laid on controlling and simplifying experimental interaction conditions to improve the descriptiveness and, consequently, scalability of the generated proton acceleration results. The corresponding experimental work was performed primarily at the Draco 150 TW laser at HZDR. The larger part of numerical simulations was conducted with the PIC code PIConGPU^[66] on HZDR's high performance computer Hypnos.

Proton energy scaling at enhanced laser contrast

As introduced above, laser background radiation preceding the main pulse induces target pre-expansion that may severely limit maximum achievable proton energies. Increasing the overall pulse power is generally accompanied by a corresponding increase in background radiation. Therefore, controlling the temporal pulse history (subsumed under the term *temporal contrast*) by appropriate filtering is rendered prerequisite to extend the initially favorable proton energy scaling observed at Draco 150 TW^[39] to the PW level. As such, a primary task of the thesis is to explore the scalability of proton cutoff energies at enhanced temporal laser contrast and to scrutinize the onset of beneficial advanced acceleration regimes. In a first step, this constitutes a), the design and implementation of a plasma mirror setup^[67] in the Draco 150 TW beam line, and b), the single-shot characterization of the achieved contrast improvement with a novel contrast diagnostic, enabling such measurements at unprecedented intensity dynamic and temporal range.

In the second step, a study with ultra-thin liquid crystal film targets at plasma mirror enhanced laser contrast is presented, that was performed in collaboration with the Ohio State University*. Those targets, which suffered pre-expansion and destruction before implementation of the plasma mirror, were now the source of excellent proton beams with a strong increase in proton cutoff energies as compared to reference measurements without plasma mirror and thicker targets. An extended diagnostics suite, not only recording proton beam properties but also reflected and transmitted pulse parts as well as emitted electrons, extends former studies in this field and, in combination, provides a more comprehensive picture of the interaction. This allowed observing the onset of relativistic induced transparency for the thinnest foils with thicknesses $\lesssim 30$ nm.

The combination of plasma mirror contrast cleaning, on-shot contrast characterization, ultra-thin targets and a large diagnostic suite to scrutinize the interaction, serves as a blueprint for successful proton acceleration experiments with PW lasers.

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Novel target technology to improve the interplay between simulation and experiment

Cryogenic continuous targets^[68,69] represent an alternative target approach that credibly increase the comparability of experimental and simulation results. Determined by the supplied cryogenic gas, single- or well-controlled few species targets are produced with a factor 10 lower density than the commonly used metal or plastic foils. Their numerical modeling benefits from a corresponding reduction of computationally expensive ionization and collision physics, the implementation and bench-marking of which, while accomplished for PIConGPU, is yet to be standardized in other, broadly used PIC-codes. Predictive simulation of experimental results hence becomes feasible with this novel target type. Two experimental studies are presented in this thesis, each conducted in international collaborations and employing different operation alternatives of cryogenic hydrogen targets at two different laser systems, Draco 150 TW and ELFIE of École Polytechnique*. Produced as renewable, self-aligning and free standing targets without requiring support structures in the vicinity of the laser-interaction, both target types, namely cryogenic jets^[68] and ribbons,^[69] allow for a multitude of diagnostics to monitor the interaction from different angles. Both studies represent the first demonstration of optimized TNSA conditions, leading to the highest proton energies observed so far from the respective target type, which are thus rendered viable alternatives to the typically used foil targets. Two-dimensional PIC simulations are presented that reproduce general trends observed in the experiment performed at Draco 150 TW and confirm operation in the TNSA regime. The studies at hand establish a numerical and experimental environment that can serve as a basis of further investigation into less considered aspects of TNSA, like multi-species effects,^[70] or the transition to advanced acceleration schemes.^[71,72]

How the millimeter-scale interaction environment affects the laser-driven proton beam

The final part of this thesis describes the discovery of all-optical imprinting of tailored structures to the proton beam profile. Formerly unrecognized by the community, the described effect leads to an extension of spatial and temporal interaction scales that need to be considered for correct interpretation of the observed proton beam signatures.

During experiments with the hydrogen jet target,^[51,73,74] structures resembling intensity features in the laser beam before focusing counter-intuitively reappeared in the otherwise smooth proton profile. A follow-up experiment, as well as two-dimensional PIC simulations reveal that residual gas molecules, remaining in the interaction chamber after evacuation, are ionized by the remnant laser light, passing around the target of limited size. As a result, low-density plasma areas extend up to > 10 mm behind the laser focus and serve as a memorizing medium for the laser intensity mode after its spatial filtering at the target. Quasi-static transverse electric

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field gradients of 10^6 to 10^7 V m^{-1} are induced in those areas, that, decoupled from the initial proton acceleration process, lead to information transfer to the protons, culminating in dose modulations in the resulting beam profile. Such profile modulations had so far been primarily associated with instabilities in the target plasma, that may restrain the scalability to high proton energies and certainly reduce control over the angular proton emission.^[40,51,75] Occurring under typical experimental laser, target and vacuum conditions, all-optical imprinting poses an additional explanation for modulated proton beams, which, contrary to plasma instabilities, is easily controllable.

On the other hand, controlled structuring of proton beams to a specific target design can be achieved via the presented method in already existing experimental setups. As the structuring itself does not limit the overall proton beam performance, this capability may be of interest to laser-driven proton source applications.

2 Theory of short pulse laser-matter interaction

In this chapter basic concepts of laser-matter interaction that are relevant for the results of this thesis are introduced. Target normal sheath acceleration (TNSA) is a secondary process resulting from charge separation fields that are installed following laser-solid interaction. In general, the solid target is ionized by laser light preceding the main pulse, such that the latter interacts with a pre-formed free electron population. Laser energy that is absorbed into the latter translates into ultra-high field strengths, in which protons and ions are accelerated to MeV energies.

2.1 Plasma formation and interaction physics

2.1.1 Ionization of target material

Ionization of atoms and the generation of plasma cannot be achieved with a single photon of a high-power laser, as its energy is too low. Ionization of target atoms therefore occurs through multi-photon, field and collisional ionization. The laser intensity I_L is an important parameter in differentiating between those ionization mechanisms and is related to the amplitude of the electric laser field component E_0 as

$$I_L = \frac{\epsilon_0 c}{2} E_0^2 \quad (2.1)$$

with the electric constant ϵ_0 and the speed of light c . It is instructive to consider the Coulomb electric field of an hydrogen atom of $5 \cdot 10^9 \text{ V m}^{-1}$ and the corresponding intensity following equation (2.1) of $3.51 \cdot 10^{16} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$. This illustrates that present day laser intensities exceed the atomic electric field by several orders of magnitude such that ionization of target material does not occur at peak intensity, but already during the rising edge of the laser pulse. The latter can extend to nanoseconds before the main pulse due to background radiation originating in the laser system, refer to Fig. 2.1a). As ionization of the target material substantially alters the interaction physics upon arrival of the main laser pulse, the primary ionization

Fig. 2.1. a) Schematic laser temporal contrast curve and corresponding barrier suppression ionization (BSI) states of Ti. b) Atomic Coulomb potential and different field ionization channels: (i) multi-photon ionization, (ii) above threshold ionization, (iii) tunneling ionization, (iv) barrier suppression ionization.

mechanisms shall be introduced in the following (refer to Fig. 2.1b), including their threshold intensities.

Multi-photon ionization (MPI) occurs once an atom absorbs n laser photons of energy $\hbar\omega_L$ (ω_L is the laser frequency), such that a bound electron acquires the atomic binding energy $W_f = n\hbar\omega_L$ and is freed from the atom. The threshold laser intensity for MPI is $I_L \simeq 10^{10} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$.^[76,77] **Above threshold ionization (ATI)** leaves the free electron with a net final energy ϵ_f after ionization, as the atom absorbs s more photons than necessary for MPI. Becoming relevant for intensities $I_L \geq 10^{13} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$, ATI leads to free electrons with the kinetic energy $\epsilon_f = (n + s)\hbar\omega_L - W_f$.^[78,79] A free electron exposed to the field of a high-power laser pulse starts to oscillate and thereby acquires a quiver energy, also called ponderomotive energy, given by^[80]

$$U_p = \frac{e^2 E_0^2}{4m_e \omega_L^2} \quad (2.2)$$

where e is the elementary charge and m_e the electron mass (see section 2.1.2 for details). Once the laser field strength is high enough, it affects even the bound electrons such that their ionization threshold is increased by U_p , called AC-Stark shift. Hence, the resulting ATI electron energy is modified to $\epsilon_f = (n + s)\hbar\omega - (W_f + U_p)$.^[81] Further increase of the laser intensity leads to tilting of the atomic Coulomb potential and the formation of a potential barrier. Electrons are ionized by tunneling through the barrier quantum-mechanically with a finite probability, called **tunneling ionization**. The effective Coulomb potential can be considered quasi-static as ionization in this regime occurs rapidly within the first fraction of the laser cycle. The model by *Ammosov, Delone and Krainov*^[82] (ADK model) describes the probabilistic tunneling rate. The Keldysh parameter^[77,83] $\gamma_K = \sqrt{W_f/(2U_p)}$, specifies the transition from MPI/ATI-dominated ionization ($\gamma_K > 1$) to tunneling-dominated ionization ($\gamma < 1$). With increasing laser field strength the potential barrier becomes narrower until the electron is classically free due to **barrier suppression ionization (BSI)**. The required laser intensity for BSI derives from equating the maximum of the potential barrier with the ionization energy W_p of a certain bound state. This yields

the appearance intensity of the ionic charge state Z_i ^[81]

$$I_{\text{BSI}} \left[\text{W cm}^{-2} \right] = 4 \cdot 10^9 \cdot \frac{W_p^4 \left[\text{eV}^4 \right]}{Z_i^2} . \quad (2.3)$$

Ionization of hydrogen is predicted at an intensity $I_L \geq I_{\text{BSI,H}^+} = 1.37 \cdot 10^{14} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$. At slightly lower intensities also lies the transition from MPI/ATI to tunneling dominated ionization regime, estimated via γ_K , at $I_L \sim 10^{14} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$, practically allowing all field ionization mechanisms to occur simultaneously. In case of a gradual intensity increase, MPI/ATI, occurring on time scales of femtoseconds, can already fully ionize an atom before the appearance intensity for BSI is reached. Figure 2.1a) schematically shows BSI-levels appearing along the temporal laser intensity curve for the case of titanium, a target material commonly used for reference shots at Draco.

Free electrons can quickly ionize the surrounding material through **impact (collisional) ionization**. The electron-ion collision frequency is calculated via^[80]

$$\nu_{\text{ei}} \left[\text{s}^{-1} \right] = 2.91 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot \frac{Z_i n_e \left[\text{cm}^{-3} \right]}{T_e^{3/2} \left[\text{eV}^{3/2} \right]} \cdot \ln \Lambda \quad , \quad \Lambda = \frac{12\pi}{Z_i} \cdot \lambda_D^3 n_e \quad (2.4)$$

where n_e is the free electron density per cm^3 , T_e corresponds to the mean electron energy in eV and λ_D is a characteristic charge screening length (see next section). As electrons further gain energy in the laser field, they collisionally ionize target areas that are inaccessible to the laser light due to its optical plasma properties (section 2.1.3). Plasma densities of solid targets used for proton acceleration are typically in the order of $n_e \simeq 10^{23} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ with electron energies T_e of few hundred keV and shielding lengths $\lambda_D \simeq 10 \text{ nm}$. The resulting collisional rates are in the order of one event per 1-10 fs and are, therefore, competing with BSI as soon as a small population of free electrons is available. However, as these electrons increasingly gain energy in the laser field, collisions become less and less frequent and collisional ionization is rendered negligible for laser intensities exceeding $10^{17} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$.^[77]

2.1.2 Electron motion in the laser field

Once electrons are freed from their atomic potential they gain energy by interacting with the laser field, as indicated in equation (2.2). A plane wave laser field with linear polarization and propagating in z -direction, described by electric $\vec{E}_L = E_0 \sin(\omega_L t - k_L z) \vec{e}_y$ and magnetic field components $\vec{B}_L = B_0 \sin(\omega_L t - k_L z) \vec{e}_x$ is assumed. Electrons subjected to this field experience the Lorentz force

$$\vec{F} = -e(\vec{E}_L + \vec{v} \times \vec{B}_L) \quad (2.5)$$

where \vec{v} is the electron velocity. The electric field component in equation (2.5) leads to electron oscillations around a fixed point in space with the velocity

$$\vec{v} = v_{\text{os}} \cos(\omega_L t) \vec{e}_y \quad , \quad v_{\text{os}} = \frac{eE_0}{m_e \omega_L} \quad (2.6)$$

Fig. 2.2. Schematic illustration of the ponderomotive force.

where v_{os} is the so called quiver velocity. For high field amplitudes E_0 , v_{os} approaches the speed of light meaning that the magnetic component of the Lorentz force has an increasing effect on the electron motion. The transition to the relativistic regime can be described with the dimensionless parameter $a_0 = p_{os}^{max}/cm_e$ with the maximum electron quiver momentum $p_{os}^{max} = \gamma m_e v_{os}^{max}$.^[80] If $a_0 \geq 1$, the electron motion in the laser field is considered relativistic. The corresponding laser intensity dependence follows with equation (2.1) as

$$a_0 = 0.85 \sqrt{\frac{I_L [\text{W cm}^{-2}] \lambda_L^2 [\mu\text{m}^2]}{10^{18}}} \quad (2.7)$$

in practical units, where λ_L is the laser wavelength. This implies that relativistic intensities are reached for $I_L \simeq 2 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$ in the case of Ti:Sa wavelength $\lambda_L = 0.8 \mu\text{m}$. Accelerating protons to high oscillation velocities requires significantly higher laser intensities in the range of $10^{24} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$, which are not available with current day laser systems.

The magnetic component in equation (2.5) results in an additional electron oscillation in z -direction with a frequency of $2\omega_L$, as well as an average drift with a velocity^[80]

$$v_{D,z} = \frac{a_0^2 c}{4 + a_0^2} \quad (2.8)$$

Transition to realistic experimental conditions requires confining the delivered laser energy both spatially and in time, in order to reach sufficiently high intensities. Focused ultra-short laser pulses feature steep radial and temporal intensity gradients, which have significant influence on the electron motion. According to the Woodward-Lawson theorem,^[84] electrons do not gain net energy in plane wave laser fields in vacuum but return to their initial state once the laser is turned off. This situation changes with a spatially varying laser envelope as is the case with a focused beam. There, the electron oscillates radially to a position with smaller field amplitude and hence, less restoring force. This leads to an effective force towards

regions of lower laser intensity

$$\vec{F}_p = -m_e c^2 \nabla_r \bar{\gamma} \quad (2.9)$$

called relativistic ponderomotive force with the time-averaged relativistic Lorentz factor

$$\bar{\gamma} = \sqrt{1 + \frac{v_{D,z}^2}{c^2} + \frac{v_{os}^2}{c^2}} \approx \sqrt{1 + a_0^2} \quad (2.10)$$

where a_0^2 is frequently replaced by $a_0^2/2$ to account for the cycle average of the harmonically oscillating laser field.^[50] For simplicity, $\bar{\gamma}$ will be written as γ throughout this thesis, always describing the time-averaged Lorentz factor if not stated otherwise. The corresponding ponderomotive potential reads

$$U_p = m_e c^2 (\gamma - 1), \quad (2.11)$$

which is also the kinetic energy an electron initially at rest acquires from the laser field, introduced in equation (2.2). In the non-relativistic limit $a_0 \ll 1$ the ponderomotive force is given as

$$\vec{F}_p^{nr} = -\frac{e^2}{4m_e \omega_L^2} \nabla_r E_0^2. \quad (2.12)$$

Following equations (2.9) or (2.12), an electron will drift from regions of higher to regions of lower intensity, illustrated in Fig. 2.2. This process is sometimes called ponderomotive scattering. The scattering angle ϑ is linked to the final energy expressed with the relativistic factor γ via $\tan \vartheta = \sqrt{2/(\gamma - 1)}$.^[80] In case the electron propagates with an initial (non-relativistic) velocity $\beta_0 = m_e v_{D,z,0} / \gamma_0$ and lorentz factor γ_0 , the scattering angle is given by^[85]

$$\tan \vartheta = \frac{\sqrt{2(\gamma/\gamma_0 - 1)/(1 + \beta_0)}}{\gamma - \gamma_0(1 - \beta_0)}. \quad (2.13)$$

Ponderomotive scattering can lead to a net gain in electron kinetic energy and is therefore sometimes called vacuum acceleration. This has been demonstrated in numerical and experimental studies by actively limiting the interaction region between laser and electrons^[86-88] or by tailoring the laser focus to create a potential well.^[89] *Thévenet et al.*^[90] showed that electrons extracted from a solid target surface where injected in the reflected part of the laser beam and ponderomotively scattered including a net energy gain (refer also to chapter 3 of this thesis).

2.1.3 Plasma properties and laser propagation in plasma

As introduced in section 2.1.1, the target material generally gets ionized by pulse parts preceding the main laser pulse, such that at peak intensity, the laser interacts with a pre-formed plasma. As soon as populations of free electrons and ions exist, few electrons may escape the interaction region due to the ponderomotive force given by equation (2.9).^[91] The resulting net positive charge of the ionized volume prevents the remaining electrons from escaping. The charge imbalance is small,

so a quasi-neutral ion-electron distribution persists. The collective behavior of the plasma allows for a fluid-like treatment of its basic properties, thereby largely simplifying its analytical description.^[77] The density of the free electron fluid is

$$n_e = Z_i n_i = Z_i N_A \rho A^{-1} \quad (2.14)$$

with the charge state Z_i , ion density n_i , Avogadro number N_A , mass density ρ and atomic number A . Considering electrons and ions as two separate fluids that are in local thermal equilibrium, the populations' average energies correspond to "temperatures" T_e and T_i of their respective Maxwellian velocity spectra. The Debye-length λ_D is a typical plasma parameter describing quasi-neutrality. Considering a single charged particle inside the plasma, the Coulomb field of this charge is screened by the surrounding plasma inside a sphere with the radius λ_D such that particles outside this sphere experience the $1/e$ -times reduced field of the charged particle at its center. In the case of a positive charge,

$$\lambda_D = \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon_0 k_B T_e}{e^2 n_e}}, \quad (2.15)$$

where ϵ_0 is the electric constant, $k_B T_e$ is the average kinetic energy of the surrounding electron fluid, e is the elementary charge and n_e is the electron density. The free electron population reacts to fluctuations and installs screening on a time scale that is the inverse of the electron plasma frequency $\omega_{p,e} = \sqrt{e^2 n_e \epsilon_0^{-1} m_e^{-1}}$. Due to their higher mass, ions react on much longer time scales with the frequency $\omega_{p,i} = \sqrt{m_e/m_i} \cdot \omega_{p,e}$ and are considered immobile on a timescale of the ultra-short laser pulse length $\tau_L \simeq 30$ fs. If not stated otherwise, the plasma frequency ω_p is therefore associated with the electron motion throughout this thesis.

After rearrangement of the charges to establish quasi-neutrality through screening, a quasi-static electric potential $\Phi(\vec{r})$ between electron and ion density distributions exists that satisfies Poisson's equation^[92]

$$\Delta \Phi(\vec{r}) = \frac{e}{\epsilon_0} [n_e(\vec{r}) - Z_i n_i(\vec{r})], \quad (2.16)$$

where $n_e(r)$ follows a Boltzmann distribution

$$n_e(\vec{r}) = n_{e,0} \exp\left[\frac{e\Phi(\vec{r})}{k_B T_e}\right] \quad (2.17)$$

with the initial free electron density after ionization $n_{e,0} = Z_i n_i$. Due to their longer reaction times, ions initially remain in a step-like distribution. Reduction of the geometry to one dimension and integration of equation (2.16) using equation (2.17) yields the electric field at the ion front^[92]

$$E_{\text{front}} = \sqrt{\frac{2n_{e,0} k_B T_e}{e \epsilon_0}} \quad (2.18)$$

where e denotes Euler's number.

As long as the collisionality of the plasma is low ($\nu_{ei}/\omega_p \ll 1$), which is often the case for peak intensity laser-plasma interactions, the plasma's refractive index η_0 is given by

$$\eta_0 = \sqrt{1 - \frac{\omega_p^2}{\omega_L^2}} . \quad (2.19)$$

The laser can only propagate in the plasma as long as η_0 is real, that is, $\omega_p < \omega_L$, in which case the plasma is called underdense because the electron density is below the critical density

$$n_c = \epsilon_0 m_e \omega_L^2 / e^2 . \quad (2.20)$$

The critical density for titanium:sapphire lasers such as Draco is $n_c = 1.74 \cdot 10^{21} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. The laser pulse is reflected at the critical density plane where $n_e = n_c$, or, for oblique laser incidence under an angle δ at $n_e = n_c \cos^2 \delta$.^[80] Beyond the reflective plane the plasma is considered overdense and its refractive index is imaginary, meaning that the laser field decays quickly in the form of an evanescent wave and reaches only as far as the skin depth $l_s = c/\omega_p$. If the electron motion becomes relativistic, the associated mass increase $m_e^{\text{rel}} = \gamma m_e$, results in modified laser reflection properties from overdense plasmas. The relativistic electron mass translates to the modification of the plasma frequency to $\omega_p^{\text{rel}} = \omega_p / \sqrt{\gamma}$. Due to the increased electron inertia, generation of the necessary current to reflect the laser pulse is reduced and the laser can propagate further into the target until $n_e = \gamma n_c$, which results from replacing m_e with m_e^{rel} in equation (2.20).

At laser propagation through transparent (not necessarily yet ionized) media the optical Kerr effect needs to be considered, causing a variation in refractive index proportional to the local laser intensity, such that $\eta = \eta_0 + \eta_2 \cdot I_L$, where η_2 is the density dependent second order nonlinear refractive index.^[93] In the case of air, $\eta_2 = 3 \cdot 10^{-19} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ W}^{-1}$. For a Gaussian lateral laser beam profile, I_L and therefore η is higher in the center than in the outer regions. According to classical optics, light rays are always bent towards regions of higher refractive index, meaning that during propagation of a Gaussian beam through transparent media laser energy accumulates at the center of the beam. This effect is called self-focussing. Analytical treatment of the scenario reveals that a critical laser power $P_{\text{crit}} \sim \eta_0 \lambda_L^2 / \eta_2$ exists beyond which self-focussing is expected. For air, $P_{\text{crit}} = 4 \text{ GW}$, therefore high-power laser beam lines are usually in vacuum during and after final temporal pulse compression to avoid self-focussing. Propagation through transparent media not only potentially affects the laser pulse spatially, but can also modify its wavelength spectrum. Called self-phase-modulation, this effect has severe implications on the laser pulse's temporal structure while propagating through transmissive components in the laser chain.

Upon laser self-focussing the intensity peaks close to the propagation axis, leading to high-order multi-photon ionization. The resulting increase in free electron density contributes negatively to η_0 and acts defocussing on the laser beam. In case self-focussing and MPI-related defocussing contributions even out, a stable channel or filament is formed which oscillates in radius and is able to guide the laser

beam over large distances.^[94] In case of a fully ionized underdense plasma, guiding occurs due to the ponderomotive force exerted by the laser on the free plasma electrons. Directed along the negative gradient of the laser intensity envelope, this force results in local electron density changes and the formation of the a guiding structure. Another contribution arises in case the plasma electrons gain relativistic energies in the laser field leading to relativistic corrections to their mass, where the refractive index does not hold in its simple form (equation 2.19) anymore. This effect is termed relativistic self-guiding and occurs for laser powers higher than a critical power $P_{\text{crit, rsf}} [\text{GW}] = 17\omega_L^2/\omega_p^2$.^[95]

These guiding plasma structures are a prerequisite for efficient laser wakefield acceleration (LWFA) of electrons in underdense plasmas.^[13] As the laser propagates through the guiding plasma, it expels electrons radially from the laser axis due to its ponderomotive force. The electrons are subsequently reattracted by the remaining immobile ions and propagate back towards the laser axis. Gaining significant momentum on their return trajectory, they overshoot their initial position. As a result, plasma oscillations with frequency ω_p are formed behind the laser, in which strong electromagnetic fields can be sustained. Electrons injected into these fields are accelerated to GeV-energies.^[17] The maximum field strength in the wake is given by the wave breaking limit^[96]

$$E_{\text{WB}} = \frac{m_e c \omega_p}{e} . \quad (2.21)$$

Typical electron densities in LWFA experiments are in the order of 10^{18} cm^{-3} , resulting in electric fields of $E_{\text{WB}} \simeq 100 \text{ GV m}^{-1}$. Acceleration to 1 GeV can in principal be achieved within 1 cm acceleration length, substantially less than with conventional superconducting accelerators that feature field gradients in the order of 10 MV m^{-1} . The next section deals with laser-acceleration of electrons into a mostly overdense target, marking the first stage of laser-driven proton acceleration.

2.1.4 Laser energy absorption into plasma electrons

As mentioned in section 2.1.2, protons and ions cannot be accelerated directly by the laser field due to their high mass. Their acceleration is achieved indirectly by extremely high electro-static charge separation fields, like in equation (2.18), that are installed following laser-interaction with a preformed plasma at the front surface of a solid. Acting as the sole mediator of laser energy to the accelerated protons, free plasma electrons are of fundamental importance for the efficiency of the underlying interaction. The process of laser energy conversion into electron kinetic energy is often termed heating, as the final electron velocity distribution resembles a Maxwellian characterized by an average temperature T_h . Consequently, electrons that have undergone laser-heating are called hot electrons as opposed to the cold electron background in overdense target regions that are not reached by the laser* Installment of quasi-static electric fields for proton and ion acceleration has been

*Although this formulation will be adopted in this thesis for consistency with previous works, it should be noted that both experimental and numerical studies have reported on more complicated electron energy distributions.^[50,97-99]

particularly successful using largely overdense targets such as metal ($n_e \gtrsim 450 n_c$) or plastic ($n_e \sim 250 n_c$) foils,^[20] although recent studies suggest the possibility of equally good acceleration conditions when deploying targets with densities close to n_c , called near-critical targets.^[100–104] Final proton energies strongly depend on the absorption efficiency of laser energy in hot electrons,^[80] however, generating optimal absorption conditions in experiments remains challenging. Revolving around various laser and target parameters, absorption is often described through models that apply only to a certain range of those parameters. As the laser intensity scales over many orders of magnitude over time (see Fig. 2.1a), potentially more than one of those models need to be considered during a single interaction event.

An important target parameter at play is the extent of target pre-expansion at the arrival of the peak laser intensity. Upon initial plasma formation, plasma shielding and quasi-neutrality results in the establishment of an electric front field described in equation (2.18). An initially step-like plasma density profile expands freely and in a self-similar fashion into vacuum,^[92] thereby acquiring a more exponential electron density distribution, here described along z

$$n_e(z) = Z_i n_i = n_{e,0} \exp\left(-\frac{z}{L_p} - 1\right) . \quad (2.22)$$

L_p is the characteristic scale length of the expanded plasma profile calculated via $L_p = c_s t$ where $c_s = \sqrt{Z_i k_B (T_e + T_i) / m_i}$ is the ion sound speed. As mentioned above, the ion motion can be omitted here due to their substantially higher mass, such that c_s is in the order of 1 to 10 $\mu\text{m ps}^{-1}$ for average electron energies of 10 keV to 1 MeV, respectively. Plasma expansion can start at significantly earlier times than the arrival of the peak laser intensity due to preceding pulse pedestals and prepulses (refer to Fig. 2.1a). L_p is therefore frequently used to quantify so-called preplasma conditions.

Collisional absorption dominates the low intensity regime in the early phases of the laser pulse. Electrons oscillating in the laser field according to equation (2.6) dissipate their kinetic energy to surrounding electrons and ions via collisions.^[80] In the case of ion-collisions this absorption mechanism is also termed inverse Bremsstrahlung.^[105] Collisional absorption can contribute significantly to the pre-expansion of the target and the preplasma scale length L_p until collisions can be omitted at higher intensities $I_L \gtrsim 10^{17} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$ and correspondingly higher electron temperatures.^[77] Collisionless absorption models then need to be consulted, the most relevant of which have proven to be resonance absorption,^[106,107] Brunel/vacuum heating^[108] and $\vec{v} \times \vec{B}$ heating.^[109] All of these mechanisms are most effective close to the critical density surface and sometimes depend on the laser polarization, i.e. the oscillation direction of the \vec{E} -field component, with respect to the target surface. From convention follows that p -polarization indicates oscillation parallel to the plane of incidence, while s -polarization denotes oscillation perpendicular to it. In the case of normal laser incidence on the target both polarizations are parallel to the target surface, while in case of oblique incidence, only a p -polarized laser field has an \vec{E} -field component perpendicular to the target surface.

Resonance absorption is considered dominant for laser intensities $< 10^{17} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$ and significant preplasma scale lengths down to $0.1 \lambda_L$.^[105] As the laser beam im-

pinges obliquely onto the target surface it is reflected at $n_e = n_c \cos^2 \delta$, however, an evanescent field can tunnel up to n_c . In case of a p -polarized laser field, resonant plasma waves with a frequency equal to ω_L are excited. Enhanced \vec{E} -fields associated with these plasma waves lead to electron acceleration, the temperature of the most energetic ones scaling as^[105] $T_{h,RA} \sim (T_{e,0}/L\lambda_L^2)^{1/3}$ where $T_{e,0}$ is the initial electron temperature.

For higher intensities $\lesssim 10^{18} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$ and shorter scale lengths $L_p \ll \lambda_L$ in front of a highly overdense target ($n_e/n_c \gg 1$), the electron oscillation amplitude acquired in the first half laser cycle exceeds the plasma scale length and electrons are effectively pulled out into the vacuum. In the second half of the laser cycle they are accelerated back into the target and can even reach beyond the critical density surface where they experience a reduced laser field and significantly smaller restoring forces. As a result, one hot electron bunch per laser cycle is injected into the target bulk. This mechanism is called vacuum or **Brunel heating**.^[108] In a more collective picture, the laser light couples nonresonantly into an electrostatic plasma wave.^[105] The electron temperature scales as $T_{\text{hot,VH}} \sim (I_L \lambda_L)^a$ where $1/3 \leq a \leq 1/2$.^[80]

Recalling the increasing significance of the $\vec{v} \times \vec{B}$ term of the Lorentz force (equation (2.5)) for the electron motion at relativistic laser intensities $I_L \geq 10^{18} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$, a third collisionless absorption mechanism is introduced, called relativistic **$\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$ heating**.^[109] Analogous to Brunel heating, electrons oscillate in the laser field and are displaced beyond the critical density surface, where they experience a significantly reduced field. Only here, this oscillation is dominated by the \vec{B} -field term of equation (2.5) with a resulting oscillation frequency of $2\omega_L$ along z , i.e. normal to the target surface in case of normal laser incidence. The superimposed average drift as well as transverse ponderomotive scattering (refer to section 2.1.2) add to the process of ponderomotively accelerating electrons into the target bulk.

It is instructive to briefly review the temperature scaling models proposed for $\vec{v} \times \vec{B}$ heating, due to its high relevance to the laser intensity regime studied in this thesis. While for mildly relativistic intensities $I_L \lesssim 10^{19} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$, the ponderomotive electron temperature scaling^[110,111]

$$k_B T_{h,\text{pond}} = U_p = m_e c^2 \left(\sqrt{1 + a_0^2} - 1 \right) \quad (2.23)$$

applies, experimental measurements remained significantly below predicted ones for higher laser intensities.^[112] *Beg et al.*^[113] proposed an empirical scaling that better matched experimental results $k_B T_{\text{hot,Beg}} = 0.469 \cdot m_e c^2 a_0^{2/3}$. A fully analytical treatment, applying to both relativistic and non-relativistic laser intensities was introduced by *Kluge et al.*^[50]

$$k_B T_{h,\text{Kluge}} = m_e c^2 \left(\frac{\pi}{2K(-a_0^2)} - 1 \right) \quad (2.24)$$

where $K(-a_0^2)$ is a complete elliptical integral of the first kind of a steep plasma density gradient. For the extreme cases $a_0 \ll 1$ and $a_0 \gg 1$, simpler analytical

equations are given assuming a negligible preplasma amount

$$k_B T_{h,a_0 \ll 1} = m_e c^2 \frac{a_0^2}{4} \quad (2.25)$$

$$k_B T_{h,a_0 \gg 1} = m_e c^2 \left(\frac{\pi a_0}{\ln 16 + 2 \ln a_0} - 1 \right). \quad (2.26)$$

This scaling was found to agree well with experimental data recorded at a titanium:sapphire laser system with parameters comparable to Draco (10 J in 100 fs pulses at $\lambda_L = 800$ nm with 22° incidence angle onto an Al foil),^[112] with electron energies ~ 1 MeV at $a_0 = 16$.

Distinguishing different absorption mechanisms in experiments as the laser-plasma interaction evolves is challenging due to the limited temporal resolution of diagnostics compared to the pulse lengths of current day short pulse laser systems. Experiments therefore focus on measuring the total (time-integrated) absorbed energy fraction. X-ray spectroscopy of Bremsstrahlung- and $K\alpha$ -emission lines from the target bulk was performed to deduce the hot electron temperature and number of electrons accelerated by the laser at the target front.^[19,114,115] Results ranged from 10 to 50% of absorbed laser energy for relativistic laser intensities. More direct measurements featured integrating spheres around the target to collect the scattered laser light during interaction and revealed peak absorption values of 90%.^[49,116] All measurements generally agree on the observation that the absorption efficiency grows for increasing relativistic laser intensities, as predicted by the electron temperature scalings presented here.^[117,118]

Enhancing the absorption of laser energy into plasma electrons has been the subject of extensive experimental and numerical studies in the field (see ref.^[21] and references therein). As absorption is most efficient close to the critical density surface, proton acceleration performance under the presence of a near-critical density plasma in front of the target was investigated. Experimental realizations include inducing a near-critical preplasma at the target front with a controlled prepulse^[52,119-121] or applying a low density material to a target foil,^[122-125] that when ionized constitutes the near-critical plasma. Microstructuring the target surface through advanced target fabrication^[126] or excitation of surface plasma waves^[127] has been proposed to enhance hot electron generation. Manipulation of the target geometry by deploying microcone^[128-130] and mass-limited targets^[41,65,131] has been another approach to increase target heating that proved beneficial for proton acceleration. An interaction scheme that benefits from the entire target plasma becoming transparent during the interaction, allowing for a more volumetric heating,^[100,132,133] is discussed in section 2.2.3.

Fig. 2.3. a) View into the interaction chamber during laser-interaction with a cryogenic hydrogen jet target. b) Visualization of target normal sheath acceleration mechanism. The diagram schematically depicts ion and electron density distributions along the laser axis after the target has expanded for some time.

2.2 Proton acceleration from solid targets

2.2.1 Target normal sheath acceleration

Laser-driven proton acceleration relies on the efficient energy transfer from laser to plasma electrons and from those to ions (refer to Fig. 2.3 for an illustration). This is realized by the formation of quasi-static electric fields at the target surface, strong enough to field ionize carbon, hydrogen and oxygen atoms in a contamination layer and accelerate them. Electrons that were accelerated by the laser at the target front (see section 2.1.4) propagate through the target nearly without collisions and exit the target at the rear surface. Quasi-neutrality of the target is maintained by cold electrons of the bulk material.^[134] Some hot electrons may escape the target but most are re-attracted by the Coulomb potential of the remaining positively charged target ions and, hence, start to oscillate through the target. As a result, a quasi-static cloud of hot electrons extends by a Debye length, given in equation (2.15), beyond the target ions and is hence called Debye sheath. Due to charge separation between the Debye sheath and the target ions a quasi-static electric field forms at their front, the field strength of which is calculated via equation (2.18).^[92] Field strengths in the order of 10 TV m^{-1} are reached, resulting in accelerating gradients of $\text{MeV } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$, six orders of magnitudes higher than in conventional accelerators. Accelerating field gradients are oriented perpendicular to the target surface assuming no significant target deformation induced by the laser.^[39] Within common conditions of short laser pulses and few μm thick overdense targets, protons and ions are emitted along the target normal. This constitutes the basic principle of the most robust and well studied proton acceleration mechanism to date: target normal sheath acceleration (TNSA).^[6,19] Apart from target normal emission, typical TNSA ion beams feature high particle numbers at very low emittance^[7] and exponential energy spectra with characteristic cutoff energies, that relate to maximum accelerating fields.^[6] Protons

are accelerated most efficiently due to their high charge to mass ratio and therefore reach highest cutoff energies. The exponential spectral shape originates from transverse inhomogeneity of the accelerating fields as well as screening effects along the accelerating gradients. The former results from a bell-shaped Debye-sheath, its lateral radius related to the opening angle of the hot electron current in the target as well as the target thickness (see section 2.2.2). The latter results in reduced acceleration of ions initially situated deeper inside the target as they are screened from the accelerating fields by their fast predecessors.^[135] Temporal variation of the field amplitude during the set-up phase and during target expansion (see section 2.2.2) has been suggested as an additional source for spread-out TNSA energy spectra. Due to electron circulation through the target, sheath fields are set up both at the target front and rear leading to ion acceleration from both sides. However, highest ion energies are commonly observed from the target rear.^[136] The following section introduces two analytical models to describe TNSA, in particular the scaling of proton cutoff energies with laser power.

2.2.2 Scaling of TNSA proton energies

1D plasma expansion model

The model by *Mora*^[137] extends plasma expansion scenarios (see sections 2.1.3 and 2.1.4) to derive maximum proton energies. The model describes the isothermal and free expansion of the plasma's ion population that initially features a step-like density profile. While equation (2.18) describes the electric front field following the plasma's quasi-neutrality between Debye sheath and the ion front at time $t = 0$, expansion of the ion front at $t > 0$ due to the force exerted by E_{front} requires a self-similar description of the transient electric field. Evaluation of the ion fluid equations of continuity and momentum yields the self-similar expansion of the electron and ion plasma given in equation (2.22) featuring an exponential slope, the ion velocity $v_i(z, t) = c_s + z/t$ and the front field $E_{ss} = k_B T_h / (ec_s t)$. However, the self-similar solution remains unphysical for times when the ion distribution's scale length $L_p = c_s t$ is smaller than the local Debye-length $\lambda_{D,loc}$. Furthermore, the solution suggests unlimited increase of the ion velocity for $z \rightarrow \infty$. Numerical evaluation of the system at the position where $\lambda_{D,loc} = L_p$, which is established as the position of the ion front, yields an expression for the front field that is valid at any time $t \geq 0$ ^[137]

$$E_{\text{front}}(t) = \sqrt{\frac{4n_{e,0}k_B T_h}{\epsilon_0(2e + \omega_{p,i}^2 t^2)}} \quad (2.27)$$

with the ion plasma frequency $\omega_{p,i}$. The maximum ion front velocity and corresponding maximum ion energy then read

$$v_i = 2c_s \ln \left(\tau + \sqrt{\tau^2 + 1} \right) \quad (2.28)$$

$$\epsilon_{\text{max}} = 2Z_i k_B T_h \left[\ln \left(\tau + \sqrt{\tau^2 + 1} \right) \right]^2 \quad (2.29)$$

with $\tau = \omega_{p,i} t / \sqrt{2} e$.

Isothermal treatment assumes a constant hot electron temperature over time, which does not correspond to reality where electrons lose kinetic energy to the accelerated ion population.^[138,139] Limiting the acceleration time t_{acc} in $\tau = \omega_{p,i} t_{\text{acc}} / \sqrt{2} e$ is therefore prerequisite for the applicability of the expansion model. As the interaction time is naturally dominated by the driving laser pulse, t_{acc} has in some cases been set to the pulse duration τ_L ,^[52] while *Fuchs et al.* were able to empirically deduce a scaling law for long^[8] and short^[140] laser pulses

$$\begin{aligned} t_{\text{acc}} &= 1.3\tau_L & \tau_L &= 0.15 \dots 10 \text{ ps} \\ t_{\text{acc}} &= \zeta(\tau_L + t_{\text{transfer}}) & \tau_L &\sim 10 \text{ fs} \end{aligned}$$

where a minimum energy transfer time $t_{\text{transfer}} \approx 60 \text{ fs}$ between electrons and ions was identified for short laser pulses. The scaling factor ζ is introduced to account for different expansion velocities depending on the laser intensity and needs to be varied linearly from $\zeta = 3$ at $I_L = 2 \cdot 10^{18} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$ to $\zeta = 1.3$ at $3 \cdot 10^{19} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$. Convincingly, the scaling for t_{acc} holds for a number of experimental campaigns at different laser facilities and also agrees with the time when proton energies saturate according to corresponding PIC simulations.^[8,140]

Proper estimation of the electron density in the Debye-sheath, as included in equation (2.27), is assessed by considering the equivalent electron pulse with its bunch length set to the laser pulse length τ_L . The total number of electrons is given by $N_h = \alpha E_L / (k_B T_h)$ where α is the conversion efficiency of laser energy E_L in hot electron energy $N_h k_B T_h$. Estimation of α is challenging as mentioned in section 2.1.4. Conservative estimates setting $\alpha = 10 \dots 20\%$ are supported by theoretical values given in the context of $\vec{v} \times \vec{B}$ - and Brunel heating.^[109] Considering $E_L = 1 \text{ J}$ and $k_B T_h = 500 \text{ keV}$ (see section 2.1.4), the total number of electrons in the sheath is $N_h \simeq 10^{11}$. The lateral radius of the Debye sheath is calculated as $R = r_L + \tan \theta \cdot d$, determined by the focal spot radius r_L , the target thickness d and the divergence angle of the hot electrons while traversing the target θ . An additional factor $1 / \cos \delta$ needs to be considered for oblique laser incidence with an angle δ . The resulting sheath density reads^[52]

$$n_{e,0} = \frac{\alpha E_L}{\pi R^2 \tau_L c k_B T_h} \cdot \quad (2.30)$$

With the Draco pulse length $\tau_L = 30 \text{ fs}$, a focal spot radius of $r_L = 1.5 \mu\text{m}$, a typical target thickness $d = 5 \mu\text{m}$ and assuming an electron divergence angle $\theta \simeq 10^\circ$,^[52,141] sheath electron densities around $5 \cdot 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ are expected. Equation (2.30) conveniently links sheath electron density, laser energy and hot electron temperature, while additionally acknowledging the limited conversion efficiency α .

Electro-static surface charge model

The model presented by *Schreiber et al.*^[142] relies on the similarity of the accelerating system to a quasi-static condensator field. In this picture, the Debye sheath is considered a negative charge layer at a distance λ_D from the ion front and, as introduced above, extending laterally over the radius $R = r_L + \tan \theta \cdot d$. A positive surface

charge with density is $N_h e / (\pi R^2)$ is induced at the solid-vacuum boundary after being traversed by hot electrons from the target front. Considering that only the few most energetic electrons leave the foil entirely, most electrons propagate until $z = \lambda_D$, turn around and re-enter the foil. Over time, this results in an average number $2N_h \lambda_D / L_p$ of electrons that are steadily outside the foil, and a corresponding number of positive surface charges to maintain charge neutrality. A near-homogeneous electro-static field between positive and negative charges results from solving the corresponding Poisson equation, yielding

$$E_{es}(\xi) = \frac{k_B T_h}{e \lambda_D} \left[1 - \frac{\xi}{\sqrt{1 + \xi^2}} \right] \quad (2.31)$$

with the normalized longitudinal spatial parameter $\xi = z/R$. Note that E_{es} gives the same value as equation (2.18) at $\xi = 0$, which corresponds to the position of the surface. The maximum energy that ions can gain in this field when travelling to $\xi \rightarrow \infty$ is calculated as $\epsilon_{\max}^{\infty} = Z_i k_B T_h R / \lambda_D$ which can be expressed without explicit dependence on T_h as

$$\epsilon_{\max}^{\infty} = 2Z_i m_e c^2 \sqrt{\frac{\alpha P_L}{P_R}} \quad (2.32)$$

with laser power $P_L = E_L / \tau_L$, the relativistic power unit $P_R = 8.71$ GW and the absorption efficiency α of laser energy E_L into electron energy. Integration of the equation of motion results in an expression for experimentally observable maximum ion energies^[143]

$$\epsilon_{\max}^{exp} = X^2 \epsilon_{\max}^{\infty} \quad \text{with} \quad X = \tanh \frac{\tau_L}{2\tau_0} \quad , \quad \tau_0 = \frac{R}{\sqrt{2\epsilon_{\max}^{\infty} / m_i}} \quad . \quad (2.33)$$

As T_h does not appear explicitly in this formulation, all ionization, absorption and electron transport physics is included in the absorption parameter α , posing a clear difference to the fluid expansion model. The reference time τ_0 indicates how long a proton is exposed to the field of the surface charge. The Taylor expansion of X^2 around $\tau_L / (2\tau_0) = 0$ is quadratic in first order $X_{(1)}^2 = [\tau_L / (2\tau_0)]^2$, which means that the proton energy scales dominantly linear with laser power in the case of short laser pulses $\tau_L \leq 2\tau_0$. For longer pulses $\tau_L > 2\tau_0$ a square-root scaling with laser power is expected. For Draco, $\tau_0 = 18$ fs, when assuming an electron divergence angle^[52] of 10° and conversion efficiency of 10%. While operation at the threshold between linear and square-root scaling is predicted, collected experimental data suggest a linear tendency.^[39,144] Particular relevance of the Schreiber Model for the ultra-short pulse regime was established experimentally by demonstrating the importance of the very early stage or *intra-pulse phase* of the proton acceleration process.^[46]

Comment on scaling models

The scaling models presented here are two examples of quasi-static and plasma expansion models to predict the generated proton cutoff energy. While showing remarkable agreement with some experimental data, e.g. in references^[8,39,140,142],

these 1D models only describe the ion acceleration portion of the interaction, while electron heating and transport are summarized in input parameters. As such, they cannot account for 3D effects, resulting for example from a focused laser pulse with a lateral intensity profile or the radial dissipation of the Debye sheath at the target rear. Above mentioned input parameters are seldomly precisely known and are often based on assumptions derived from experiments or simulations.^[21] Parameters like the laser spot size r_L and laser power P_L may be measured in experiments to a certain precision, but the electron temperature T_e , absorption efficiency α and electron divergence angle θ are highly sensitive to interaction and transport processes in the plasma and their assessment is not straight-forward. Both T_e and α are themselves described in a number of different scaling models and their measurement in experiments has delivered varying results (refer to section 2.1.4). Furthermore, the electron temperature T_e is often considered constant, assuming thermal equilibrium conditions during the entire interaction, although experiments and numerical simulations have indicated more complicated electron energy distributions.^[97-99] This conflict is easily perceived when taking into account the time history of the laser pulse and hence different ionization dynamics (section 2.1.1), temperature scalings and absorption mechanisms (section 2.1.4) during different sections of the contrast curve (refer to Fig. 2.1a), as well as energy loss of the electron population due to plasma expansion, collisions and radiative losses.

Describing the electron population as a Boltzmann distribution as in equation (2.17) further implies nonphysical behavior like the existence of particles with infinite kinetic energy.^[21] The resulting infinite acceleration of ions, e.g. in equation (2.29), has to be contained by artificially limiting the acceleration time t_{acc} , introducing energy loss to the electron population^[138,145-147] or requiring electron energy conservation.^[148-150] In reaction to experimental observations,^[97] some scaling models include two electron populations, representing hot (laser-accelerated) and cold (bulk) electrons.^[151-153]

Quasi-static models assume no influence of propagating ions on the electron cloud and the accelerating field. This requires the assumption of substantially lower ion than electron numbers. A hybrid model without this assumption was suggested in reference^[154]. Multi-species effects on TNSA spectra induced by different ion populations were assessed e.g. in ref.^[155], describing a more realistic TNSA setting. For high laser intensities and thin or near-critical targets, TNSA scaling models may not apply anymore due the increasing influence of processes that were so far omitted in theoretical descriptions,^[147] including e.g. temporal laser contrast conditions, 3D effects and the onset of other acceleration mechanisms (refer to next section).

Drawing quantitative conclusions from the comparison of analytical scaling models with experimental results is inherently limited by the required assumptions about model input parameters. Numerical simulations are a common tool to bridge these issues, because they offer modeling of the entire interaction, starting from the laser pulse impinging on a target to the accelerated ion bunch, while resolving plasma processes evolving during the interaction on the femtosecond and nanometer scale. The particle-in-cell (PIC) method^[156,157] enables the self-consistent calculation of electromagnetic fields and currents on a discretized grid with finite-sized

macro-particles in the cells between. The algorithm bases on few assumptions, but since basic kinetic features like the plasma frequency and the Larmor radius need to be resolved in time and space, PIC simulations of solid density targets with $n_e \sim 100\text{-}1000 n_c$ easily require thousands of grid points in all dimensions, as well as thousands of time steps to cover the relevant interaction range.^[158] A high number of macro-particles is further required to cover large variations in electron density, e.g. between the expanded low-density plasma region and the highly overdense target bulk.^[21] As such, realistic PIC simulations can become computationally very costly or even exceed computational resources currently available. Coping with these constraints requires the simplification of simulation setups, mostly realized by reducing the number of dimensions, assuming lower target densities or decreasing the simulation size.^[159] Therefore, the credibility of simulation results strongly depends on the capability of the simplified numerical setup to accurately represent essential experimental conditions.

The interpretation of experimental data is best approached by considering both analytical and numerical results, and evaluating the validity of the derived conclusions in view of inherent modeling limitations laid out here.

2.2.3 Exploring the microscopic scale

Laser temporal contrast and target thickness

The quality of laser-accelerated proton beams, namely particle number and maximum energy, is crucially dependent on the target condition upon arrival of the laser pulse. More specifically, a steep plasma density gradient at the target rear leads to the most effective acceleration performance, while long ion density scale lengths may limit maximum reachable proton energies.^[139,160] Due to laser pulse parts preceding the main pulse (see Fig. 2.1b), early target expansion not only influences the absorption physics (section 2.1.4,^[49,161]) but can also severely degrade* accelerating TNSA fields.^[52,119,163,164] The amplified spontaneous emission (ASE) pedestal and prepulses, sometimes arriving as early as nanoseconds before the main pulse can be of ionizing intensity $I_{pp} \geq 10^{10} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$ and therefore initiate plasma formation and expansion. Even at lower intensities, evaporation of target material and accumulation of gas in front of the solid target leads to a preplasma once ionizing intensities are reached.^[165] Ablation or melting is associated with phase transitions of the target material from solid to gas or liquid, respectively. Their initiation thresholds depend on laser fluence, rather than intensity^[166,167] and are summarized under the term damage thresholds. If the latter is exceeded by ASE or prepulses, the morphology of the target is substantially modified by these processes and interaction conditions with the main laser pulse are changed, affecting the energy absorption or destroying the target completely in some cases. The damage threshold fluence of metals is $\sim \text{J cm}^{-2}$ for a prepulse duration of 1 ns.^[168,169]

Contrast-induced preplasma is primarily formed at the target front as the direct laser-target interaction plane, often leading to highest proton energies being ob-

*As mentioned in section 2.1.4, some studies observed that a certain amount of preplasma at the target front can also be beneficial for laser energy absorption into target electrons.^[52,120,162]

served from the target rear,^[136] that is associated with shorter preplasma scale lengths. However, even at the rear surface preplasma formation can be initiated due to hot electron propagation and refluxing through the entire target. Furthermore, the preplasma expansion at the target front can launch compressional shock waves into the target bulk.^[53,170] After propagation through the target with the velocity $v_s \sim \mu\text{m ns}^{-1}$, the shock exits the rear target surface where it may evaporate target material, and even create an ion density gradient that is harmful for proton acceleration.^[121] This effect is often mitigated by using sufficiently thick targets ($d \sim 1$ to few $10 \mu\text{m}$), such that the shock wave reaches the target rear well after the arrival of the main pulse.^[171] The shock velocity is given by^[53]

$$v_s = \frac{c_{s,0}}{2}(\sqrt{1+x}+1) \quad \text{with} \quad x = \frac{4\alpha_s}{\rho_0 c_{s,0}^2} \cdot p_s \quad (2.34)$$

where $c_{s,0}$ and ρ_0 are the material specific sound speed and uncompressed mass density, α_s is an empirical material constant^[172] and p_s is the shock pressure, which scales with laser intensity as $p_s \simeq (I_L/\lambda_L)^{2/3}$.^[173] For titanium as a typical target material, $\rho_0 = 4.53 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$, $c_{s,0} = 4.91 \mu\text{m ns}^{-1}$ and $\alpha_s = 1.02$ resulting in a shock velocity of $v_s \simeq 5 \mu\text{m ns}^{-1}$ for a prepulse intensity of $I_{pp} = 10^{13} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$. If a prepulse of this intensity is present at $t \geq -1 \text{ ns}$, it might be necessary to use foil thicknesses of $d \geq 5 \mu\text{m}$ to maximize the proton beam performance.

While given laser temporal contrast conditions dictate the minimum target thickness, it is in fact favorable to reduce laser prepulses and pedestals in order to use targets as thin as possible. Figure 2.4 displays experimental results of the scaling of proton cutoff energies with target thickness from the literature. Often, highest proton energies are reached for the thinnest targets, agreeing with the theoretical scaling model depicted as grey lines. In the following, three reasons are given why reducing the target thickness (always assuming the temporal contrast conditions allow it) can be beneficial for proton acceleration.

First, using thin targets reduces the effect of the hot electron divergence angle θ inside the target bulk such that higher rear surface charge densities are reached, which leads to higher accelerating field strengths E_{TNSA} .^[52,177] This is easily perceived by considering equations (2.27) and (2.30), revealing that $E_{\text{TNSA}} \propto (r_L + \tan \theta \cdot d)^{-1}$ with focal spot radius r_L and target thickness d . E_{TNSA} is maximized for such target thicknesses where $\tan \theta \cdot d/r_L \ll 1$.

Second, reducing the target thickness leads to reheating of the hot electrons by the laser when exiting the target front after one recirculation cycle through the target.^[184] More precisely, hot electrons propagate with v_D to a maximum distance λ_D beyond the target rear surface where they are reattracted by the positive target ions and propagate back to the target front in a time shorter than the laser pulse length. After exiting the target front, they once again experience acceleration by the laser field, which leads to an overall increase in mean hot electron temperature $k_B T_h$, and therefore in maximum proton energy, as $\epsilon_{\text{max}} \propto k_B T_h$, according to equation (2.29).^[183] Considering the distance of an electron trajectory during one recirculation event $2 \cdot (\lambda_D + d)/\cos \theta$, the number of electron circulations within one laser pulse

Fig. 2.4. Selected target thickness scans from the literature: 1^[174], 2^[175], 3^[176], 4^[68], 5^[177], 6^[60], 7^[178], 8^[179], 9^[180], 10^[181], 11^[182], 12^[39], 13^[183], 14^[48]. Grey lines show the scaling of maximum ion energy with target thickness by using equation (2.29) with $t_{\text{acc}} = \tau_L$ and including electron temperature and target thickness dependence from equations (2.26) and (2.30). The solid line represents Draco parameters with $a_0 = 16$, $\tau_L = 30$ fs and assuming an absorption coefficient $\alpha = 0.2$ and electron divergence $\theta = 15^\circ$. All parameters remain the same for the dotted (dashed-dotted) line, except $a_0 = 8$ ($a_0 = 8$, $\tau_L = 600$ fs). The model graphs are only displayed down to a target thickness of 100 nm. This represents the fact that for very thin targets, TNSA scaling models may not apply anymore, because the proton cutoff energy is dominated by effects that are not considered in the model (refer to section 2.2.2). The lower limit used here (100 nm) is only symbolic, as such effects strongly depend on the individual experimental laser and target conditions.

length is

$$N_{\text{circ}} = \frac{\tau_L \cdot v_D}{2(\lambda_D + d)} \cdot \cos \theta \quad , \quad (2.35)$$

assuming collisions are neglected. In case the lateral electron displacement $2N_{\text{circ}}(\lambda_D + d) \tan \theta$ is in the order of the focal spot radius r_L , ponderomotive scattering due to the lateral intensity gradient needs to be taken into account, leading to a reduction of hot electrons recirculating within the focal spot.^[116,185] The total distance covered by an electron with $v_D \approx c$ within a laser pulse length of 30 fs is $\sim 9 \mu\text{m}$, and typical Debye lengths λ_D are in the order of 100 nm for $k_B T_h \sim 1$ MeV. In this case, the target thicknesses should be below $4 \mu\text{m}$ to benefit from electron reheating, however, for $d = 4 \mu\text{m}$, lateral electron displacement is around $1.5 \mu\text{m}$ which is already a typical value for r_L so lateral ponderomotive scattering can render reheating ineffective. Further reducing the target thickness leads to smaller lateral electron displacement and better reheating conditions. Nevertheless, the number of electron circulations in equation (2.35) saturates if $d \ll \lambda_D$. The increase in proton energies due to electron reheating therefore stagnates for targets that are substantially thinner than the Debye length. The effect of electron reheating can also be attained by reducing

the lateral size of the target, such that electrons are reflected at the target edges and circulate back into the focus region.^[41,65,131,186]

Third, proton acceleration from very thin targets can benefit from the onset of relativistic induced transparency (RIT).^[48,61,133,174,182,187] As electrons are heated to relativistic energies by the laser, the associated relativistic mass increase $m_e^{\text{rel}} = \gamma m_e$ leads to an extended skin depth $l_s^{\text{rel}} = \sqrt{\gamma} l_s$ such that the laser can propagate deeper into the plasma and interact with a higher electron number.^[188] Decreasing the target thickness to the order of l_s^{rel} thus results in an increasingly volumetric absorption of laser energy into target electrons, which eventually promotes all cold electrons to hot, resulting in a higher average electron temperature and a stronger accelerating field for ions than for $d \gg l_s^{\text{rel}}$.^[61,63,189] Some studies report on best proton acceleration performance if the onset of complete relativistic target transparency is close to the time of the peak intensity on target.^[64,190] On the other hand, TNSA is terminated prematurely if the target turns transparent at earlier times, due to the lack of a reflecting critical density surface required for the establishment of longitudinal TNSA fields.^[64,189] Even though TNSA may be rendered ineffective under these conditions, other mechanisms described in the literature could take over, potentially leading to energetic ion beam production. In the break-out afterburner (BOA) scheme, ion acceleration in the transparency regime is supported by the Buneman-instability which is believed to efficiently transfer kinetic energy from the strongly heated electrons to the ion population.^[191–193] Coulomb explosion^[55,104,194–196] results from sufficient electron eviction from the interaction region, such that the resulting charge imbalance leads to ion acceleration due to their mutual Coulomb repulsion. Furthermore, target transparency has been associated with the formation of beneficial magnetic fields, supporting or even boosting ion acceleration.^[103,132,197–200]

The amount of transmitted light in the RIT regime can be calculated via^[187]

$$T = \frac{1}{1 + (\pi\sigma/\gamma)^2} \quad (2.36)$$

with the relativistic gamma factor $\gamma = \sqrt{1 + a_0^2/2}$ and the normalized areal electron density $\sigma = (n_e/n_c) \cdot d/\lambda_L$. Acknowledging that l_s^{rel} is density dependent implies that RIT can be reached with targets that are relatively thick and mildly overdense. For example, a plastic target with $n_e/n_c = 200$ needs to be fabricated as an ultra-thin film with $d \simeq 20$ nm to become relativistically transparent at Draco 150 TW peak intensity, i.e. $a_0 \simeq 16$. Under the same laser conditions, cryogenic hydrogen targets with $n_e/n_c = 30$ become transparent at $d \simeq 50$ nm. The heuristic scaling proposed by *Esirkepov et al.*^[62] suggests transparency onset at even thicker targets. In their scaling deduced from multi-parametric PIC-simulations, the normalized areal electron density scales with the laser dimensionless vector potential a_0 as

$$\sigma \approx 3 + 0.4 \cdot a_0 \quad (2.37)$$

A similar scaling has been observed in experiments with ultra-thin diamond-like crystal foils.^[189] For the Draco laser parameters, optimal target thicknesses following equation (2.37) are 38 nm for plastic and 251 nm for cryogenic hydrogen targets.

As a result of such considerations, near-critical density targets are often used in experiments that explore RIT.^[100,201]

Using circular instead of the so far assumed linear laser polarization, as well as normal incidence on a steep density gradient target, can mitigate premature onset of transparency. This is owed to the suppression of laser energy absorption into plasma electrons, as neither oscillating $\vec{v} \times \vec{B}$ - nor \vec{E} -field components exist perpendicular to the target surface for $\vec{v} \times \vec{B}$ - and Brunel absorption, nor any underdense plasma in front of it to support resonance absorption.^[58,202] Regardless of the lack of laser absorption, proton acceleration has been demonstrated successfully under these laser and target conditions,^[68,75,175,203,204] thereby confirming theoretical predictions of a highly efficient mechanism called radiation pressure acceleration (RPA).^[57-59] Without the $2\omega_L$ oscillating component, the ponderomotive force exerted via the $\vec{v} \times \vec{B}$ -component of the Lorentz force follows the envelope function of the laser pulse, which, upon reflection of the overdense plasma, pushes the plasma electrons inwards as a consequence of the laser's "radiation pressure", following from momentum conservation. Those electrons pile up beyond a charge depletion layer which gives rise to a reattracting electrostatic field. This field is balanced by the ponderomotive laser force, quickly installing an equilibrium position for the compressed electron layer.^[56] The resulting net amplitude of the electrostatic field is given as a consequence of the equilibrium of both forces as^[58]

$$\frac{1}{2}\epsilon_0 E_{\text{es}}^2 = \frac{1 + R_f}{c} I_L \quad (2.38)$$

where R_f is the target reflectivity. For $I_L \simeq 10^{20} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$ and $R_f = 1$, field strengths E_{es} around 40 TV m^{-1} are reached. What follows is the acceleration of ions from the depleted area towards the compressed electron layer, which is accompanied by a retreating critical density surface. In case the laser pulse is still on, it can hence penetrate beyond the initial target surface and once again compress an electron layer and subsequently accelerate the remaining ions due to its radiation pressure. This part of the RPA is called hole boring (HB).^{*} If the target is thin enough, RPA leads to the acceleration of the entire target foil to relativistic energies in the focal volume, continuously gaining energy from the laser through the constantly renewed charge separation field E_{es} .^[57] On the other hand, the foil has to be sufficiently thick such that enough electrons are available to support laser reflection in the form of a relativistic mirror.^[175] These considerations result in an optimal target thickness of $d_{\text{opt,RPA}} = a_0/n_e$ (n_e in units of n_c and d in units of c/ω_L). Due to the ballistic acceleration of the quasi-neutral plasma slab by the laser radiation pressure, this regime of RPA is called light sail-RPA or RPA-LS, owing to its initial postulation,^[208] where this method was proposed to accelerate space ships to high velocities. Following theoretical predictions, all particles are accelerated to the same velocity leading to monochromatic energy spectra where the center energy poten-

^{*}For the sake of completeness it is noted that HB can be the source of collisionless shock waves into the overdense target plasma.^[205,206] Ions that are reflected by the shock can gain velocities that are twice the shock velocity, potentially resulting in monoenergetic ion bunches as observed in a number of experimental studies.^[102,207]

tially scales more favorably with laser intensity than maximum proton energies achieved via TNSA.^[56,58,189,209]

Realizing RPA-LS conditions in experiments remains challenging due to stringent requirements to laser and target conditions. RPA with linear laser polarization requires intensities exceeding $10^{24} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$ ^[210] that are not available with current-day laser technology.* Further, if the ions are not accelerated quickly enough to relativistic velocities, instabilities can develop in the target plasma which can be both beneficial and harmful for the ion acceleration, but are generally difficult to control in experiments.^[20,75] In particular, the Rayleigh-Taylor instability originating at the target front can lead to the early onset of target transparency, thereby disrupting RPA.^[75,215] Hybrid acceleration schemes leading to increased proton energies through combinations of RPA, TNSA and RIT at different stages of the acceleration have been proposed theoretically and observed in experiments and numerical simulations.^[48,55,182,212,216,217]

Controlling target conditions upon laser interaction

Control of the laser temporal contrast is a primary prerequisite in optimizing TNSA as well as attempting to access other acceleration schemes like RPA and RIT. The time of initial plasma formation due to laser pulse parts preceding the main pulse and the subsequent expansion of preplasma on the target front and rear are sensitive starting conditions for the main interaction and hence define the final proton and ion beam quality. Laser-proton acceleration from thin targets $d \leq 1 \mu\text{m}$ is therefore often limited by laser temporal contrast conditions, as pre-expansion of the target rear degrades accelerating gradients or the entire targets are rendered transparent too early for efficient acceleration fields to be established. Unfortunately, as laid out above, it is precisely those thin targets that are necessary to optimize TNSA and access efficient RPA and RIT regimes. Pursuing the latter in experiments is therefore directly linked to actively controlling the laser temporal contrast on target.

Cleaning the contrast curve of pulse parts preceding the main pulse is performed inherently during pulse production and amplification,^[218] via cross-polarized wave generation (XPW)^[219] or saturable absorbers^[167,218] or by frequency doubling of the pulse.^[220,221] Self-induced plasma shuttering via plasma mirrors^[67,222-224] has developed into a highly efficient and widely used contrast cleaning method. On the other hand, artificial prepulses are introduced to actively tailor the preplasma scale length.^[52,119,120,140] Unfortunately, time-resolved characterization of the resulting target condition, particularly its density distribution prior to and during main pulse interaction, is challenging due to the plasma's high opacity. All plasma regions with densities exceeding the critical density are inaccessible by diagnostics relying on back-illumination of the target with an optical probe laser.^[225,226] Such diagnostic techniques, including shadowgraphy^[227,228] and interferometry,^[226,229-231] are only operational in those plasma regions that are underdense to the wavelength of

*However, already at lower laser intensities around $\sim 10^{21} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$ and linear polarization, protons from the front can be accelerated via the laser's radiation pressure and contribute to the overall proton spectrum.^[70,211,212] Some theoretical works even propose a dominance of RPA-LS at these laser conditions, given some laser and target conditions are met.^[212-214]

the utilized probe laser light. Further difficulties are posed by microscopic spatial ($\lesssim \mu\text{m}$) and ultra-short temporal (tens of fs) scales, as well as the fact that plasma self-emission masks the interaction region by overexposure of the imaging system. Reflective probing of target front and rear can provide information about the shape and velocity of the critical density surface, off of which the laser reflects.^[215,232-234] Naturally, also here the target density distribution beyond the reflecting surface remains obscure. While the development of advanced diagnostics of the target condition is constantly evolving,^[54,235-241] so are numerical computer simulations, which are indispensable tools in the analysis and interpretation of experimental results (refer to section 2.2.2).

Simulations, however, only produce meaningful results in case initial conditions match those present in the experiment.^[55] Unfortunately, reducing the complexity of the many-parameter laser-target interaction process is unavoidable as simulation time is limited and costly. This necessary simplification of simulation setups more often than not results in simulation data that differ significantly from experimental observations, hence, cannot support quantitative interpretation. Therefore, reducing the complexity of experiments accordingly can lead to actual comparability and credibility of ab-initio simulations. First, improving the laser contrast to avoid preplasma formation until the latest possible time before arrival of the main pulse reduces the required time span to be simulated. Second, using targets of low solid density reduces the demands towards resolution capabilities as well as computationally costly collision physics. Implementation and bench-marking of the latter is yet to be standardized in many broadly used PIC-codes. The same reasons apply for third, the use of single compound targets of low atomic number in order to avoid complicated ionization physics. Fourth, with the risk of undesired influence on rear surface accelerating fields, removal of the contamination layer by ablation lasers might be advantageous as their thickness and constituents is near to uncontrolled.^[242] As an alternative, the formation of targets in-situ within the interaction chamber might reduce the amount of surface contaminants.^[68,243] Fifth, detailed knowledge of the on-shot laser pulse's topology in the high-power laser focus, both temporally and spatially, is currently becoming available through advanced laser diagnostics, to be used as input parameters for simulations.^[244-247] All stages of laser-driven proton acceleration strongly depend on the peak laser intensity, therefore, including the real a_0 , as well as spatial and temporal intensity gradients in simulations could substantially improve their results.

Investigation of plasma processes in the overdense target bulk

Numerical simulations are essential in investigating the hot electron transport through the target bulk, which is inaccessible by optical probing but was found to be connected to the spatial distribution of accelerated protons.^[248] Electrons that are heated by the laser at the target front form a dense current J_h propagating into the target bulk^[80]

$$J_h = \frac{-eN_e}{\tau_L} = \frac{-e\alpha E_L}{\tau_L k_B T_h} , \quad (2.39)$$

Fig. 2.5. Experimental proton beam profiles collected with 5 μm diameter hydrogen targets (a,b) and with a 2 μm thick titanium foil (c) for comparison. Note that the gray scale was adjusted for every image individually to ensure visibility of important features. d) Optical probing images from interferometry measurements of the preplasma region at the target front (top) and rear (bottom) at 2 ps before interaction with the main laser pulse. The overdense target regions are entirely masked by plasma self emission. The density of the underdense plasma is derived from the phase shift of the interference fringes. e) Transverse magnetic field map from 3D PIC simulations. A dashed line indicates the location of the critical density surface before laser interaction. The laser is incident from the left. The filamentary \vec{B} -field structure develops as a consequence of electron streaming instabilities in the target rear preplasma and leads to proton beam deflections. Figure adapted from ref.^[51]

which results in currents in the order of 10 MA for laser energy $E_L = 3\text{J}$, pulse length $\tau_L = 30\text{fs}$, average hot electron energy $k_B T_h \simeq 1\text{MeV}$ and absorbed energy fraction $\alpha = 0.15$. Due to energy conservation, a return current of cold electrons J_c needs to exist that balances the net current and the associated magnetic fields.^[134] The return current constitutes of cold electrons from the target bulk that are available as valence electrons (only in the case of metal targets) or have become free by collisional or field ionization.^[249] In a plasma with a certain electric conductivity σ_e , the corresponding return current density j_c can be associated with an electric field E_c that inhibits the hot electrons from further penetrating the target, $j_c = -j_h = \sigma_e E_c$. As a result, substantial differences have been observed in the generated TNSA proton beam profiles when using either insulator or metallic targets in experiments.^[248] This could be attributed to the size and shape of the Debye sheath formed by the hot electrons at the rear surface of such targets.^[250,251] The hot electron propagation within the target is also subject to strong resistive magnetic fields installed by the cold electron return current, where electron refluxing in the case of thin targets

further complicates the situation.^[252]

The hot electron transport through the target is subject to plasma instabilities* that lead to current filamentation and spatial modulation of the Debye sheath and the accelerating fields accordingly.^[253] The resulting structures in the accelerated proton beam profile often serve as a primary diagnostic to investigate the properties of electron transport and filamentation in the overdense target region,^[40,51,254] not least owing to the lack of suitable optical probing techniques as mentioned above. Instabilities in the target plasma can be both beneficial, e.g. the Buneman-instability for the BOA regime,^[63,193] and detrimental, e.g. the Rayleigh-Taylor instability for RPA-LS,^[75] for the proton acceleration performance. In view of the application of laser-driven proton beams to radio-biological studies, modulated proton beam profiles are harmful as they result in an uncontrolled spatial variation of the dose and may impact the scalability of proton cutoff energies.^[40]

Figure 2.5 shows an example measurement of modulated proton beam profiles from an experiment with cylindrical targets consisting of pure solid hydrogen at the Draco laser.^[51] Interference measurements of the underdense preplasma at target front and rear revealed substantial pre-expansion due to moderate temporal contrast conditions when the measurements were conducted (see Fig. 2.5d). Laser and target conditions were met for the development of an electron streaming instability between the hot electron current and the cold return current, predominantly in the rear surface preplasma. The associated filamented magnetic fields of this Weibel or current-filamentation instability^[184,255] can reach field strengths in the order of kT. TNSA protons accelerated from the target are deflected when passing through these fields, potentially leading to the observed emission patterns (Fig. 2.5a,b).

*Plasma instabilities originate in a perturbation that subsequently grows due to a positive feedback loop.^[38]

3 Ultra-high contrast assisted proton acceleration in the transparency regime

Advancing laser-driven proton beams to meet demands posed by applications requires strategies to optimize the acceleration performance at given laser conditions. Several acceleration mechanisms have been identified as potential candidates to boost the currently achievable maximum energy when cultivated (refer to section 2.2.3). In reality, more than one mechanism is expected to contribute to the acceleration process, which on one hand increases complexity, but on the other hand delivers additional degrees of control and has recently led to the highest laser-driven proton energies reported so far.^[48] Identifying contributions from advanced acceleration schemes and discerning their influence on the resulting proton beams relies on numerical simulations, as most experimental diagnostics only record time-integrated signatures and struggle to resolve the spatial scales at play. Unfortunately, the latter equally poses problems to simulations at given computational resources, resulting in small temporal and spatial interaction windows accessible through numerical studies. Moreover, simulation results sensitively depend on the chosen input parameters, which need to be assessed as precisely as possible in experiments to ensure comparability between experimental and numerical results.^[55]

In experiments, strategies are sought to select or enhance a favorable mechanism, or even a beneficial combination of mechanisms to maximize the generated proton energies. Optimization of the overall acceleration has proven to be most viable in practice through target material and thickness scans as a function of laser parameters (see Figure 2.4 and references therein). While sheath acceleration is understood dominant for thick targets of high density, radiation pressure acceleration (RPA) contributions and acceleration concepts related to relativistic induced transparency (RIT) become more and more pronounced when reducing the target thickness and density, and may even dominate the acceleration for ultra-thin targets (refer to section 2.2.3). This however requires close control of the laser temporal contrast, as thin targets of low density are especially sensitive to pre-expansion due to pulse

parts that precede the main laser pulse.^[46,52,178,256] Therefore, enhancement of the laser contrast to a degree that the target remains overcritical until the arrival of the main pulse serves as a stable starting condition to explore and optimize RPA and RIT contributions. Another benefit of contrast cleaning lies in a reduced temporal range to be represented in numerical simulations for proper depiction of the initial interaction conditions.

Plasma mirror (PM) setups in the laser beam line are widely established tools to improve the laser temporal contrast by few orders of magnitude^[67,223,257,258] with the tradeoff of losing up to 50 % of laser energy in the process. Implementation, relying on typical operation intensities exceeding 10^{16} W cm⁻², can either be realized in the final focusing beam line directly before laser-target interaction^[259] or in a separate setup, where two focusing optics are necessary to focus and recollimate the laser beam before and after interaction with the PM substrate, respectively. As the laser impinges on the PM surface it is mainly transmitted as long as the intensity is below the ionization threshold of the substrate material. Once the intensity rises above the ionization threshold, the surface becomes a plasma which reflects the laser beam. Under optimal conditions this trigger point lies few 100 fs before the peak of the laser pulse resulting in the suppression of amplified spontaneous emission (ASE) and prepulses by few orders of magnitude and an overall steepening of the rising slope of the main laser pulse.

In a first step, a plasma mirror setup for the Draco 150 TW beam was designed and implemented to enhance the temporal contrast and allow for proton acceleration experiments with ultra-thin and low-density targets. The contrast improvement was then determined with a novel diagnostic based on self-referenced spectral interferometry,^[247] enabling single-shot contrast measurements at unprecedented intensity dynamic, temporal range and resolution. The temporal resolution of this diagnostic even allows for the first on-shot measurement of the PM switching point. It also delivers a description of the temporal pulse shape on a time scale relevant for numerical simulations.^[260] After giving an overview of the Draco laser system and the intrinsic contrast management (section 3.1), the plasma mirror setup and the resulting contrast improvement are presented in section 3.2.

In a second step, the established plasma mirror setup was used in a proton acceleration study conducted with ultra-thin targets at enhanced temporal contrast (section 3.3). In collaboration with the Ohio State University*, liquid crystal film targets (LCT) of variable thickness ranging from few μm down to < 10 nm were irradiated with contrast cleaned Draco 150 TW pulses under an incidence angle of 45° . The experimental arrangement allowed for a more elaborate set of diagnostics than realized in previous studies in the field, namely target normal and laser axis proton detectors, laser pulse transmission and reflection diagnostics and the detection of front surface electrons. A stable proton acceleration regime delivering cutoff energies around 20 MeV in the few 100 nm thickness range was established. Even higher proton energies exceeding 25 MeV were detected for thinner targets, although with greater shot-to-shot fluctuation. The onset of relativistic target transparency was observed for the thinnest targets. The combination of all diagnostics delivered

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explicit indicators for the acceleration conditions depending on targets thickness, that, in combination with simulation results, paint a more conclusive picture of the acceleration mechanisms at play.

Some results presented in this chapter have been previously published in references^[261,262]. As such, some overlap exists in several text passages and displayed figures.

3.1 The Draco laser system

3.1.1 General setup

The experimental results presented in the following were acquired at the high-power titanium:sapphire laser system Draco (**D**resden **l**aser **a**cceleration **s**ource) at Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf (HZDR). This double chirped pulse amplification (CPA) system based on a commercial PULSAR 200 system from Amplitude Technologies* separates in two laser arms with individual final amplification and compression stages, providing either PW or 150 TW pulses, i.e. 45 J or 6 J pulse energy[†] in 30 fs with a maximum repetition rate of 10 Hz.^[10] The gain medium of Draco is titanium doped sapphire (Ti:sapphire) pumped by Nd:YAG lasers that are themselves pumped by flash lamps. The resulting Ti:sapphire pulse spectrum is centered around 800 nm. Chirped pulse amplification^[9] (CPA) relies on temporal pulse stretching before amplification such that the resulting intensity is well below the damage threshold of the gain medium as well as below the critical intensity for nonlinear effects such as self-focusing (refer to section 2.1.3)[‡]. After amplification the pulse is recompressed to reach ultra-high pulse powers. Draco comprises two CPA stages and a cross-polarized wave generation (XPW) filter in between. The XPW filter allows for the improvement of the temporal laser contrast through suppression of low-intensity pulse parts. The technique relies on a nonlinear optical effect in an anisotropic crystal (CaF_2 in the case of Draco), that results in a third order dependence of the outgoing XPW signal on the time-dependent intensity of the incoming pulse.^[219] An overview of the temporal contrast management at Draco is given in the next section.

Figure 3.1 displays the schematic layout of Draco and its 150 TW final amplification and compression stage. Before entering the first CPA stage (CPA1), the pulse train generated in a commercial Femtolasers oscillator (800 nm central wavelength, 10 fs pulse duration, nJ energy) at 78 MHz repetition rate is reduced with a Pockels cell pulse picker to 10 Hz for seeding into the laser system, and pre-amplified to 10 μJ in a booster amplifier. An all-reflective stretcher then stretches the pulse to 500 ps pulse length before its amplification to 0.5 mJ in a regenerative and, subsequently, to 25 mJ in a multi-pass amplifier. Active elements in the amplification chain allow for the optimization of the spectral phase and amplitude to enable best possible final

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[†]Here the Draco design values are given before final temporal pulse compression, which reduces the pulse energy available in the experimental areas by approximately 30%. Throughout this thesis, pulse energy values are given where necessary in the description of specific experiments.

[‡]The CPA technique was recently awarded with the Nobel prize in physics.^[263]

DRACO front end & 6 J amplifier

Fig. 3.1. Schematic layout of the Draco front end, 6 J amplifier, final pulse compression and beam transport to the 150 TW experimental area for proton acceleration.

temporal pulse compression to 25 – 30 fs. In order to amplify a broad spectrum, which is a prerequisite for the generation of ultra-short pulses, higher order terms of the spectral phase and spectral intensity deviations from a top-hat profile need to be precompensated. In the case of Draco, this is achieved with acousto-optic programmable filters (AOF), which are designed to select or discard certain portions of the pulse spectrum. One AOF (Dazzler*) is situated at the exit of the stretcher and precompensates group velocity dispersion imposed on the laser pulse as it propagates through dispersive elements in the laser chain and the gain medium. The Dazzler correction terms are provided in a feedback-loop with a Wizzler*, which mea-

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asures the spectral phase through self-referenced spectral interferometry (SRSI)^[264] after pulse compression at the end of the CPA stage. Another AOF (Mazzler*) is situated in the regenerative amplifier and precompensates gain-narrowing and red-shifting, introduced to the intensity spectrum during propagation through all amplifiers. An in-air compressor consisting of two optical gratings marks the end of the first CPA stage. The aforementioned XPW-filtering of the temporal pulse contrast is performed after CPA1. Due to low efficiency of this third order process, the cleaned pulse enters the second CPA stage with only 0.3 mJ pulse energy. Analogous to CPA1, the pulse passes through a stretcher (~ 1 ns), a regenerative and a multi-pass amplifier. Two additional multi-pass amplifiers increase the pulse energy first to 100 mJ and subsequently to 1.5 J. The laser pulse is then split into two laser arms for final pulse amplification in cryogenic amplifiers, either to 6 J for the Draco 150 TW beam or to 45 J for the Draco PW beam. Cryogenic or water cooling of the last amplifier crystals is necessary to handle the heat load and reduce thermal lensing.

Both laser beams can be operated independently and in parallel due to separate vacuum compressors, laser diagnostics and experimental areas. The 150 TW beam supplies two experimental areas, one dedicated to laser-wakefield acceleration (LWFA),^[265,266] and the other to laser-driven ion acceleration.^[38,144] The PW beam is currently exclusively used for ion acceleration, although the transport beam line to the LWFA experiment is already under construction.^[10] The experimental results of this thesis were acquired with the Draco 150 TW beam.

There, final pulse compression to 30 fs and beam transport to the experimental interaction chamber occurs under vacuum and at the final beam size of 100 mm diameter. Optimal final focusing requires correction of the pulse wave front, which is distorted from its optimal flat phase during propagation over optical elements and long distances for transfer purposes. A deformable mirror corrects the wave front after final compression by altering its surface curvature via an array of 31 separate piezo electrodes according to correction terms acquired from a wave front sensor (SID4[†]). The wave front of the attenuated laser beam, as it enters the experimental area, is imaged to the sensor with high spatial resolution by an aberration-corrected microscope objective. The sensor is an integral diagnostic in the laser-target interaction chamber due to its importance for optimal final focus quality and, therefore, reproducibly high laser intensity on target for proton acceleration. Figure 3.2 displays the attenuated Draco 150 TW focus after wave front optimization at the target chamber center (TCC) at the plane of laser-target interaction. To derive the peak intensity, the pulse energy is measured with a full aperture energy sensor that is positioned in the collimated laser beam. At a measured 60 % energy transmission through the compressor, 3.6 J laser pulses reach the experimental area for final focusing. The pulse length is acquired on-shot from an in-vacuum autocorrelator,^[267] displaying stable values of ~ 30 fs. The gray value per pixel in Fig. 3.2a) is hence calibrated to display the laser power per pixel, and including spatial calibration of the focus imaging system, to intensity. The maximum of the intensity distribution is associated with the peak laser intensity, yielding $I_0 = 7 \cdot 10^{20} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$. The full width

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Fig. 3.2. Draco 150 TW focus in the experimental area for laser ion acceleration after wave front optimization. a) High dynamic range (HDR) image of the focal spot, collected over a number of shots at different camera filter settings with a calibrated set of neutral density filters. The HDR-image is reconstructed by overlaying the single images, each weighted according to their filter setting. b) Horizontal (top) and vertical (bottom) line outs of the intensity distribution in the focus. Analysis of the focus image reveals that 70 % of the pulse energy is confined to a region where the laser intensity is higher than I_0/e^2 (grey shaded area), where I_0 is the peak intensity. The radius of this region is the beam waist w .

at half maximum (FWHM) describes the diameter of the area, in which intensity values are higher than $0.5 \cdot I_0$. If not stated differently, the FWHM is used to describe the spot size throughout this thesis. In the measurement displayed here, $\text{FWHM} = 3.5 \mu\text{m}$ and the average intensity within the FWHM is $I_{\text{FWHM}} = 5 \cdot 10^{20} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$. Another parameter to describe the spot size is the beam waist w , which equals the distance between the beam center and the point where the intensity has dropped to I_0/e^2 . Following the measurement displayed here, 40 % of the pulse energy is contained within the FWHM and 70 % within $2w$, corresponding to a Strehl ratio of ≈ 0.8 .

3.1.2 Temporal contrast diagnostic and management at Draco

Control of the temporal contrast poses an important prerequisite for laser-ion acceleration experiments with thin targets. To inhibit target ionization and expansion prior to the arrival of the main laser pulse, the contrast management at Draco is aimed at reducing pulse parts preceding the main pulse on the nano- and picosecond time scale. Figure 3.3a) depicts temporal contrast curves measured after CPA1 and CPA2, representing the final status during the redaction of this thesis. It should be noted that experimental results presented throughout this chapter and the remaining thesis were acquired at different stages of intrinsic laser contrast improvement, which will be detailed where necessary. Several temporal sections along the displayed curves are identified: the nanosecond- and few 100 picoseconds

Fig. 3.3. a) Temporal contrast measurements with a scanning third order autocorrelator (Sequoia HD) after amplification to 25 mJ pulse energy and compression in air in CPA1 (pink), to 1.5J in CPA2, also compressed in air (blue) and to 6J and compression in vacuum (black). It should be noted that the in-air compressor used here is a part of the diagnostics suite and is different from the in-air compressor in the laser chain displayed in Fig. 3.1. The contrast measurement close to the intensity peak is limited by the temporal resolution of 100 fs for the Sequoia HD. b) Temporal contrast improvement achieved through cross-polarized wave (XPW) filtering after CPA1, measured before and after the XPW with self-referenced spectral interferometry at extended time excursion (SRSI-ETE).^[247] The XPW process is associated with high pulse energy losses, which is illustrated by the reduced intensity dynamic (noise level at $4 \cdot 10^{-7}$) observed in the measurement after the XPW filter (green curve). The inset shows the pulse rising edge on a few ps timescale. The grey shaded area represents a 30 fs (FWHM) long Gaussian laser pulse.

range, which is dominated by the incoherent amplified spontaneous emission (ASE), the main pulse's rising slope beginning at roughly 200 ps before the pulse peak and arising from uncompressed coherent pulse parts, and prepulses that are present on all timescales and the origin of which is sometimes unclear.

Before detailing potential contributions to the temporal contrast curve, a brief overview of contrast measuring devices used at Draco and their operation principle is given. Those diagnostic devices are either based on delay-scanning third order autocorrelation (Sequoia and Sequoia HD*) or self-referenced spectral interferometry at extended time excursion (SRSI-ETE^[247]). The operation parameters of their respective technological implementation are given in Table 3.1. The measurements displayed in Fig. 3.3a) were recorded with the Sequoia HD, the successor of the so-far primary temporal contrast diagnostic at Draco, the Sequoia. For the measurement, the diagnostic laser pulse is split and one portion is frequency doubled, while the other portion is sent over a delay stage. Both pulses are recombined in a nonlinear crystal where the third harmonic is produced as the autocorrelation signal, which is subsequently detected with a photo multiplier. Varying the time delay of the fundamental with respect to the second harmonic pulse allows for scanning over a total temporal window of 500 ps, limited by the length of the delay stage, with a resolution of 100 fs. A motorized wheel with calibrated neutral density

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	Sequoia	Sequoia HD	SRSI-ETE
Operation mode	multi-shot	multi-shot	single-shot
Dynamic range	10^{10}	10^{13}	10^8
Temporal range / ns	0.5	3	0.018
Resolution / fs	100	100	20
Spectral acceptance / nm	20	20	100

Table 3.1. Operation parameters of temporal contrast measurement devices utilized at the Draco laser.

filters in front of the photo multiplier allows scanning over an intensity dynamic range spanning 10 orders of magnitude in the case of the Sequoia. The Sequoia *HD*, featuring an extended dynamic as well as temporal range, now covering 13 orders of magnitude in intensity and 3 ns respectively, was recently implemented in the Draco diagnostic beam line.* Potential measurement artefacts result from the operation principle of third order autocorrelators, leading to postpulses appearing as false prepulses and vice versa.^[268]

A novel laser contrast diagnostic relying on self-referenced spectral interferometry at extended time excursion (SRSI-ETE) allows for single-shot measurements of the pulse contrast at unprecedented intensity dynamic of 10^8 , temporal resolution of 20 fs and temporal range of 18 ps.^[247] SRSI, as is also implemented in the Wizzler, relies on spectral interferometry between the diagnostic pulse and its temporally shifted replica (called reference pulse), the spectral phase of which is flattened beforehand by temporal filtering through XPW generation. The spectral interferogram effectively delivers a "comparison" of spectral amplitude and phase of the diagnostic and reference pulse. Assuming the phase of the reference pulse is flat and its spectral width is larger than that of the diagnostic pulse, spectral phase and amplitude of the latter are retrieved from Fourier transform (FT) processing of the the spectral interferogram.^[264] The spectral phase and amplitude are in principle sufficient to fully describe the laser pulse (and in case of the Wizzler, provide correction terms for the Dazzler), and the temporal contrast curve is directly given after FT of the spectral interferogram by singling out and squaring the interference term (AC term). The conventional implementation in the Wizzler achieves a temporal range of 5 ps and an intensity dynamic of 10^5 , which is largely insufficient to diagnose the temporal contrast of current day high-power laser systems. Extending both temporal and dynamic range is achieved by two design refinements. First, implementation of an imaging spectrometer allows for FT and subsequent filtering in both spectral and spatial domains, which extends the accessible dynamic range. Acquisition of not only the spectral but also the spatial phase in principle allows for the reconstruction of the entire laser field distribution, including spatio-temporal couplings.^[269]† Second, a small angle between diagnostic and reference beam is introduced at the plane of the spectrometer entrance slit. This eliminates the influence of aliases in the time domain which would otherwise limit the accessible time range.^[247] While the Sequoia requires several 100 laser shots to scan the same temporal window

*The nanosecond contrast outside the temporal range of the Sequoia HD can be measured with a fast photodiode in combination with calibrated neutral density filters.

†This capability is not yet implemented in the SRSI-ETE device currently used at Draco.

and dynamic with sufficient statistics, SRSI-ETE allows for temporal contrast characterization in a single shot. This delivers crucial control over proton acceleration conditions that are highly sensitive to changes in the temporal pulse profile.

Several components in the Draco laser chain can contribute to different parts of the pulse contrast displayed in Fig. 3.3a).

Base level on the ns-timescale The base level after one CPA stage is generally dominated by incoherent amplified spontaneous emission from cavity-like amplifiers like regenerative amplifiers, and in the case of CPA1, both oscillator and booster amplifier. The base level after CPA1 (pink curve in Fig. 3.3a) lies at 10^{-9} and is further reduced by two orders of magnitude by a fast pockels cell that switches at ~ 700 ps before the main pulse. Not optimized in the displayed contrast curve, the pockels cell switching is normally closer to the main laser pulse. After CPA2, the base level lies at 10^{-12} in this most recent measurement (grey curve in Fig. 3.3a). The ASE contribution is systematically restricted by optimizing pockels cell settings and the pump laser timing.

Rising slope Several components in the laser chain can contribute to the coherent rising slope of the laser pulse. However, their identification is challenging and remains work in progress. One potential source is diffusely scattered coherent light from optical surfaces in stretcher and compressor, that is collected by down-stream optics and propagates further in the laser chain.^[270] Another potential contribution arises in the Dazzler's acousto-optical crystal, which has a limited length and, therefore, limited bandwidth acceptance. Higher order spectral phase components might not be dispersion compensated by the Wizzler-Dazzler loop and could hence further contribute to the rising slope of the laser pulse.^[271]

Prepulses Prepulses can originate from various locations that are often difficult to identify, which renders prepulse mitigation challenging. In particular, prepulses that are within the pulse length of the stretched main pulse cannot be filtered with pockels cells and are thus equally amplified, allowing them to reach intensities that are sufficiently high to pre-ionize the target.

Prepulses on the nanosecond timescale can result from uncontrolled shortcuts of scattered laser light, for example in the multi-pass amplifier. If this scattered light is captured by a mirror of a later pass it can propagate further through the laser chain as a prepulse, effectively skipping beam path as compared to the main pulse. These prepulses are often longer than the main pulse because they propagate through a different amount of transmissive material, resulting in non-optimal dispersion compensation. Another source of prepulses are postpulses that are mirrored to precede the main laser pulse through nonlinear phase generation (B-integral), arising in transmissive media, e.g. the amplifier crystals or the active Mazzler material.^[272] Postpulses can arise for example due to multiple reflections of the main pulse at plan-parallel exit windows of pockels cells in the RA. Design improvements to the RA geometry can result in the suppression of such pre- and postpulses with pockels cells.

As mentioned above, the XPW efficiently improves the temporal contrast of the first CPA stage with the downside of very low energy throughput. Figure 3.3b) displays SRSI-ETE measurements of the laser pulse before (pink curve) and after (green curve)

temporal filtering. The second measurement is limited in intensity dynamic due to the low efficiency of XPW signal generation. Regardless, the cleaning effect is visible in the steepening of the rising slope, as well as in the suppression of prepulses to an intensity below the noise level of the measurement.

The interpretation of signatures along the recorded contrast curves requires knowledge over potential measurement artefacts that originate in the contrast diagnostics themselves. As mentioned before, postpulses can also appear as prepulses in the Sequoia (HD) curve (and vice versa), a process that is associated with the working principle of the third order autocorrelator. Those mirrored pulses can usually be identified due to a different signal height as compared to their respective counterpart. Furthermore, the Sequoia's bandwidth acceptance is limited to 20 nm. Spectral components beyond that wavelength range may not be represented in the contrast curve, where they would correspond to signatures in the direct temporal vicinity of the main pulse, such as the rising slope. On the other hand, diagnostics based on self-referenced spectral interferometry (SRSI) like the Wizzler and SRSI-ETE device are not limited in bandwidth and are therefore more reliable in detecting such features. The effect of the Sequoia's limited bandwidth acceptance on the reliability of detected contrast signatures is not yet determined and may be marginal. Ongoing studies are concerned with identifying and benchmarking such systematic measurement errors.

Both Sequoia and SRSI-ETE were used for pulse contrast characterization after reflection off the plasma mirror located in the experimental chamber of the proton acceleration experiment. Details on the plasma mirror setup and the achieved temporal contrast improvement are given in the following section.

3.2 Establishment of a plasma mirror setup for on-demand temporal contrast enhancement

Following the scope of this thesis, a central project was the establishment of additional temporal contrast filtering via the plasma mirror technique in the Draco 150 TW beam line to allow for experiments at variable contrast. As such, an additional control handle was provided to optimize the laser-driven proton source and to discern the influence of different parts of the temporal contrast curve on the acceleration performance. Based on previous works^[67,223,257,258] a compact recollimating single plasma mirror setup that can be operated on demand was designed, implemented and commissioned. The achieved temporal contrast improvement was characterized via third order autocorrelation (Sequoia) and SRSI-ETE.

3.2.1 Plasma mirror setup

After final pulse compression and wave front correction, the p -polarized laser pulse enters the experimental chamber dedicated to laser-proton acceleration. On-demand positioning of the motorized first turning mirror either sends the pulse directly to the target area, or through the dedicated plasma mirror (PM) setup for temporal contrast cleaning. The arrangement of the latter, including both beam line options, is displayed in Figure 3.4. Within the PM setup the laser pulse is focused by an $F10$ off-axis parabolic mirror* (OAP1 in Fig. 3.4), folded by the mirror F1, reflected off the PM substrate, folded by the mirror F2 and recollimated by the $F10$ OAP2. F1 and F2, while allowing for a compact setup (by saving approximately 20 cm along the focusing direction, i.e. the horizontal dimension in Fig. 3.4), need to withstand laser fluences of 120 mJ cm^{-2} . In the given setup no debris shielding of the OAPs is necessary as they face away from the plasma plume ejected after laser-PM interaction. As PM substrates serve rectangular fused silica substrates of dimensions $100 \times 50 \text{ mm}^2$ with anti-reflection coatings adapted to the spectral bandwidth of the laser pulse of $\sim 760 - 840 \text{ nm}$ on the front and the rear surface. The size of the substrate allows for approximately 450 shots, after which it needs to be replaced, requiring venting and opening the vacuum chamber. The substrate is situated at the so-called working point at a certain distance from the focus of OAP1, where optimal contrast cleaning without laser beam distortion is achieved. The working point location is determined by performing a fluence scan (refer to next section), resulting in a substrate position at 8 mm behind the focus of OAP1 in the current implementation.

Alignment of the PM beam line is performed at low energies via a narrow high-reflection coated column on one side of the substrate. Motorized linear stages allow translation of the PM substrate to a fresh position after each laser shot. Alignment of the PM substrate mount includes verification that the final focus position at the target for laser proton acceleration is not affected by lateral translation of the PM substrate.

*The F -number relates the focal length f to the initial beam diameter before focusing w_{init} , such that $F = f/w_{\text{init}}$.

Fig. 3.4. Plasma mirror setup. After compression the laser pulse enters the experimental chamber where it can either be sent to the target area directly or first propagate through the plasma mirror beam line, determined by the position of the motorized mirror M. Folding the beam between the off-axis parabolas OAP1 and OAP2 and the plasma mirror substrate via F1 and F2 allows for a compact setup with a footprint no larger than 1 m² at a (collimated) beam diameter of 10 cm. The zoom-in displays an on-shot image of the PM substrate recorded with a color camera.

On-shot monitoring of the PM-reflected collimated beam profile and its pointing stability is realized by focusing the leakage through mirror M in Fig. 3.4 with an F10 singlet lens into a diagnostic beam line with CCD cameras recording the laser near- and far-field, respectively. In the given setup the on-shot far-field cannot serve to monitor final focusing quality, as the wave front correction is generally performed for the high intensity focus at the target (see Fig. 3.2). The on-shot far-field, on the other hand, monitors the focused beam at a different plane along the beam line for which the wave front is not optimized to the same quality level. Whether the final focus is impaired following plasma mirror interaction can so far only be determined through target focus scans (see section 3.3). Those however, indicate no substantial deterioration of the focus quality.

Before entering the target area for proton acceleration, a motorized full-aperture powermeter can be inserted into the laser beam to measure the laser pulse energy in vacuum. This allows to assess the absolute plasma mirror reflectivity.

The temporal contrast measurement is performed with a fraction of the laser beam that is picked off with a half-inch mirror positioned just within the outer boundary of the collimated beam profile after mirror M. The diagnostic beam is transported through a 1 mm thin window and distributed either to the SRSI-ETE or the Sequoia by a flipping mirror. The Sequoia measurement of the PM-enhanced laser contrast is performed at selected time delays along the curve, as an entire measurement would be too time- and PM-substrate consuming. Due to its single-shot operation, the SRSI-ETE allows for the collection of a substantial data set and a statistical characterization of the on-shot pulse contrast within the limits of its intensity and temporal range. Largely sufficient to characterize the contrast improvement induced

Fig. 3.5. Plasma mirror fluence scan. a) Laser near-field measurements after reflecting off the PM for different PM substrate positions along z and the according fluences F . b) PM reflectivity for entire fluence scan, as measured for two different laser energies: $E_L = 3.4$ J (black markers) and $E_L = 317$ mJ (blue markers). Line graphs show plasma mirror expansion model from ref.^[273] Comparison to our experimental results gives estimates on plasma parameters: $I_{\text{ion}} = 6 \cdot 10^{12} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$, for $E_L = 3.4$ J (317 mJ): ion sound speed $c_s = 0.1 \mu\text{m ps}^{-1}$ ($0.03 \mu\text{m ps}^{-1}$) and absorption of laser energy into plasma $\alpha = 14\%$ (11%). c) Model input of simplified intrinsic laser temporal contrast curve (red) compared to Sequoia trace as measured before the PM (black).

by the PM, the good temporal resolution of 20 fs also allows for close inspection of the main pulse's leading edge including the trigger point of the PM, at which it becomes fully reflective. Powermeter, Sequoia and SRSI-ETE can be operated with and without passing the laser pulse through the PM setup, allowing for direct comparison between both configurations at full laser energy. In principle, using only a small portion of the beam for contrast measurement allows for applying the major part of the laser pulse for proton acceleration. This sets the stage for conducting simultaneous measurements to correlate the shape of the laser pulse's rising slope and the resulting proton beam performance. However, such a study is yet to be performed.

3.2.2 Characterization of the plasma mirror performance

Optimal operation conditions of the PM are explored by performing a fluence scan, that is, translating the PM substrate several millimeters along the laser axis z around the laser focus of OAP1 and recording the reflected energy with the powermeter, while monitoring the reflected intensity mode with the near-field diagnostic behind mirror M. The results are displayed in Figure 3.5a) and b). In agreement with the literature on plasma mirrors, the reflectance of the PM is at a minimum when positioned in the laser focus at $z = 0$, due to strong perturbation of the plasma surface at the given intensity of up to $10^{20} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$ ^[38,169] (spot size $\simeq 20 \mu\text{m}$ FWHM, Rayleigh range $\simeq 250 \mu\text{m}$). Performing the fluence scan at a lower laser energy of 317 mJ results in a narrower reflectivity drop and allows for a more precise measurement of the best focus position. At full energy, defocusing by $z \pm 7$ mm leads to reflectivities reaching a maximum of 90 % and decreasing for larger distances from the focus. A closer look at the reflected laser modes and reflectivities in Figures 3.5a) and b) reveal an asymmetric behavior for substrate positions before versus after the focus. Specifically, the reflected laser profile

displays stronger perturbations for $z = -4$ mm ($z = -6$ mm) than for $z = 4$ mm ($z = 6$ mm), although the fluence on the substrate should be similar for both cases. This asymmetry has been observed in previous measurements^[169] and can be related to variations in local intensity distributions between planes before and after the focus. Intensity profiles behind the focus can be interpreted as images of object planes in the collimated laser beam before focusing with OAP1, which results in smoother, more defined intensity distributions than in the case of their respective counterparts before the focus. Best operation conditions are thus expected for a PM substrate position behind the laser focus. The displayed images of the reflected laser near-field suggest an unperturbed intensity mode, and hence optimal final focusability on target, for distances larger than $z = 8$ mm, which was therefore selected as working point. This corresponds to a spot diameter of $680 \mu\text{m}$ and a mean intensity of $\simeq 2.5 \cdot 10^{16} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$ (fluence 950 J cm^{-2}) on the PM substrate, resulting in a PM reflectivity of 89%.

Depending on the temporal contrast curve, the position of the selected working point determines the time of the plasma mirror triggering before the arrival of the main pulse. A working point close to the focus leads to earlier PM triggering and less effective temporal cleaning. Larger working point distances lead to later triggering closer to the main laser pulse and, hence, more effective cleaning, as well as a higher stability against day-to-day changes in the temporal contrast curve. This however also leads to a decrease in reflected laser energy for increasingly large distances, so the best working point position is a compromise between optimal reflection conditions and energy throughput. On-shot monitoring of the reflected light mode during day-to-day operation verifies that the selected operation parameters result in a continuously stable PM performance.

The results of the fluence scan are compared with the plasma mirror model from *Shaw et al.*^[273,274], which allows for the derivation of several plasma parameters from the specific shape of the reflectivity drop around $z = 0$ mm (ref. to Fig. 3.5b). More specifically, the model determines the PM reflectivity based on the laser energy absorbed in the plasma, the shape of the plasma surface when the main laser peak is reflected and the intensity distribution of the laser spot on the PM. These properties are calculated based on the temporal contrast curve and the beam divergence, determined by the F -number of the OAP. Due to the low ASE level (see Fig. 3.3a), this calculation and the result is mostly determined by the rising pulse edge. A simplified version of the laser temporal contrast curve (Fig. 3.5c) and a Gaussian radial intensity distribution are used as input parameters. For every position z , the model calculates the time of ionization for every radial position as the time along the appropriately scaled temporal contrast curve when the laser intensity exceeds the ionization threshold I_{ion} of the PM substrate atoms. In the following time steps the ionized region expands with the ion sound speed c_s . The expanded surface is characterized by an expansion parameter, which, combined with the size of the ionized region and the absorbed energy fraction into the plasma α , determines the reflectivity. While the near-field images of the reflected beam imply partial expansion and small-scale perturbation of the PM surface (e.g. at $z = 4$ mm in Fig. 3.5a), similar to surface probing results (for instance in ref.^[232]), the PM model

Fig. 3.6. Laser temporal contrast measurements comparing the intrinsic laser contrast, measured with the Sequoia (black) and SRSI-ETE (blue) with the PM-enhanced contrast (red, where each data point is the result of averaging over 3 – 4 shots, and green, respectively). The thin red line indicates the complete course of the enhanced contrast curve at times ≤ -1 ps, and is the result of scaling the reference curve with the contrast enhancement factor. The SRSI-ETE traces are averaged over 5 shots. A number of consecutive single-shot SRSI-ETE measurements, each represented by a thin green line, are displayed in the inset, allowing stable determination of the PM trigger point. The dynamic range in the given SRSI-ETE setup is $5 \cdot 10^7$, indicated by the light blue dashed line.

relies on a more homogeneous, normally distributed expansion. For an input laser energy of 3.4 J, the resulting plasma parameter estimates are $I_{\text{ion}} \simeq 6 \cdot 10^{12} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$, $c_s \simeq 0.1 \mu\text{m ps}^{-1}$ and $\alpha \simeq 14\%$. These values agree well with the literature on plasma mirrors and femtosecond laser ionization of solids.^[137,223,274,275]

Calculating reflection conditions at the working point at $z = 8$ mm resulted in a maximum expansion amplitude of the PM surface in the order few nanometers, which can be associated with a practically unperturbed reflecting surface. This result is in agreement with smooth reflected beam modes as observed in the near-field diagnostic.

Characterizing the contrast improvement achieved with a plasma mirror is challenging, as typical contrast diagnostics either require many laser shots (delay-scanning third order autocorrelators like the Sequoia*) or, if operating single-shot, lack intensity dynamic (SRSI^[264] like the Wizzler[†] or frequency optical gating, in short FROG^[276]). As a result, only few studies of this kind exist^[258] and none that assess the on-shot contrast improvement at sufficient temporal resolution and intensity range. Such a measurement has become feasible with the SRSI at extended time excursion (SRSI-ETE) technique,^[247] described in section 3.1.2.

Figure 3.6 displays temporal contrast curves with and without plasma mirror clean-

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†Fastlite, Valbonne Sophia Antipolis, France

ing, measured on a single-shot basis with SRSI-ETE and on a multi-shot basis with the Sequoia. While the dynamic range of SRSI-ETE of $5 \cdot 10^7$ in the given setup is roughly 3 – 4 orders of magnitude lower than of the Sequoia, its temporal resolution is significantly better (20 fs as compared to 100 fs), thus enabling higher precision measurements of the rising slope of the main laser pulse. Within the intensity dynamic range of the Sequoia (10^{10}), the intrinsic ASE level (before contrast cleaning with the PM) is better or equal to 10^{-10} on the few 100 ps range before the arrival of the main laser pulse.* Prepulses in this range are efficiently suppressed by the plasma mirror and their remaining intensity after the PM is below the ionization threshold of the target for laser proton acceleration but slightly above the Sequoia detection level. This enables good characterization of the contrast improvement factor induced by PM filtering (see prepulse at ~ -230 ps in Fig. 3.6) and additionally helps identifying prepulse signatures resulting from measurement artefacts of mirrored postpulses. Postpulses are not reflected at late times after PM triggering and hence do not produce such measurement artefacts. Therefore, these artefact prepulses vanish in the PM-cleaned Sequoia curve (signal of "prepulse" at ~ -260 ps in Fig. 3.6 is in the order of the Sequoia noise level).

Comparison of the Sequoia signal with and without PM at a real prepulse yields a contrast improvement of 2 – 3 orders of magnitude. This is corroborated by both Sequoia and SRSI-ETE measurements of the rising pulse slope: at -1.6 ps the relative laser intensity is lowered from $2 \cdot 10^{-5}$ without PM to $3 \cdot 10^{-8}$ with PM.

The inset in Fig. 3.6 shows the contrast development close to the trigger point: while the curves with and without PM start to converge at ~ -1 ps, indicating the initiation of the PM triggering, the curves merge at -200 fs representing the actual switching point after which the PM causes no further contrast improvement. It should be noted that the laser intensity at the position of the pick-off mirror for contrast measurement is slightly lower (40% as deduced from the recorded near field images) than in the center of the beam. This results in a systematic measurement error of the PM triggering point of only few fs as deduced from the PM model.^[273] Compared to the temporal resolution of SRSI-ETE of 20 fs, this measurement error can be omitted.

The combined contrast measurement further reveals that about 0.1% of the entire laser energy is contained in the temporal contrast slope until the PM triggers at the given working point. This value is dominated by the few 10 ps rising pulse edge, while the ASE contribution is low enough to be neglected. Cleaning the pulse contrast with the assessed enhancement factor of $10^2 - 10^3$ then results in $10^{-4}\%$ of the total laser energy preceding the main laser pulse on target.

Of both devices, the SRSI-ETE gives the most accurate measurement of the plasma mirror effect on the rising slope of the laser, showing remarkable shot-to-shot stability of the PM switching (thin green lines in the inset of Fig. 3.6), while the Sequoia measurement is clearly limited by its comparably low temporal resolution. On the other hand, from the Sequoia trace follows that when irradiating the target with a PM-cleaned pulse, ionization of the target surface starts no earlier than ~ 3 ps prior to the arrival of the main laser pulse. Current development of an improved

*Refer to section 3.1.2 for a more recent measurement of the intrinsic Draco contrast at higher dynamic range.

SRSI-E TE device aims at further increasing the intensity dynamic to eventually reach from the peak intensity to below the ionization threshold at $\sim 10^{13} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$.

The implemented PM design realizes contrast enhancement with a single plasma mirror substrate to minimize the laser energy loss in the process. However, the arrangement can in principle accommodate a second PM substrate to further improve the laser contrast.^[277] The effect of debris produced at one of the substrates and deposited on the second and its impact on the contrast enhancement performance will need to be investigated over the course of several shots, which is a straightforward measurement with SRSI-E TE. Inserting debris shields with openings for the laser beam may become necessary.

The results presented here served as a blueprint for the subsequently implemented PM in the Draco PW beam line. Similar anti-reflection coatings lead to a comparable contrast enhancement factor. The time of PM triggering and the energy throughput there naturally depend on the fluence on the PM substrate at the given absolute temporal contrast curve.

Fig. 3.7. a) Target area with laser and particle diagnostics. b) Example film thickness measurements with white light interferometry. In the absence of interference fringes, as is the case for the thinnest targets, the thickness is determined primarily through analysis of spectrally resolved absolute target reflectivity values.

3.3 Proton and electron acceleration from liquid crystal targets at enhanced laser contrast

Efficient and on-demand contrast cleaning established through the plasma mirror setup serves as the starting point for the proton acceleration study presented in the following with ultra-thin targets. The study was conducted in a collaborative effort with the Ohio State University (OSU) and was aimed at investigating the onset of acceleration mechanisms beyond TNSA. As introduced in section 2.2.3, different effects come into play when reducing the target thickness to the order of the laser skin depth. When harnessed, such effects potentially lead to better proton beam properties than achievable through TNSA. Compared to previous experimental studies into the matter (ref. to Fig. 2.4 and references therein), the presented study features a broad diagnostic suite, which, in combination with the on-shot laser contrast measurement and preliminary PIC simulations, offers an improved perception of the acceleration process.

3.3.1 Target area for laser-driven proton acceleration

A schematic overview of the Draco 150 TW laser-target interaction area is given in Figure 3.7a), including diagnostics that were specifically selected for this experiment.^[38,144] The laser beam is focused with an $F2.5$ off-axis parabolic mirror (OAP) under an incidence angle of 45° to a focal spot size of $3 \mu\text{m}$ full width half maximum (FWHM), reaching laser intensities of $\sim 6 \cdot 10^{20} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$ at a laser energy of 2.65 J (after the PM) on target (refer to Fig. 3.2). The oblique laser incidence geometry selected for the presented study allows for multiple secondary diagnostics to corroborate the target conditions during proton beam production. In general, the primary ion diagnostics are Thomson parabola spectrometers (TP) situated along the laser axis (0°) and target normal (45°) directions, with an energy resolution of 0.5 to 1 MeV

in the energy range from 0 to 30 MeV.^[267,278,279] Particles are recorded with multi-channel plates imaged to charge-coupled devices (CCD), enabling online read-out on every shot. For a number of shots beam profiles of the accelerated protons were recorded with radiochromic film (RCF) stacks, that were moved into place on-demand at a distance of 55 mm from the target. Additional diagnostics were implemented to investigate the reflected and transmitted light upon interaction. A piece of spectralon (Lambertian scatterer) was used to collect the transmitted laser light at 138 mm behind the target, imaged to a CCD camera located outside the vacuum chamber and equipped with an edge filter that transmits wavelengths > 600 nm (Schott RG645). Some shots were performed without the edge filter. The current filter setting of the transmission diagnostic is indicated where necessary throughout this chapter. A ceramic (MACOR) screen was used to record the reflected light portion at a distance of 195 mm. The latter was imaged to cameras filtered with an edge filter for the reflected fundamental wavelength (1ω , Schott RG645) and a band pass filter for the second harmonic (2ω , Schott BG39) that observed the MACOR screen along the same line of sight by using a dichroic mirror. A final diagnostic was a sheet of calibrated LANEX^[280,281] (Kodak Biomax MS), which fluoresces at a wavelength of 546 nm upon impact of energetic electrons, to record the spatial distribution of target front-surface electrons ejected along the reflection direction. For a few shots, minimum electron energies were obtained by filtering part of the electron beam with a wedged aluminum piece in front of the screen. The linear slide target inserter (LSTI),^[282] developed at the Ohio State University (OSU), forms liquid crystal films by drawing a small volume of the liquid crystal 8CB (chemical formula $C_{21}H_{25}N$) over a few mm diameter aperture. Changes in wiper speed, frame temperature and liquid crystal volume result in film thicknesses ranging from few μm down to < 10 nm. Films are formed within the interaction chamber shortly before every shot, at the same position ($\pm 2 \mu\text{m}$) well within the Rayleigh range of the laser focus ($\sim 30 \mu\text{m}$) and with similar surface conditions. The film position was monitored with a scattered light imaging system, referenced to an alignment target imaged and placed in focus via the focus diagnostic. The scattered light imaging system confirmed that indeed every film was formed in the same plane with respect to the best focus. Film thickness measurements were performed before every shot via reflective white light interferometry with a commercial Filmetrics unit.* This technique had proven successful in measuring LCT thicknesses in previous internal OSU studies. Cross-referencing the interferometry method with independent thickness measurement techniques at HZDR,^[283] namely x-ray reflectometry^[284] and ellipsometry,^[285] verified the reliability of this diagnostic. Example thickness measurements are displayed in Fig. 3.7b).

3.3.2 Proton beam results

The proton acceleration results acquired with liquid crystal film targets are assembled in Figures 3.8 and 3.9. A target thickness scan was performed from $> 1 \mu\text{m}$ to < 10 nm, by far the broadest thickness scan conducted at Draco to this point (compare to Fig. 2.4). A striking result is the proton emission characteristic for shots

*Filmetrics Europe GmbH, Unterhaching, Germany

Fig. 3.8. a) Proton energy spectra in target normal (blue) and laser axis (red) direction at PM-enhanced laser contrast, recorded with Thomson parabola (TP) spectrometers. The laser axis signal is averaged over the few shots for which appreciable signal was detected, and as such represents an upper limit for proton numbers in this direction. b) Radiochromic film (RCF) stacks displaying the proton emission distribution for different target thicknesses (indicated along the top). All films represent results from high contrast laser-target interaction, apart from one film displaying a moderate contrast shot on a target thickness of $d = 6.5 \mu\text{m}$. c) Representative beam profiles of forward (upper right) and backward (lower left) accelerated protons from a 36 nm thick target at PM-enhanced contrast. Proton cutoff energies for this shot are 12 MeV in forward and 10 MeV in backward direction. An offset of the proton emission centroid with respect to the target normal, represented by the dark central hole on the films, is evident.

at enhanced laser contrast after the laser passes through the PM setup. Down to the thinnest targets, protons are predominantly emitted in target normal direction. Fig. 3.8a) displays target normal proton spectra for various target thicknesses (blue graphs) in comparison to an average of proton spectra observed along the laser axis (red). The majority of shots ($> 90\%$) at enhanced laser contrast show no laser axis ion signal for any thickness, and when present, the laser axis energy cutoff and yield are significantly lower than observed along the target normal at the same shot. Correspondingly, proton beam profiles measured with RCF stacks along the target normal (exemplary selection displayed in Fig. 3.8b) exhibit a well confined proton beam of small divergence ($< 10^\circ$ half angle) roughly centered around the target normal. However, for thinnest targets the onset of beam break-up is visible through the emergence of a radial streak pattern. The rightmost film shows the proton beam emission obtained from a moderate contrast shot without PM on a $6.5 \mu\text{m}$ thick target. The comparatively larger proton beam divergence is consistent with a pre-

expanded and deformed target rear surface during the main proton acceleration period. For one selected shot with a 36 nm thick target at enhanced contrast an additional RCF stack was positioned along the backward target normal direction. Figure 3.8c) shows that protons in forward and backward target normal direction are comparable in maximum energy, yield, and beam divergence, indicating similarly strong accelerating fields on both surfaces. This is a distinct indicator of effective laser pulse contrast cleaning such that even the target front remains sufficiently unexpanded for such a high accelerating gradient to form. It further indicates that radiation pressure acceleration in the light sail regime (RPA-LS) is not the dominating acceleration mechanism at the given laser and target conditions. Different from the bipolar emission characteristic observed here, RPA light sail-accelerated protons are emitted exclusively in forward direction as the entire target is accelerated by the laser pulse^[57] (see section 2.2.3).

The proton emission centroid in Figures 3.8b) and c) displays a slight offset from the target normal towards the laser axis in forward direction and the reflected beam in the backward direction. This angular shift is attributed to an intra-pulse TNSA effect where the electron distribution accelerated in the direction of the laser beam causes a sheath field asymmetry which likewise impacts the proton emission distribution,^[27] both in forward and backward direction. This observation is in agreement with an absorption dominance of the $\vec{v} \times \vec{B}$ force, the efficiency of which is generally understood to be independent of incidence angle and laser polarization. The latter was confirmed by inserting a $\lambda/2$ wave plate in the laser beam to vary the laser polarization on target between p , i.e. 45° with respect to the target surface, and s , i.e. parallel to the target surface. Inserting the wave plate lead to a decrease in overall proton beam performance by roughly a factor two, presumably due to a reduced laser focus quality resulting from inserting transmissive material in the high-power laser beam (see section 3.1). Proton cutoff energies were found only weakly dependent on laser polarization, i.e. , $\epsilon_{\max,p} = (9.6 \pm 0.5) \text{ MeV}$ and $\epsilon_{\max,s} = (7.4 \pm 1.1) \text{ MeV}$ for a target thickness of $\sim 30 \text{ nm}$. The uncertainty in ϵ_{\max} results from shot-to-shot variation. Acknowledging the limited energy resolution $\sim 1 \text{ MeV}$ of the TP spectrometers as an additional systematic error, no significant difference in proton beam performance is discerned between s - and p -polarized laser light. This corroborates the important role of $\vec{v} \times \vec{B}$ heating, where the B -field component dominates the oscillatory electron motion at the target surface.

Figure 3.9 displays maximum proton cutoff energies with (circles) and without (triangles) plasma mirror recorded on the forward target normal TP (blue) and RCF stacks (pink). Open markers indicate single shot data and filled markers show the same data averaged in thickness bins. Shots without the plasma mirror result in decreasing maximum proton energy as film thicknesses decrease below $1 \mu\text{m}$. Calculation of the shock velocity v_s from equation (2.34), using Mylar as a material of LCT-comparable solid density $\rho_{\text{Mylar}} = 0.92 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ and well-known material parameters,^[53] yields that shock formation at the target front, propagation through the target and subsequent break-out at the target rear before arrival of the main pulse is already possible for target thicknesses $d \lesssim 3 \mu\text{m}$ with a prepulse or ASE pedestal at $\sim -500 \text{ ps}$ and $I_{\text{pp}} \geq 5 \cdot 10^{11} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$. Just beyond the temporal and dynamic range accessible by the Sequoia, such a prepulse or ASE pedestal could

Fig. 3.9. a) Maximum cutoff energy of target normal accelerated protons from liquid crystal film targets. Circles (triangles) indicate data taken with (without) the plasma mirror for temporal contrast enhancement. Open markers are single data points (blue = Thomson parabola, pink = RCF), filled markers are averaged energies within thickness bins indicated by the grey background shading. Arrows indicate where RCF data represent a lower limit. A 1D proton energy scaling model^[50,137] with $a_0 = 16$, absorption coefficient $\alpha = 0.2$ and the electron divergence angle $\theta = 15^\circ$ is overlaid as a grey line. b) Ratio of maximum C⁶⁺ versus proton energies measured along the target normal direction.

therefore easily explain the observed decrease in proton beam performance at moderate laser contrast without plasma mirror. Additionally, proton numbers recorded in the laser axis TP were substantially higher without than with plasma mirror, indicating large-angle explosion-like proton emission as a result of substantial target expansion prior to the main laser interaction. Leading to a strongly deformed rear surface and the associated degradation of accelerating TNSA fields, this observation is consistent with decreasing proton cutoff energies at moderate laser contrast* reported in the literature.^[39,52,164]

On the other hand, high contrast proton results displayed in Fig. 3.9a) exhibit an overall increase in proton cutoff energy along the target normal direction as the target thickness decreases down to 300 nm, at which point the cutoff energies plateau. The observed tendency of increasing proton cutoff energies with decreasing target thickness d follows from the electron density in the Debye sheath after hot electron propagation through the target with the divergence angle θ (equation (2.30)). Thinner targets result in a smaller diameter of the sheath and hence, an increased accelerating field acting on the protons and ions in the rear-surface contamination layer.^[52,177] Saturation of cutoff energies for the thinnest targets sets in once $\tan \theta \cdot d$ is negligible compared to the focal spot radius r_L (see section 2.2.3). The model displayed in 3.9a) as a solid line is calculated using the 1D expansion model from equation (2.29)^[137] including the electron temperature scaling from equation (2.24)^[50] and the sheath electron density from equation (2.30).^[159] Remarkable

*It should be noted that the intrinsic temporal contrast of the double CPA Draco 150 TW has been significantly improved since the presented study was conducted, see section 3.1. Since then, proton energies ~ 20 MeV have again been demonstrated without plasma mirror from 2 μm thick Ti foils, refer to next chapter or ref.^[74], similar to earlier results with an optimized single CPA system.^[40]

agreement between the model and the experimental data indicates a sheath-field dominated acceleration with target conditions during interaction that are close to the idealized ones considered analytically. However, substantial shot-to-shot variation is observed for target thicknesses < 100 nm.

Following from the high carbon content in the target material, a strong carbon ion signal was detected in the Thomson parabola. Best focus shots exhibit high-yield C^{6+} traces and lower-yield C^{5+} and C^{4+} traces as the only other ion species detected apart from protons. The recorded carbon spectra do not feature spectral modulations like those frequently observed in experiments directed at RPA (e.g. refs.^[175,203]). C^{6+} maximum energies in the target normal direction follow the same target thickness dependence as proton cutoff energies down to the thinnest targets, with an average ratio ~ 3 of carbon versus proton energies (Fig. 3.9b). This observation suggests that protons and carbon ions gain energy in the same electric accelerating field E_{acc} , which follows from a simple consideration: the equation of motion of an ion in the field E_{acc} reads $dp/dt = Z_i e E_{acc}$. Integration over the acceleration time (see section 2.2.2) gives the velocity $v_i = Z_i e E_{acc} t_{acc} / m_i$ and hence the kinetic energy $\epsilon_{kin} = Z_i^2 / (2m_i) \cdot (e E_{acc} t_{acc})^2$. Assuming E_{acc} and t_{acc} remain unchanged, the ratio of ion cutoff energies of C^{6+} versus protons is $\propto Z_{6+}^2 \cdot m_p / m_{C^{6+}} = 36/12 = 3$, which is in agreement with the experimental observation, as well as general predictions for TNSA.^[142]

Remarkably, proton and C^{6+} cutoff energies remain high even for the thinnest targets irradiated in this study. This indicates that the acceleration process is neither limited by contrast conditions, nor terminated prematurely due to an untimely onset of RIT. Analysis of reflected and transmitted laser pulse parts corroborate this observation, as is detailed in the following two sections.

3.3.3 Ultra-high contrast target interaction

Proton acceleration results presented in the previous section establish that even the thinnest targets remain largely intact during the acceleration process at enhanced laser contrast. Performing target focus scans along the laser axis z can further reveal if optimum acceleration conditions are given at best focus, hence whether the highest laser intensity available with a laser system is in fact exploited for the acceleration. Decreasing the peak laser intensity on target by scanning the target position out of focus equally reduces the intensity of prepulses and, consequently, the degree of target pre-expansion.^[164,169,286] Some studies therefore observe an increase in proton energy when placing the target at some distance upstream or, symmetrically, downstream of the best laser focus.^[164]

Fig. 3.10a) displays proton cutoff energies, integrated specular reflection and transmission signals* for focus scans collected with different LCT thickness classes at enhanced laser contrast. Due to the efficient contrast cleaning with the PM in the study presented here, highest proton energies are observed when the target is positioned at the plane of the optimal laser focus throughout all target thickness classes. The optimal focus plane ($z = 0$) had been determined beforehand with the

*Absolute values of the transmission diagnostic need to be considered with caution. Refer to section 3.3.4 for details.

Fig. 3.10. a) Proton cutoff energies (blue), target reflectivity (1ω -component in red), 2ω emission (green) and transmittivity (black, recorded with the edge filter RG645 in front of the CCD) from focus scans for different target thickness classes (i-iv). Solid round markers represent averages over several laser shots (the standard deviation is displayed as error bars) while open diamond markers show shots that delivered the highest proton cutoff energy within those samples. The reflected light diagnostic was not available in all shots, resulting in fewer displayed data points than from other diagnostics. b) Representative 1ω and c) the corresponding 2ω intensity profiles observed along the specular reflection direction from moderate (no PM) and high contrast shots. Of the latter, three exemplary shots at different target thicknesses and focus positions are shown.

focus diagnostic* and the operation principle of the LSTI ensures target formation in a fixed plane. Highest proton energies coincide with low target reflectivity in 1ω and high second harmonic (2ω) generation. The latter is consistent with an intact critical density surface, which represents the primary origin of the second harmonic emission.^[288] A high efficiency of 2ω generation therefore serves as an additional indicator for good temporal laser contrast conditions.^[289] Highest target transparency values are observed for the thinnest targets of $d = 9 - 30$ nm close to the best focus position. The data in Fig. 3.10a) shows an asymmetry along z throughout all thickness classes, with the tendency of slightly higher proton energies at $z = -100$ μm than at $z = 100$ μm . This asymmetry is associated with a greater laser profile quality after ($z < 0$) than before ($z > 0$) the best focus position,^[169] as was confirmed in measurements of the defocused low-power laser spot^[290] and is consistent with the asymmetry observed in fluence scans with the plasma mirror (section 3.2.2).

Target surface conditions during laser interaction can further be scrutinized by considering the beam profiles of the reflected laser portion (1ω) and the 2ω emission, exemplary data of which is displayed in Fig. 3.10b) and c).^[289,291-293] Without plasma mirror, low signal in very diffuse beams with large emission angles is measured in both diagnostics. In contrast, operation with plasma mirror results in fairly confined reflected beams with divergence angles close to the initial beam divergence introduced by the OAP. This observation is consistent with an intact and largely flat critical density surface during reflection, which performs like a second plasma mirror.^[232] Intensity modulations observed in the 2ω profiles are expected due to the strongly intensity-dependent higher harmonic generation process.

Reflectivity measurements displayed in Fig. 3.10a) resemble the reflection curve from the plasma mirror fluence scan (section 3.2.2). Here, the drop in reflectivity for shots at best focus is consistent with the development of a hole signature in the center of the reflected beam profiles as observed in the two rightmost images of Fig. 3.10b). The hole occurs independent of target thickness and does not correspond to an increase in transmission values, hence the drop in reflectivity cannot be associated with the onset of RIT (except in Fig. 3.10a(i), refer to next section). Three different effects are thus considered to contribute to this signature. First, laser energy absorption into the plasma scales with laser intensity and is therefore highest at best focus and in the center of the beam, when considering a Gaussian radial intensity profile in the focus. This results in a decrease in reflected light from the critical density surface at the center of the laser focus, which, also when propagating away from the focus region and back into the near-field beam profile, can result in the observed hole in the intensity distribution. Second, the hole signature could derive from a slightly expanded critical density surface, resulting in a reflectivity drop similar to the one observed in the PM fluence scan (section 3.2.2) and in reflective probing studies.^[232] However, as the observed overall intensity distribution is well confined, such expansion curvature has to feature much lower expansion amplitudes than in the PM and probing cases. Ray-tracing simulations

*Without plasma mirror, highest proton energies (from thicker reference targets) were observed in the same focal plane, indicating that no additional focusing or defocusing term is imposed on the laser beam during plasma mirror reflection.^[287]

performed by *Metzkes et al.*^[232] have shown that expansion amplitudes as low as ~ 10 nm would already result in detectable distortions in the reflected beam profile. Such surface expansion amplitudes are rendered realistic when once again applying the reflectivity model^[273] with the given PM cleaned contrast curve. Third, the critical density surface could be pushed inwards by the radiation pressure of the laser pulse's rising slope,^[287,294] potentially leading to a comparable reflected beam signature as the outward expanded surface.

Determining which of these effects lead to the observed hole signature can substantially contribute to the estimation of the interaction conditions and need to be investigated in future studies. The direction of the critical density surface motion can be assessed by measuring the wavelength shift of the reflected beam spectrum.^[215] Recording the absorbed energy fraction has been convincingly demonstrated with integrating spheres,^[49,116] with the drawback of blocking the interaction region for most other diagnostics.

High contrast laser-target interaction is further corroborated indirectly by observing energetic electrons with high flux on the LANEX screen positioned in laser reflection direction. An integrated electron beam charge of up to 30 nC sr^{-1} per shot was measured with energies exceeding 9 MeV, obtained by recording the LANEX fluorescence behind different thicknesses of an Al wedge. This is similar to recent results^[90] where electrons ejected in this manner required laser interaction with a sharp density profile originating from high contrast pulse irradiation. Section 3.3.6 details the ponderomotive interaction between the accelerated surface electrons and the reflected laser pulse portion.

3.3.4 Transition to target transparency

Transmission values for different LCT thicknesses irradiated with PM-cleaned laser pulses are displayed in Fig. 3.11a). Only measurements with the same neutral density filters are included to avoid systematic errors introduced by unclear filter calibrations. Measuring with and without wavelength filter (Schott RG645, transmits wavelengths > 600 nm) results in a variation in transparency values that exceeds the observed shot-to-shot fluctuation. This is an indication for spectral modulation effects during laser transmission,^[238] adding a variable systematic error to the measurement that is not easily assessed. Absolute transmission values presented here should therefore be treated with caution. However, general tendencies can be evaluated. The most striking observation lies in a significant increase of transparency for target thicknesses $d < 30$ nm, featuring large shot-to-shot fluctuations, while for thicker targets a largely constant and relatively low transparency value offset is apparent. Classical transparency is only expected for thicknesses < 9 nm, so the observed increase in transmission can be identified as the onset of relativistic transparency (RIT, refer to section 2.2.3). In this regime, transparency occurs even for thicker targets due to the relativistic mass increase of the plasma electrons. The relativistic skin depth $l_s^{\text{rel}} = \sqrt{\gamma}c/\omega_{p,e}$ can hence serve as an estimate for the maximum target thickness $d_{\text{RIT,max}}$ that turns transparent due to RIT. Acknowledging the reduction in effective a_0 due to oblique laser incidence, $l_s^{\text{rel}} = d_{\text{RIT,max}} \simeq 20$ nm

Fig. 3.11. a) Transmitted light measurements versus target thickness (round markers) collected by imaging a Spectralon sheet and calibrated to shots without a target. Raw data images (with equal color scaling) display the upper half of the transmitted light mode (recorded with RG645 filter). Open (filled) markers show transmission values collected with (without) the RG645 filter. Blue line graphs display transparency values predicted by equation (2.36) for different electron densities. The pink line shows the time of transparency onset t_{onset} from equation (3.1), assuming a laser pulse described with a Gaussian temporal intensity envelope with FWHM = 22 fs and $a_0 = 20$, depicted in b). 2D PIC simulation results of t_{onset} collected with the same laser parameters are displayed as black crosses. c) Electron density distributions along z for two target thicknesses derived from the 2D PIC simulation at the time of peak intensity interaction. The initial position of the 70 nm target is displayed as dashed grey lines. A horizontal line indicates where $n_e = \gamma n_c$. The 10 nm thick target becomes undercritical before peak intensity interaction, while the 70 nm thick target remains overcritical until the laser pulse has passed.

for the nominal electron density of $n_e/n_c = 200$. The heuristic scaling from *Esirkepov et al.*^[62] given in equation (2.37) predicts optimal RIT conditions for even thicker targets with $d \simeq 40 \text{ nm}$. Despite the strong fluctuations, the measured transparency values are in overall agreement with the predicted thickness thresholds for RIT onset. For comparison, shots with few μm thick LCT's at intrinsic temporal contrast without plasma mirror resulted in transmission values around 40 % (measured with the RG645 filter). The transmission results were further compared with the model from *Vshivkov*^[187], that describes the amount of transmitted light in the relativistic transparency regime given by equation (2.36). Calculated values are displayed as blue lines in Fig. 3.11 a) for different electron densities.

In the previous sections, proton acceleration results, reflected laser beam profiles and efficient second harmonic generation were presented that collectively demonstrate laser interaction with an intact critical density surface, even for the thinnest targets used. Transmission values however suggest that the target becomes partly transparent during the interaction. In the following, a 1D model is introduced that illustrates the transition from a largely overcritical target, from which typical TNSA signatures are observed, to the RIT regime, where advanced acceleration mechanisms may increasingly influence the generated proton beam. The model is loosely based on RIT-descriptions found in references^[190,201], and describes the reduction

in target core density n_{core} due to expansion during laser pulse interaction. Once $n_{\text{core}} < \gamma n_c$, the target is considered relativistically transparent. Assuming areal mass density conservation during the expansion, the core areal mass is reduced by the amount in the expanded region. Using equation (2.22) for the expanded plasma density distribution, the target core density is described by

$$\begin{aligned} n_{\text{core}} &= n_0 - \frac{2 \cdot n_0}{d} \int_0^\infty \exp\left(-\frac{z}{L_p} - 1\right) dz \\ &= n_0 - \frac{2 \cdot n_0 L_p}{e \cdot d} , \end{aligned} \quad (3.1)$$

where e is Euler's number. It is further assumed that the expansion at the target front and rear, described by the same plasma scale length L_p , is determined by the ion sound speed c_s via

$$L_p = c_s \cdot t \quad \text{with} \quad c_s = \sqrt{Z_i k_B T_e / m_i} . \quad (3.2)$$

The electron energy $k_B T_e$ is calculated following the scaling given in equation (2.24).^[50] The resulting energy value is scaled with a factor l_s/d to account for laser electron heating only in the front surface skin layer. To assess the time of transparency onset t_{onset} during laser pulse interaction, the laser pulse is described by a Gaussian temporal intensity envelope function $a(t)$ (refer to Fig. 3.11b) in equation (2.24). This envelope function is further used to calculate the time-dependent ionization state $Z_i(t)$ following the BSI model in equation (2.3). Including the thus time-dependent scale length $L_p(t)$ in equation 3.1 results in an expression for the target core density for all times during the laser pulse $n_{\text{core}}(t)$. Equating $n_{\text{core}}(t) = \gamma(t)n_c$ and solving for t delivers the time of relativistic transparency onset t_{onset} within the laser pulse. Here, this equation is solved numerically for every target thickness d . The results are displayed in Fig. 3.11 (pink curve). 2D PIC simulation results* (black crosses) are included for reference. There, line-outs of the electron density along z were evaluated for every time step (see Fig. 3.11c). When the electron density decreased below the relativistic critical density, the corresponding time step was identified with t_{onset} . While the experiment was conducted with $a_0 = 16$ ($a_0 = 11$ if accounting for oblique laser incidence on target), PIC simulations and the analytical calculations of t_{onset} were performed for $a_0 = 20$, and can therefore only serve as an example case for the process of transparency onset, without allowing the derivation of quantitative conclusions on the experimental data. Convincingly, both simulations and model results exhibit similar trends and predict that for $a_0 = 20$, LCT targets with thicknesses $< 40 - 60$ nm should become relativistically transparent at some point during the duration of the laser pulse. Previous works predicted that optimal volumetric electron heating conditions in the RIT regime were achieved if the target turns transparent in the instant of peak intensity interaction t_{l_0} .^[64,190] For the chosen

*Simulations were performed with PICLS.^[295] Spatial coordinates were considered in two dimensions but particle momenta in all three (2D3V). Simulation parameters: 8CB target with density $n_e/n_c = 190$ if fully ionized, $a_0 = 20$, the laser pulse was modeled as a plane wave with normal incidence on target and a Gaussian temporal envelope with FWHM = 22 fs. No preplasma was applied (however, a 1 nm short scale length was introduced to avoid unphysical behavior at the vacuum-plasma interface), and the target atoms were singly pre-ionized.

laser parameters, simulations and the model predict $t_{l_0} = t_{\text{onset}}$ for an optimal LCT film thickness d_{opt} between 20 (simulations) and 30 nm (model). Calculating t_{onset} with laser parameters more adapted to the experimental laser setting, this condition is met for a film thickness of $d_{\text{opt}} = 25$ nm. The authors of references^[64,190] suggest that the proton beam performance decreases for thinner targets due to non-optimal laser energy absorption, which appears inconsistent with our measurements, that show high proton energy below the nominal d_{opt} .

The proposed 1D model visualizes the transition from an overcritical to a relativistically transparent target during the course of the laser pulse and is further illustrated with PIC simulation results. However, the collectivity of experimental results, consisting of proton cutoff energies and beam profiles, reflected and transmitted light values and second harmonic emission from the front surface, suggest operation at mostly overcritical target densities even for the thinnest LCT films. For the latter, laser light starts to leak through the target, although with lower integrated transmission signals than would be expected from theory and previous studies.^[61,187,189] Maximum proton energies remain high for these targets, although nominally operating below the optimal target thickness.^[62] A plausible explanation could lie in a re-compression of the previously expanded target front surface by the radiation pressure of the leading edge of the main pulse, as has been observed in recent 3D PIC simulations (e.g. refs.^[201,260]) of comparable geometry and target composition. Leading to a layer of potentially even higher electron density than initially given by the mass density of the target material, this behavior would lead to a shift of the RIT threshold towards thinner targets than predicted by the model, which does not take target compression into account. Such a threshold process of target expansion, recompression and the onset of transparency would be highly sensitive to small changes in target and laser conditions. This could serve as an explanation for the observed shot-to-shot fluctuations in transmitted light values and proton cutoff energies for the ultra-thin targets used in this study.

3.3.5 3D PIC simulation

Investigation of the transparency onset of initially largely overcritical targets and its implications on the resulting proton beam parameters through predictive 3D numerical simulations remains challenging due to the required resolution capabilities. In general, the simulation cell size should be small enough to roughly resolve 1/4-th of the plasma wavelength^[159] $\lambda_p = 2\pi c/\omega_p$, which in the case of LCT-targets in the focus of Draco 150 TW amounts to $\lambda_p/4 \simeq 50$ nm/4 $\simeq 12$ nm. However, resolving the target thickness of ultra-thin targets used in this study with sufficient grid resolution demands an even smaller cell size. At limited computational resources, this requires clever size adaption of grid cells and simulation windows. In the framework of the collaboration surrounding this study, 3D3V PIC simulations were performed by colleagues at the Ohio State University, using the computer code large scale plasma^[296] (LSP). In the simulation, 30 fs long p -polarized laser pulses with a peak intensity of 10^{21} W cm⁻² were incident under 45° on a fully ionized 8CB target with density $n_e/n_c = 184$ and thickness of either 30 nm or 300 nm without preplasma.

Fig. 3.12. Results from 3D PIC simulation with LSP. a) Laser field map in terms of the Poynting vector magnitude $|S|$ for a 30 nm (left) and 300 nm (right) thick liquid crystal film target at 20 fs after peak intensity interaction with the target front surface (t_{i_0}). The laser is incident from the left and the initial target position is indicated by blue dashed lines. b) Angular proton emission at $t_{i_0} + 300$ fs for both target thicknesses. The target normal is at $\delta = 0^\circ$ (laser axis at 45°).

The grid cell size was varied for different target thicknesses and over the simulation window, between 15 nm along the target normal and 45 nm in the two perpendicular dimensions for the 300 nm target, and 1.5 nm close to the focus region and spreading out to 12 nm at larger distances for the 30 nm target. The simulated focal spot size was reduced to $1.2 \mu\text{m}$ (compared to $3 \mu\text{m}$ in the experiment) to reduce the overall simulation window size while allowing for maximum available propagation length for the accelerated protons in forward direction.

Fig. 3.12 displays laser field maps (a) and proton emission characteristics (b) observed in the simulation. The laser transmission increases when decreasing the target thickness from 300 nm to 30 nm, indicating the onset of RIT in the latter case. Interestingly, the transmission changes by roughly a factor two between both cases (from 2% to 5%), which is in good agreement with the trend observed in the experiment (refer to Fig. 3.11a). Further consistency is observed in the proton angular emission, which, like in the experiment, is dominantly centered around the target normal for both targets, while larger emission angles are observed from the thinner target (compare to experimental proton emission data in Fig. 3.8). Cutoff energies increase from 10 MeV for the thicker to 28 MeV for the thinner target case. Preliminary interpretation of the simulation results suggests a transition from sheath field dominated acceleration from the surfaces of the largely overcritical 300 nm target, to a more volumetric, Coulomb repulsion dominated acceleration for the partly transparent 30 nm target.^[297] Further evaluation of the 3D simulation data is underway, including more elaborate parameter scans with 2D PIC to derive a conclusive picture of the acceleration scenario.

Fig. 3.13. Accelerated electrons from the target observed with a calibrated Lanex screen positioned at ~ 20 cm distance. a)- e) display electron beam distributions for different target positions with respect to the best focus at $z = 0$. The specular laser reflection is centered around 0° and its beam diameter is indicated with a dashed white line in c). Dashed black lines in d) and e) indicate emission signatures at $z < 0$. Line-outs of the electron dose, averaged vertically in the white area in b), are overlaid as white graphs in b) and e). The rectangular shadow on the left of the images corresponds to an inserted Aluminum wedge, increasing in thickness from ~ 0.5 mm at the top to a maximum of 19.5 mm at the bottom of the image. f) shows a schematic of the scattering geometry for different target positions. Note that in reality, a lateral offset of the specular laser reflection for different positions z is too small to be detected on the ceramic in front of the Lanex.

3.3.6 Electron acceleration from the target front surface

Analytical and numerical assessment of the spatio-temporal evolution of the target plasma during the laser pulse requires precise knowledge over key interaction parameters. In particular, the peak a_0 of the high-power laser focus, as well as its spatial intensity distribution and time history are some of the most influential aspects for the interaction. These properties need to be acquired in single-shot operation to allow for the investigation of threshold processes like the onset of RIT, that may be sensitive to shot-to-shot variations of laser parameters. In this sense, the SRSI-ETE technology marks important progress in diagnosing the on-shot temporal contrast curve (refer to section 3.2.2). However, the spatial intensity distribution is commonly measured in a time-integrated manner by imaging the attenuated laser focus to a camera chip (refer to Fig. 3.2) and scaling the resulting fluence map with the laser energy. The real a_0 on target is hence subject to a number of assumptions, the validity of which often remains uncertain. Therefore, on-shot assessment of the full-power spatio-temporal intensity distribution in the laser focus is a highly dynamic effort in the field, that already has led to promising new diagnostic approaches.^[244–246]

The ponderomotive force exerted by a focused laser pulse on a free electron strongly depends on the lateral and temporal intensity profile and the initial electron position with respect to the center of the pulse's intensity envelope (refer to section 2.1.2).^[85,86,298] Depending on these aspects, the electron is scattered under a certain

angle and can even gain kinetic energy during the process. Attempts to derive the peak laser intensity by focusing the laser into a material of low density and measuring the angular electron emission properties show promising results,^[299–302] but require dedicated experimental setups.

Laser-solid interaction is itself accompanied by acceleration of plasma electrons away from the target front surface. Due to $\vec{v} \times \vec{B}$ - and Brunel heating, electrons are pulled out of the target surface in the first half laser cycle and are pushed back in during the second half cycle. Most electrons are thus propelled into the overdense target bulk, leading to the hot electron population crucial for TNSA (see section 2.1.4). Some fraction however escapes into vacuum and is emitted under emission angles ranging from closely along the target surface,^[303] along the laser specular reflection^[304–308] or anywhere in between, depending on laser incidence angle, electron energy or target surface conditions.^[127,161,309–312] The angular emission characteristic can even serve as a diagnostic for the given preplasma scale length^[311] and is closely related to the dominant absorption mechanism.^[161]

Electrons accelerated from the LCT front surface at ultra-high laser contrast are displayed in Figure 3.13. Integrated charges up to 30 nC sr^{-1} were detected at enhanced laser contrast, while shots without PM resulted in no detectable electron signal. Inserting an Aluminum wedge into the electron beam in front of the LANEX screen revealed that electrons with energies exceeding 9 MeV reached the screen. Fig. 3.13a)-c) show a distinct hole in the electron angular distribution that is centered around the axis of the specular reflected laser beam. This is a clear indication of ponderomotive scattering between the emitted surface electrons and the reflected laser pulse.^[90,310,311] The electron bunch length thus needs to be in the order of the laser pulse duration with sufficient temporal overlap for such distinct signatures to develop.

Unnoticed by previous studies, the observed electron emission distribution shows a strong dependence on the target position along z with respect to the best focus position. In particular, the hole in the electron signal is only obtained in shots where the target was positioned at best focus* or upstream of the best focus ($z \geq 0$), refer to Fig. 3.13f) for an illustration of the geometry. The hole however disappears when moving the target downstream ($z < 0$) of the focus and a different, less distinct emission pattern emerges, displayed in Fig. 3.13d) and e). As mentioned in section 3.3.3, the target surface can be considered largely flat at the given contrast conditions and therefore practically acts as a second plasma mirror, reflecting the laser beam with low losses and negligible beam distortions (see Fig. 3.10b). For $z \geq 0$, the observed depletion of electron charge along the specular reflection axis is interpreted as resulting from surface electrons scattering off the ultra-high intensity laser focus. Assuming a simple scattering setup with a Gaussian laser focus, the scattering angle ϑ is linked to the difference in electron energy before (γ_0) and after (γ) the scattering process, as given in equation (2.13). Thus, analyzing angularly resolved electron spectra along the edge of the hole, following previous studies,^[299–302] could reveal trends that ultimately provide a non-invasive diagnostic for the peak intensity in the laser focus. In contrast to those works, front surface electrons are initially not

*The best focus position, i.e. $z = 0$, is associated with highest proton energies, refer to section 3.3.2.

Fig. 3.14. 2D PICLS simulation results of electron density distributions 136 fs after laser-target interaction. In a) (b), the laser pulse is focussed at $50 \mu\text{m}$ after ($100 \mu\text{m}$ before) its reflection at the target surface, marked with an orange circle (in b, the laser focus lies outside the simulation window). A hole in the electron distribution, marked by a white circle, develops in a), while at the same position in b), no hole is visible and even a slight increase in electron density is observed.

at rest but have acquired up to relativistic energies during their acceleration at the target surface, potentially rendering the scattering geometry more comparable to Thomson scattering conditions.^[313–315] This, however, needs further verification. At target positions $z < 0$, the laser focus lies before the target and the accelerated electrons are scattered off the diverging reflected laser beam. There, due to the relatively short Rayleigh length of $\sim 30 \mu\text{m}$, the intensity mode does not resemble a focus anymore and regains features of the flat-top intensity distribution. In the transition region between Gaussian beam and flat-top, indistinct electron scattering angles are observed, refer to Fig. 3.13d). However, when moving the target further downstream, once again a clearer signature emerges (Fig. 3.13e). Highest spatial intensity gradients are at the edge of the flat-top laser profile, which leads to smaller holes in the electron distribution that surround the specular reflection axis at a certain distance. The associated displacement of electrons leads to a dose increase at the center of the specular reflection direction. When optimized, integrated particle numbers of 345 pC were detected within $\pm 5^\circ$ with 20% shot-to-shot fluctuation. As mentioned above, the bunch duration is assumed to be in the order of the laser pulse length, which potentially leads to relatively high electron currents. Such electron beams could be of interest for a number of applications, for example the generation of THz radiation.^[316,317]

The observed signatures in the electron emission pattern result from an interplay between laser-acceleration of electrons at the target front that depends on temporal contrast conditions, injection of those electrons into a certain phase of the reflected laser pulse at a specific distance from the beam center, as well as co-propagation and scattering with the pulse, potentially accompanied by vacuum laser acceleration.^[86,90,318] In combination, these effects result in a distinct angular emission distribution which, if characterized concerning tendencies with laser energy,

focal spot size, pulse length, varying pulse contrast and maybe even spatio-temporal couplings, could serve as a simple, non-invasive characterization of the laser performance, that can be applied on a daily basis. Establishing the necessary connection between angular electron emission characteristic and the intensity distribution in the laser focus requires further scrutiny, which is however beyond the scope of this thesis.

Preliminary PIC simulation results reproduce the tendency observed in the presented experiment, as displayed in Fig. 3.14. The simulation was carried out with the 2D code PICLS^[295] with laser incidence under 45° on a 8CB target of density $n_e/n_c = 190$, if fully ionized. The pulse length was 40 fs and the target was singly pre-ionized and a preplasma with exponential shape and a scale length of 10 nm was applied to its front surface. Focusing of the beam envelope was adjusted such that the best focus with peak $a_0 = 20$ lies either 100 μm before or 50 μm after the target surface, with a spot size of 3.5 μm (FWHM). In overall agreement with experimental results, focusing after the target results in a hole in the electron emission along the specular reflection axis, while an increase in electron dose is observed in the same location if the laser focus lies before the target.

Based on the results presented here, follow-up experimental and numerical studies are currently being designed and conducted that evaluate the potential of the observed effect for purposes of diagnosing the laser focus properties.

3.4 Conclusion

The first proton acceleration study at plasma mirror enhanced laser contrast at Draco was presented. The Draco 150 TW temporal contrast was improved by 2 – 3 orders of magnitude by the recollimating single plasma mirror, as characterized on-shot in the experimental area with self-referenced spectral interferometry at extended time excursion (SRSI-ETE)^[247] and corroborated on a multi-shot basis with a Sequoia*. The SRSI-ETE allows for the inspection of the rising slope of the laser pulse at unprecedented intensity dynamic, temporal range and resolution. An important result is the determination of the plasma mirror switching point on a single-shot basis at (-200 ± 20) fs before the main laser pulse, which represents the first measurement of this kind.^[319] The presented single-shot contrast improvement and characterization setup will enable developing a deeper understanding, e.g. by providing input parameters for numerical studies, of the influence of the laser pulse's rising slope on the ps-timescale on the target surface preplasma density scale length, and the resulting effect on the laser proton acceleration performance. Extending these studies to even higher laser intensities is possible due to the recent implementation of a similar plasma mirror setup layout including SRSI-ETE diagnostic in the Petawatt branch of the Draco laser.^[10]

Irradiation of liquid crystal films^[282] of various thicknesses with the contrast-cleaned laser pulse revealed an increase in proton energies by roughly a factor two when going from ~ 1 μm thick to ~ 10 nm thin targets. While the minimum

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target thickness for efficient proton acceleration is often limited by the experimental laser contrast (e.g. references^[52,164]), our results show maximum proton energies, although at high shot-to-shot fluctuations, down to the thinnest targets used. On the other hand, without contrast cleaning proton energies quickly decreased below 10 MeV for $d < 1 \mu\text{m}$ and no proton signal was detected for targets below 300 nm, indicating significant target pre-expansion resulting in decaying acceleration gradients. This was efficiently inhibited when deploying the plasma mirror, as was confirmed not only by observing proton emission signatures characteristic to TNSA, but also through close inspection of the reflected light mode and the detection of high charge electron beams from the target front surface. Signatures in the angular emission distribution of the latter may serve to diagnose properties of the high-power laser focus, which in general is highly challenging and the subject of ongoing effort in the field.

Access to the relativistic induced transparency (RIT) regime was observed for target thicknesses below 30 nm by monitoring the transmitted laser light. The transmission signal increased from relatively low and stable values for a large range of target thicknesses to a maximum of $\sim 20\%$, at large shot-to-shot variations, in the RIT regime. Proton cutoff energies remained high for the ultra-thin targets, expressing no significant tendency of a beneficial or detrimental effect resulting from the transparency onset. The former would be expected as a result of a more volumetric laser-heating of the target electrons. The latter has been associated with an early onset of transparency, where the peak laser intensity interacts with a transparent target, severely limiting the absorbed energy fraction and inhibiting establishment of effective longitudinal charge separation fields.^[64,189] A 1D model was presented to illustrate the transition from an overcritical to a relativistically transparent target during the laser pulse, based on the expansion evolution of the target density distribution. The time of complete target transparency can be derived with this model, and calculated trends agreed relatively well with numerical results acquired with 2D PIC simulations. However, qualitative comparison to experimental results indicate that the target remains overcritical for longer times during the laser pulse than predicted by the model, which may be the result of a compression of the target front surface by the radiation pressure of the laser pulse. This suggests that further reduction of the target thickness below 10 nm may be necessary to reach optimal RIT conditions at the given laser contrast. Alternatively, targets of lower initial density are expected to reach RIT at larger thicknesses. Experimental investigation of the total absorbed energy fraction into the plasma electrons^[116] and diagnostic of the critical density surface velocity might deliver further insights. A 3D3V PIC study with LSP^[296] was performed at the Ohio State University* to derive a conclusive picture of the acceleration scenario with (partly) transparent targets. Preliminary results are consistent with experimental observations concerning target normal proton emission and transparency onset, and show a transition from TNSA for thicker targets to Coulomb explosion for thinner, partly transparent targets.^[297] Due to the high cost of such simulations, only few carefully selected parameters can be scanned. Less stringent requirements are associated with the numerical modeling of thicker targets with lower electron density. Therefore, alternative target

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approaches of moderately overcritical mass density have received increasing attention in exploring the RIT regime in experiments.^[71,100,102,104,201,320,321] Experimental and numerical studies of proton acceleration from cryogenic hydrogen targets, which feature electrons densities of $\approx 30 n_c$, are presented in the following chapter.

The presented study shows that the control of the temporal pulse contrast by on-demand PM filtering can substantially improve the proton acceleration performance. In view of increasing laser pulse energies with the accompanying increase of prepulse and pedestal intensities, the availability of contrast filters, in combination with on-shot contrast diagnostics and substantial flexibility in target thickness and material, will prove decisive in reaching optimal scalability of maximum proton energies with PW laser power. This is confirmed in the fact that the so far highest proton energies achieved with the Draco PW of ~ 50 MeV were generated in shots with PM contrast cleaning and thin plastic foils of $d \approx 100$ nm. Furthermore, the importance of an ever-extending diagnostic suite was demonstrated, to correlate various, mostly macroscopic and time-integrating experimental observables and deduce information of interaction conditions on the microscopic spatial and ultra-short temporal scale. Complementing this diagnostic arrangement with detectors for the spectra of higher-order surface harmonics,^[322] as well as electrons and Bremsstrahlung x-rays emitted in various directions, could deliver further information about the critical density surface motion, laser absorption efficiency and bulk electron dynamics at given laser pulse parameters. Probing the plasma with few-cycle optical laser pulses^[241] and x-rays^[54] will play an important role in this endeavor, as they offer insight into the plasma density evolution at high temporal resolution. While access to XFELs is highly limited, more compact secondary radiation sources such as laser-wakefield accelerators (LWFAs) are increasingly utilized to image ultra-fast plasma phenomena.^[323] The Draco PW and 150 TW arms can be temporally synchronized and combined in one interaction chamber, readily enabling such advanced pump-probe experiments. Ideally, snap-shot like images of the interaction, e.g. the onset of RIT, could then be linked to absorption efficiency values and maximum proton energies. Comparison with predictive numerical simulations would deliver best operation parameters to reliably maximize the performance of the laser-proton accelerator.

4 Laser-proton acceleration from cryogenic hydrogen targets

Investigation of the underlying physics governing laser-proton acceleration requires detailed knowledge over plasma processes taking place during laser-target interaction. However, experimental inspection of the latter is challenging due to small spatial and short temporal scales involved as well as the high plasma opacity (see section 2.2.3). Numerical simulations are essential tools in the exploration and comprehension of the dominating acceleration mechanism including electron transport and the growth of plasma instabilities in the target bulk, that generate the observed experimental signatures.^[40,48,51,55,75] In particular, plasma instabilities have been identified as a potential limit for maximum proton energies generated in experiments. Unfortunately, the computation power and time required for sensible numerical representation of experimental conditions frequently exceed available resources. More specifically, highly overdense and very thin targets (as were used in chapter 3) require a high degree of spatial grid resolution, which in turn limits the spatial and temporal interaction window accessible with simulations as well as the number of attainable parameter scans at the available computation power.

A plausible solution to these computational issues is proposed by advanced target technology, generating few-species and mildly overcritical targets for experimental laser-proton acceleration.^[324] More specifically, low-density liquid^[286,325-327] and cryogenic solid targets^[68,69,321,328,329] pose less stringent requirements to their numerical modeling due to low plasma densities in the range of only few $10 n_c$. Solid cryogenic targets are produced from cryogenic gases, which enables selection of either single-species (hydrogen, helium*, argon, neon etc.) or well-controlled few-species (methane, hydrogen-deuterium mixtures etc.) target constituents.^[331] This substantially reduces simulation complexity due to simpler ionization physics involved (refer to section 2.1.1) than with conventional solid density and compound

*Helium is particularly interesting regarding the applicability of pure laser generated He-beams to ion beam therapy.^[330]

foil targets.

Furthermore, continuous cryogenic target approaches are beneficial regarding several experimental aspects. First, optical probing of the interaction region from different observation angles is possible as these targets are generally free-standing without support structures in the interaction vicinity.^[225] Among other things, the preplasma expansion scale length can thus be assessed and used as simulation input parameters as mentioned above.^[51] Second, controlled prepulses can be applied to pre-expand the moderately overcritical target and explore alternative acceleration scenarios such as RPA and RIT.^[71,72] Third, taking advantage of high laser shot rates by implementing renewable and self-aligning targets marks an important step in preparing laser-driven proton sources for multidisciplinary applications.^[73] This effort is inherently linked to the mitigation of debris production associated with metallic and plastic target remnants ejected from the interaction region and adsorbed to the surrounding optical components. This has become a critical aspect in the community^[324] not least owed to the financial effort accompanying increasingly large optics for PW-class lasers. The plasma plume expanding from cryogenic targets becomes gaseous at ambient temperatures and is removed from the chamber by the vacuum pumps without accumulating on optics.

Experimental realizations of cryogenic targets range from single-shot free standing hydrogen foils^[321,328] over droplet^[329] and cluster^[332] sources to continuous jets^[68] and ribbons.^[69] First proof of concept studies with continuous hydrogen targets were performed^[51,73,333] that confirmed pure proton beam production with TNSA as the dominating acceleration mechanism. However, the achieved maximum proton energies, particle yield and beam divergence so far could not compete with proton beams obtained from metal foils.^[22]

The experiments presented in this chapter cover and extend a number of the aspects introduced above. Two proton acceleration studies with continuous cryogenic hydrogen targets of different production mechanism are presented, as well as two-dimensional PIC simulations investigating the overall proton generation mechanism and the influence of the target shape. Each of the two experimental studies represents the first demonstration of efficient proton-acceleration from the respective hydrogen target used, reaching maximum energies and particle yields comparable to shots on reference metal or plastic foils at optimized interaction conditions. The results of both experiments have been previously published in references^[74,334]. Therefore, some overlap in text and figures may exist.

The first part of the chapter presents experimental results obtained with a solid hydrogen ribbon target^[69] at the short pulse laser ELFIE (8 J pulse energy in 350 fs) of Laboratoire pour l'Utilisation des Lasers Intense (LULI, École Polytechnique). Having delivered maximum proton energies in the range of 1 MeV in previous tests at a long-pulse laser facility,^[333] here the first study applying the ribbon target on a short pulse laser is presented. The solid ribbon of 1 mm width is extruded from a cryogenic reservoir of solidified hydrogen at two available thicknesses, 61 μm and 100 μm , determined by the aperture dimensions.

The second part of the chapter presents an experimental campaign with the cryogenic hydrogen jet system^[68] at Draco 150 TW. Variation of the target shape was

realized by applying two different aperture geometries: a circular aperture with a diameter of $5\ \mu\text{m}$ and a novel, rectangular aperture of dimensions $20\ \mu\text{m} \times 2\ \mu\text{m}$ delivering a cylindrical or a planar, i.e. sheet-like jet, respectively. The technical feasibility of the latter is demonstrated for the first time and will be subject to a more thorough characterization in future experiments. Continuous target operation allows for the collection of a broad data set, enabling extensive statistical evaluation of the proton beam performance. This includes correlation of the latter to the on-shot positioning of the jet with respect to the drive laser focus, monitored by means of probe beams in two perpendicular axes. Both jet geometries deliver typical TNSA-like proton beams with an angular emission distribution that resembles those obtained from wire targets^[171,335] with exponential energy spectra terminating in cutoff energies that reach 20 MeV. Two-dimensional particle-in-cell (2D3V PIC) simulations were conducted to investigate the interaction mechanism governing the proton beam generation, as well as the influence of the target geometry on the angular proton emission distribution. The collected experimental and numerical results demonstrate that by tailoring the hydrogen jet geometry, particularly regarding its lateral confinement and overall target surface shape, the generated proton beam properties can be improved. The planar jet's dimensions lead to higher proton numbers in laser forward direction as compared to the cylindrical case, making it the favorable hydrogen jet geometry for potential applications of the generated proton beams.

4.1 Cryogenic hydrogen ribbon at ELFIE

4.1.1 Experimental setup

The experiment was carried out at the ultra-high intensity laser system ELFIE at LULI, France. ELFIE operates at a central wavelength of 1053 nm with a laser pulse length of ≈ 350 fs and a pulse energy of 8 J. Focusing to a spot size of $6\ \mu\text{m} \times 4.5\ \mu\text{m}$ FWHM results in an intensity of $10^{19}\ \text{W cm}^{-2}$ on target. The normalized temporal intensity contrast ratio is 10^{-7} up to 1.5 ps before the maximum intensity. The hydrogen ribbon was produced with the ELISE (experiments on laser interaction with solid hydrogen) cryostat developed at CEA Grenoble, France.^[69] A solid ribbon is extruded from a reservoir of frozen hydrogen, to which an exchangeable nozzle is attached. Liquid hydrogen is filled into the reservoir and cooled to a temperature near the triple point (≈ 12 K), at which the hydrogen freezes out. By heating the upper part of the reservoir the now solid hydrogen is pressed through the nozzle with a pressure exceeding 100 bar. The hydrogen forms a 1 mm wide ribbon, which flows continuously into the vacuum chamber (see Fig. 4.1a). The target dimensions are determined by the nozzle shape and can be set to either $62\ \mu\text{m}$ or $100\ \mu\text{m}$ in the current implementation. The ribbon flow speed of a few millimeter per second is controlled by the heating of the hydrogen, generating a differential pressure in the reservoir. Substantially slower than target production with the cryogenic jet ($100\ \text{m s}^{-1}$, refer to section 4.2), this flow speed poses less stringent requirements to the vacuum systems. However, during shots the ribbon target stability suffered sub-

stantially from energy originating in the laser-plasma interaction that is transported along the target and into the source. In case of the 62 μm thick ribbon target, the temperature in the hydrogen reservoir was increased sufficiently to melt the solid hydrogen and empty the entire reservoir into the vacuum chamber in a single shot. This effect was mitigated by using the 100 μm wide aperture where the reservoir operation temperature was lower and the increase in temperature on shot less critical. This technical limitation imposed a significant restraint on the shot rate achievable with this target.

The target apparatus was attached to the top of the ELFIE target chamber. Motorization in vertical direction allowed removal of the source from the target chamber center to perform reference shots on different solid foil targets. A fraction of the main laser was frequency doubled to serve as a probe beam, illuminating the hydrogen ribbon in transverse direction with respect to the drive laser axis. Imaging the back-lit hydrogen ribbon to a CCD camera allowed for its alignment before and monitoring during the shot. The main beam was focused onto the hydrogen ribbon under normal incidence at a distance of 2 mm below the nozzle. The energy spectra of the protons emitted at the target rear surface were recorded using radio-chromic film stacks (RCF) placed 5 cm behind the target. Attached to a mechanical feedthrough, RCF stacks were exchanged between shots via a separately pumped transfer chamber to avoid venting the main chamber. The latter would have required a complete heating and cooling cycle of the cryostat over the duration of a few hours. A hole in the center of the RCF stacks allowed for simultaneous measurement of the spectra with a Thomson parabola spectrometer aligned in target normal direction, which coincided with the laser forward direction. As mentioned above, reference targets (10 μm thick gold foils and 6 μm to 100 μm thick plastic foils) were irradiated during the campaign under the same laser conditions for comparison. In addition, the results were compared to a set of measurements with metal targets of different thicknesses performed prior to this campaign at the ELFIE laser under comparable experimental conditions.^[336]

4.1.2 Target stability

Although subject to a substantial spatial jitter, the ribbon target was hit in every laser shot due to its large lateral width of 1 mm. However, uncontrolled movement of the target along the laser axis was to such extent that only few laser shots were performed at the plane of the optimal laser focus. Figures 4.1b) and c) display the ribbon position with respect to the focal plane at the target chamber center (TCC) deduced from the perpendicular probing images over the course of five seconds at a probe repetition rate of 5 Hz for the 62 μm and the 100 μm thick ribbon. Only in $\sim 40\%$ (50%) of images was the 62 μm (100 μm) thick ribbon within the Rayleigh range of the laser of roughly $\pm 50 \mu\text{m}$ around the focal plane. Superimposed with this short term jitter, a slower movement on a time scale of minutes was observed, the total amplitude of which occasionally was so large that the ribbon moved beyond the target imaging field of view of 380 μm diameter. That large scale movement was attributed to bending of the ribbon, which could easily reach a total length of

Fig. 4.1. a) Front view of the hydrogen ribbon with a width of roughly 1 mm and a thickness of either 62 μm or 100 μm , depending of the nozzle used in the setup. The length of the ribbon can extend to several centimeters. b), c) Total position shift of the 62 μm thick (b) and 100 μm thick (c) hydrogen ribbon along the laser direction and relative to the target chamber center, recorded over the course of five seconds at 5 Hz. The overall jitter is dominated by a larger movement of the ribbon on a time scale of several minutes, that is not represented in the comparatively short time range displayed here.

few centimeters before breaking off. As the typical time span between aligning the target to the focus and launching a laser shot was in the range of several minutes, the actual on-shot position measured did not correspond to the best focus position because the target had drifted away in the meantime. As a result, the majority of shots was performed at non-optimal focusing conditions leading to a systematically lower proton acceleration performance. Nevertheless, proton energies higher than 10 MeV were achieved in 30% of the shots. For comparability to the results with foil targets, for which optimal alignment to the laser focus was easily achieved, only two shots on the hydrogen ribbon that delivered the highest proton energies are considered for subsequent analysis in the following section.

4.1.3 Proton acceleration results

Figure 4.2a) shows proton energy spectra of the two best performing shots for the different hydrogen target thicknesses compared to a 10 μm thick gold and a 25 μm thick plastic foil, recorded with RCF stacks in forward direction. All three target types deliver similar proton emission profiles as displayed in the upper part of Fig. 4.2a) and the expected exponential behavior of typical TNSA energy spectra. Energy spectra from hydrogen (red and blue) and from plastic (pink) exhibit similar shapes and cutoff energies of ~ 14 MeV. The gold foil (black squares) leads to a maximum proton energy of 18 MeV, 28% higher than the best performing hydrogen ribbon, as well as a slightly higher overall proton number. Proton beams from the hydrogen ribbon show a standard TNSA-like divergence of roughly 30° full opening angle.^[7] As the ribbon was shot only a few millimeters below the cryostat, the nozzle blocks a small section of the upper proton beam profile.

A comparison of the maximum proton energies from hydrogen, metal and plastic targets is given in Fig. 4.2b). Each data point for the hydrogen ribbon marks the proton energy of the best performing shot for the specific target type. Maximum

Fig. 4.2. a) Energy spectra for different hydrogen, plastic (PET) and gold targets recorded with RCF stacks, the 10 MeV layer of which is displayed above the diagram. In case of the hydrogen ribbon, the shadow of the nozzle is visible in the upper part of the film. b) Maximum proton energies for different target types. The gold and aluminum foil reference measurements (gray symbols) were collected in an earlier run^[336] and verified with a 10 μm gold target (black dot). The displayed data points for hydrogen are mean values from the best two shots each.

proton energies from the hydrogen target, i.e. 13 MeV and 14 MeV from the 100 μm and 62 μm thick ribbon respectively, are displayed as red dots. Several cutoff energies from different metal and plastic targets are shown. Complementary to the 10 μm thick gold foil (black marker), maximum energies for aluminum and gold foils with thicknesses varying from 0.75 μm up to 62 μm from previous measurements at ELFIE are displayed as gray symbols.^[336] Those previous measurements show a maximum in proton energy of 19 MeV at a foil thickness of 6 μm and are in good agreement with the reference shot from the present study on a 10 μm gold target. Plastic targets with an electron density between hydrogen and metal, were varied in target thickness between 5 μm and 100 μm (pink triangles) and delivered maximum proton energies for 25 μm thickness. At 13 MeV, the cutoff energies from the 25 μm plastic foil is comparable to that obtained from the hydrogen targets.

As demonstrated in the previous chapter and in Figure 2.4, thin targets are more sensitive to poor laser temporal contrast conditions than thick targets (refer to section 2.2.3 and chapter 3). Therefore, usually an optimal target thickness is observed, for which highest proton energies are achieved.^[52] Targets that are thinner than the optimal target thickness experience substantial rear surface expansion induced by laser pulse parts preceding the main pulse (see section 2.2.3). This is accompanied by a degradation of accelerating fields, leading to a decrease in observed proton cutoff energies.^[52] Here, the optimal thickness of the heavy metal targets is around 6 μm, as observed in Figure 4.2b). In case of the lighter plastic targets, target pre-expansion becomes relevant at even thicker targets around 20 μm, leading to the observed decrease in proton energies. Variation of the hydrogen ribbon thickness between 62 μm and 100 μm does not result in a significant effect on proton cutoff energies. Further reducing the thickness would probably lead to

Fig. 4.3. a) Schematic overview of the experimental arrangement around the target chamber center (TCC) with the planar jet oriented normal to the incoming laser beam. b) Images of the cold cylindrical and planar jet as observed along the main laser axis and an on-shot side view of the cylindrical jet at 3.5 ps after the main pulse. The low jet transparency indicates that it was entirely ionized at this probe timing. Light from plasma self-emission is observed in the center of the jet.

decreasing proton energies, due to an even lower electron density than that of plastic and higher sensibility to contrast conditions. Implementation of temporal contrast enhancement, for example with a plasma mirror, could resolve this issue in future studies and enable better TNSA performance. In combination with substantially thinner hydrogen ribbons, this could lead to higher proton cutoff energies. A number of technological improvements on the ELISE cryostat are currently pursued in order to reduce the ribbon thickness. For optimal TNSA conditions on an ultra-short pulse laser like Draco, thicknesses of few μm and lower would be required. The cryogenic hydrogen jet technology, presented in the following section, is better adapted to Draco laser parameters. It also offers higher flexibility in target thickness and shape. Combined with on-demand contrast cleaning with the plasma mirror introduced in chapter 3, optimal TNSA conditions are more easily explored.

4.2 Cryogenic hydrogen jet at Draco 150 TW

4.2.1 Experimental setup

The experiment was performed with the 150 TW Draco laser in the same experimental area introduced in section 3.2. Figure 4.3a) gives an overview of the adapted experimental arrangement. At a lower laser shot rate, the single recollimating plasma mirror (PM) setup (section 3.2.2) was used on demand to enhance the temporal contrast. The jet apparatus injects a cryogenically cooled hydrogen liquid through a micrometer sized aperture into vacuum.^[68] For the chosen source parameters, that is, a temperature of $\sim 18\text{ K}$ and absolute pressure $\sim 4\text{ bar}$, the hydrogen flow is laminar at velocities of about 100 m s^{-1} . Two picosecond probe beams,^[225,337] aligned along and perpendicular to the drive laser axis and synchro-

nized as precisely as ± 2 ps to the drive pulse, monitored the on-shot jet position with respect to the laser focus with an accuracy of $1\ \mu\text{m}$. Selecting a wavelength of $515\ \text{nm}$ permitted the probe light to be better distinguished from the predominant plasma self-emission accompanying the laser target interaction.^[338] The plasma self-emission spectrum is peaked in the range of the fundamental and harmonic frequencies of the drive laser pulse.

Two different jet geometries were generated and compared: cylindrical with a nominal diameter of $5\ \mu\text{m}$ and planar of about $20\ \mu\text{m}$ width and $2\ \mu\text{m}$ thickness. Both jet shapes are depicted in Figure 4.3b) as observed along the main laser axis, with a third image showing an on-shot side view of the cylindrical jet at $3.5\ \text{ps}$ after interaction with the drive laser. Volumetric density modulations along the jet axis, as are observed in the images of the cold jet, can be attributed to the hydrodynamic Plateau-Rayleigh instability that occurs during solidification of the hydrogen liquid.^[339] The jet was aligned with respect to the laser focus using a two-axis actuator unit.

As with the ribbon target, energy originating in the laser-plasma interaction resulted in small damages to the aperture of the planar jet, which consisted of a material more sensitive to heat than the cylindrical jet aperture. Those damages rendered the jet production unstable and could even lead to its complete disruption. As compared to the cylindrical jet, operation of the planar jet was therefore associated with lower shot rates.

Ion detectors consisted of two Thomson parabolas (TP) that were aligned along the drive laser axis and under 45° , and radio-chromic film (RCF) stacks at a distance of $45\ \text{mm}$ behind the target to diagnose the proton beam profile. In case no RCF-stack was irradiated, the transmitted laser light was recorded by imaging a ceramic screen installed at a distance of $125\ \text{mm}$ behind the target to a CCD camera equipped with an interference filter optimized to the Ti:sapphire wavelength spectrum ($800\ \text{nm} \pm 50\ \text{nm}$) and located outside the experimental chamber. A hole in the center of the ceramic screen allowed for simultaneous detection of proton spectra in the TP along the drive laser axis.

4.2.2 Target stability study

A preparatory study was dedicated to characterizing the spatial positioning jitter of the hydrogen jet to estimate the general target stability during high intensity laser shots. Figure 4.4 shows stability measurements of the cold jet's position that are recorded over the course of one to two minutes at $10\ \text{Hz}$ to quantify the two-dimensional spatial jitter for a timescale relevant to high repetition rate experiments. The spatial jitter along the drive laser axis was found to be $3\ \mu\text{m}$ for the cylindrical and $12\ \mu\text{m}$ (Gaussian root mean square, RMS) for the planar jet which is well within the Rayleigh range of $\sim 30\ \mu\text{m}$ for the given laser setting. However, a lateral jitter of $10\ \mu\text{m}$ was observed for both target geometries and is rendered significant when considering the laser focal spot size of only $3\ \mu\text{m}$ (FWHM). Taking into account the lateral size of both jet shapes, as determined by the probe shadowgraphy images (cylindrical: $5\ \mu\text{m}$, planar: $18\ \mu\text{m}$), a probability histogram was derived estimating the potential overlap between laser focus and jet position and hence the amount of

Fig. 4.4. Target position stability study. a) Cylindrical jet: focus depth jitter $\sigma = 3 \mu\text{m}$, lateral jitter $\sigma = 10 \mu\text{m}$. b) Planar jet: focus depth jitter $\sigma = 12 \mu\text{m}$, lateral jitter $\sigma = 10 \mu\text{m}$, distance to nozzle: 10 mm. c) Probability histogram describing the amount of laser intensity expected to be applied to the jet depending on its lateral positioning jitter. The histogram entries are calculated from the geometric overlap of a step-like jet profile and a Gaussian laser focus intensity distribution. Intensity bins along the x-axis are normalized to the maximum intensity, which is deposited in the cylindrical jet in the event of a central hit, while the value 0 corresponds to the case that the jet is entirely outside the laser focus. The average spatial jitter of the laser focus is $1.5 \mu\text{m}$ and thus negligible compared to the lateral positioning jitter of the jet.

deposited energy on target (Fig. 4.4c). As a result, only in about 5% of shots on the cylindrical jet was the entire laser energy expected to be applied to the target, while the planar jet would be fully hit in approximately 45% of shots, making the latter a more reliable target with respect to shot-to-shot stability.

The magnitude of the spatial jitter strongly depends on the distance of the observed jet portion to the source, the stagnation pressure and the temperature stability of the hydrogen gas.^[68] All parameters need to be optimized while considering potential damages to the micrometer aperture caused by aligning the laser focus too close ($< 5 \text{ mm}$) to the source and thus impeding further jet production. The observed asymmetry in the longitudinal and lateral jitter magnitude are predominantly associated with fluid dynamic effects in the insertion nozzle. Possible causes are imperfections of the nozzle shape, e.g. localized indentations and spikes, as well as temperature gradients across the aperture. Mechanical vibrations of the source assembly introduced by the vacuum chamber are on a level of few μm and hence play a minor role.

Fig. 4.5. a) Cutoff energies from laser axis Thomson parabola for cylindrical (laser focus aligned to 15 mm below the nozzle) and planar (laser focus aligned to 6 mm below the nozzle) jet. Note that only in 50% of the shots on the cylindrical jet protons above the detection threshold ($E_p > 2$ MeV) were produced, while the planar jet was hit in all shots. b) Correlation of the lateral position of the cylindrical jet on-shot with the produced maximum proton energy (red). All evaluated shots (open markers) are binned (solid markers with error bars matching the standard error of the mean). An additional data set shows the correlation of the on-shot transmitted light with the maximum proton energy. Linear fits were introduced to reveal the general trend.

The results of the spatial jitter study demonstrate that monitoring the hydrogen jet's on-shot position is essential for the interpretation of the acquired proton acceleration data, in particular regarding the selection of representative shots for which laser and target are well aligned. The data set presented in the following was mainly collected at PM-enhanced temporal contrast, if not stated otherwise, to benefit from low plasma self-emission that would otherwise overexpose the target imaging diagnostics.

4.2.3 Proton acceleration results

Both jet geometries were characterized and compared to assess their performance as targets for laser proton acceleration experiments. Proton energy spectra featuring a typical TNSA-like exponential shape reaching to a characteristic cutoff energy of up to 20 MeV for laser energies of 2.6 J on target were recorded, which is comparable to experiments at Draco with thin metal foils of few micrometer thickness under optimized conditions.^[39] However, for the collection of shots that were performed, the detected cutoff energies cover a wide energy range as is evident from the broad distribution in Figure 4.5a). Only $\sim 50\%$ of laser shots on the cylindrical jet resulted in a detectable proton signal in the TP, which is a direct result of the positioning jitter of the jet (refer to previous section). Implementation of rotation capability of the jet source will further increase the hit probability by minimizing the lateral jitter amplitude relative to the laser focus. In contrast, the planar jet was hit (at least partially) in all shots, which agrees with the high probability of laser-target overlap assessed in the target stability study. Consequently, the distribution in Figure 4.5a) is shifted to high energies in the case of the planar jet.

Proton energies from shots utilizing the cylindrical jet were correlated with the jet's lateral position with respect to the laser focus (refer to Fig. 4.5b), which reveals the clear trend that highest proton energies were reached when the jet was hit in the center. This is supported by the analysis of the transmitted laser light, which for those high energy shots showed an evident minimum caused by central alignment of laser focus and target, such that the target blocked a large portion of the laser light. For reference, relativistic transparency of the entire jet at the given laser and plasma parameters is only expected for target thicknesses below 250 nm (equation (2.37)^[187]). As a result, the large abundance of shots resulting in low proton energies can be explained by poor lateral positioning of the target with respect to the laser focus and hence, reduced laser energy applied to the target. Positioning jitter of the target along the laser axis did not lead to significant changes in the detected proton cutoff energy. This agrees with results from section 4.2.2, showing that the jitter amplitude remained within the Rayleigh range of the laser focus. Throughout the remaining chapter, the primary focus lies on the data that is acquired during central shots on the jet, which evidently lead to the best proton acceleration performance. This ensures the comparability between different target geometries.

To assess the high repetition rate capability of the hydrogen jet target in view of its potential applications, one data set was recorded without contrast enhancement by the plasma mirror, which otherwise limited the repetition rate of the laser operation. The high repetition rate generation of proton beams at 1 Hz from the cylindrical hydrogen jet had been demonstrated in a previous experimental campaign at Draco 150 TW, although with laser parameters that were not optimized for maximum proton energies.^[51,73] For the given intrinsic (moderate) laser contrast of Draco in combination with a target thickness of a few μm , no significant difference in proton energies was detected, leading to cutoff energies of up to 20 MeV as displayed in Fig. 4.5a) (gray bars).

The angular proton emission distribution was measured primarily with radiochromic film (RCF) stacks that covered a solid angle of approximately $\pm 30^\circ$ in forward laser direction. Two representative shots under optimal conditions (and hence comparable cutoff energy) and their respective angular energy distributions are displayed in Figure 4.6 and compared to a shot on a 2 μm thick titanium foil. Line-outs from the RCF stack in the horizontal plane (the plane perpendicular to the jet axis and containing the laser polarization vector) and the vertical plane (along the jet axis) show emission angles that are consistent with TNSA proton emission from metal wire targets.^[171,335] The general tendency is similar for both target geometries: an almost isotropic, disk-like emission is observed in the horizontal plane around the jet axis, while the emission in the vertical plane is confined to half angles ranging from 10° to 20° which agrees with the emission angle observed in the foil shot. The horizontal emission property for both target shapes is supported by the recorded proton spectra in the 45° Thomson parabola. For a single shot, provided the jet was hit properly in the center, the proton cutoff energy in the 45° TP was on average 1.6 times lower than in the laser axis TP. This anisotropy in the horizontal angular energy distribution can be explained with the directionality of the high-energy electron population. Fast electrons, accelerated by the laser via $\vec{v} \times \vec{B}$ -heating preferentially

Fig. 4.6. Proton emission characteristic as detected with RCF stacks from cylindrical (left) and planar (center) hydrogen jets, compared to a reference shot on a 2 μm thick titanium foil (right, shot at intrinsic laser contrast under 45° laser incidence angle). a) 7.1 MeV RCF layer displayed. For the cylindrical jet shot, two thin glass plates of 150 μm thickness covered sections of the upper and lower half of the RCF stack. Due to this additional absorber, proton energies of 8.7 MeV are detected in those areas. The jet axis orientation is vertical. Distinct substructures appear on the proton beam accelerated from the planar jet. Similar structures are observed from the cylindrical jet, but are not visible as clearly in this display. The origin of these structures is discussed in chapter 5. b) Horizontal and vertical proton angular emission distribution from all target types evaluated along the position of the white dashed lines in a) (same position for cylindrical and planar jets). c) Proton energy spectra, corresponding to line-outs taken at the position of the dashed grey lines in b).

move in laser forward direction, which results in an anisotropy in the acceleration sheath field that consequently leads to an increase in proton energy along the laser axis. A similar effect leads to an angular shift of the proton beams accelerated from foils that are shot under oblique laser incidence^[46] (see emission pattern of the 2 μm Ti foil-shot in Figure 4.6 and from liquid crystal films in chapter 3).

Small-scale modulations are observed in the proton beams emitted from both cylindrical and planar hydrogen jets. These structures are imprinted on the proton beam by the remnant laser light that propagated around the jet in the laser focus. The details of this effect are described in chapter 5.

A significant difference between planar and cylindrical jet can be found in the number of protons per energy bin. While proton numbers for both target types are relatively high, Figure 4.6 shows that particle emission per solid angle from the planar jet is higher than from the cylindrical jet over the entire angular range covered by the RCF stack. Along line-outs in laser forward direction (Fig. 4.6c),

this difference is roughly a factor 3.5 (at proton energy of 10 MeV: planar jet $\sim 3.5 \cdot 10^9 \text{ MeV}^{-1} \text{ sr}^{-1}$, cylindrical jet $\sim 1 \cdot 10^9 \text{ MeV}^{-1} \text{ sr}^{-1}$). The proton flux from the planar jet even reaches particle numbers that were recorded with the $2 \mu\text{m}$ thick titanium foil ($\sim 4 \cdot 10^9 \text{ MeV}^{-1} \text{ sr}^{-1}$, as observed along the emission angle of highest proton energies), shot at intrinsic laser contrast.

4.2.4 PIC simulation setup

Two-dimensional PIC simulations (2D3V PIC) were performed with PIconGPU, version 0.2.1,^[66,340,341] to examine the main interaction mechanism governing the production of laser-accelerated protons for both jet geometries. Special effort was dedicated to investigating general tendencies regarding the influence of different hydrogen target geometries on the proton beam properties, in order to explain experimental observations concerning angular proton emission patterns and particle numbers.

The simulated targets consist of a pure hydrogen plasma with an electron density of $30 n_c$ in the shape of five different target geometries: circular with a $5 \mu\text{m}$ diameter, two rectangular of $10 \mu\text{m}$ and $20 \mu\text{m}$ width and $2 \mu\text{m}$ thickness and two laterally large foil-like targets, of $2 \mu\text{m}$ and $5 \mu\text{m}$ thickness. The laser was polarized in the plane of the simulation and perpendicular to the jet axis with a pulse length of 30 fs and focused to a spot size of $3 \mu\text{m}$ (both Gaussian FWHM of the temporal and spatial intensity envelope, respectively), matching the laser parameters in the experiment. The normalized peak vector potential a_0 was set to 16 in order to resemble the experimental laser intensity on target of approximately $6 \cdot 10^{20} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$. The simulation cell size was 5 nm in both directions in space with initially 10 particles per species per cell with third order particle (PCS) shape. A relatively short exponentially decreasing preplasma density slope with a scale length of $0.2 \mu\text{m}$ was assumed to isotropically surround the target. This short scale length was selected to account for the enhanced, yet not perfect temporal contrast of a high-power laser system equipped with a single plasma mirror, while ensuring well-defined discretized initial simulation conditions. The presented data is taken at 260 fs after the interaction of the laser peak intensity and the target front surface. At this time step, the proton acceleration process is largely complete and the protons have not left the $50 \mu\text{m} \times 75 \mu\text{m}$ simulation box.

4.2.5 Discussion of simulation and comparison to experimental results

Reducing the system to 2D often hampers correct modeling of absolute proton energies and particle yields. One of the reasons for this is that the Coulomb potential of charge carriers scales as $\propto \ln(r)$ with distance r in 2D as opposed to $\propto 1/r^3$ in the 3D case.^[195] Regardless, overall trends can be derived and compared to experimental results. The simulated proton acceleration results are displayed in Figures 4.7 and 4.8. Analysis of the proton beam properties reveals exponential particle spectra with maximum energies ranging from 30 to 37 MeV for all hydrogen target geometries (Fig. 4.7a). The proton phase space distributions of the circular

Fig. 4.7. PIC Simulation results 260 fs after the peak laser intensity interacted with the target front surface. a) Proton energy spectra of different hydrogen target geometries (of target width w and thickness d , if applicable), averaged within an emission angle of $\pm 4.5^\circ$ from the 0° -axis. b) Phase space images along the laser axis for the cylindrical jet with $5 \mu\text{m}$ diameter and the planar jet with dimensions $20 \mu\text{m} \times 2 \mu\text{m}$, with an initial target center position at $y = 15 \mu\text{m}$, indicated by a dashed line. Features leading to the highest proton energies are identified as typical TNSA signatures from the front and the rear surface of the target. Some protons from the target front are accelerated through the target in laser forward direction.

and the $20 \mu\text{m}$ wide rectangular target, displayed in Figure 4.7b), exhibit TNSA features extending from the front and the rear side of the target along the laser axis. These results manifest that the laser target interaction for all studied target geometries is dominated by the same acceleration mechanism, TNSA, corroborating the experimental observation presented in section 4.2.3.

Figure 4.8 displays the transition between four of the five numerically investigated target shapes regarding spatial charge density and energy-resolved angular emission distribution of the generated proton beams. While protons accelerated from the circular target are emitted almost isotropically within the simulation plane (with a slight increase in the laser direction), a strong 0° component marking the target normal in laser direction is observed for the rectangular targets, reaching maximum proton energies. The 0° component is flanked by a large background that spans the entire half sphere reaching energies that are about half the maximum energy observed in the forward accelerated component. By increasing the lateral size of the target, proton emission in larger solid angles becomes less pronounced and finally vanishes, leaving only an emission angle of $\pm 20^\circ$ for energies around 10 MeV and decreasing with growing proton energy, which is consistent with TNSA from foils.

The main effects dominating the generated proton beam quality, i.e. the target surface curvature and lateral target size, can be quantified by returning to the proton spectra of all simulated hydrogen target geometries, displayed in Fig. 4.7a) along the 0° emission axis. First, the curved surface of the circular target results in a proportionally lower particle number along the 0° axis as compared to the planar targets, which is observed in both experimental and simulation results. Second, the limited lateral size of the circular target ($5 \mu\text{m}$) and the two rectangular targets ($10 \mu\text{m}$ and $20 \mu\text{m}$) lead to higher TNSA fields and therefore higher proton energies than the foil-like cases of the according thickness. The enhancement is due to the confinement of the electron sheath and recirculation of hot electrons from the edges

Fig. 4.8. Simulation results 260 fs after the peak laser intensity interacted with the target front surface. a) Proton charge density for four different hydrogen target shapes ($5\ \mu\text{m}$ circular, $10\ \mu\text{m} \times 2\ \mu\text{m}$, $20\ \mu\text{m} \times 2\ \mu\text{m}$, infinite with $2\ \mu\text{m}$ thickness). The laser irradiates the target from the left side. Dashed white lines indicate the initial target position. b) Rear side proton emission angle distribution corresponding to the target shapes in a). The angular range covered by the RCF stacks is marked by gray dashed lines in the left-most geometry case.

of the jet, which can hence be associated with a so-called reduced mass target (RMT). Leading to a denser, more homogeneous and sometimes hotter electron sheath, the RMT-effect results in increased proton energies, as well as higher particle yields, compared to a laterally large foil.^[41,65,131] According to the short laser pulse duration and large target thickness, no significant reheating of the confined sheath electrons was observed in our simulations, which is in agreement with the results reported in the work from Kluge and colleagues^[65]. It should be noted that an expansion of the Debye-sheath along the jet axis would decrease the RMT effect and cannot be assessed in two-dimensional simulations. Of the five numerically investigated hydrogen target shapes (Fig. 4.7a), the planar geometry leads to the highest proton beam quality in terms of proton numbers and additionally, the laterally limited targets lead to the highest proton cutoff energy. Experimental data collected in this study show no significant difference (acknowledging the limited number of shots) in cutoff energies between the cylindrical and the planar jet, that would indicate effective enhancement by the RMT effect (see Fig. 4.5a). This suggests that a potential proton energy increase needs further adjustment of the planar jet geometry in thickness and lateral size. For instance, cutting the target into vertically limited pieces could result in a truly mass-limited target geometry.

Fig. 4.9. Expansion of the cylindrical jet with a controlled prepulse with peak intensity of $I = 10^{16} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$. The images were recorded with the side view probe and without the main laser pulse, to avoid saturation of the probe diagnostics due to plasma self emission.

4.3 Conclusion

Proton acceleration studies with renewable cryogenic hydrogen targets at two different laser facilities were presented. Both studies demonstrate the suitability of those targets for the efficient and debris-free generation of pure proton beams with high energies and particle numbers.

The achieved proton beam performance was subject to shot-to-shot fluctuations related to positioning jitter of the hydrogen jets and ribbons with respect to the best laser focus. However, probing of the on-shot target position allowed to select central shots, that predictably delivered highest proton energies. The key to increase the target stability will be the efficient shielding and protection of the source nozzle from disruptive radiation originating in the laser-plasma interaction.

Best proton acceleration performance was observed from μm -sized hydrogen jets at Draco 150 TW, resulting in high proton energies and numbers of up to 20 MeV and $\sim 10^9 \text{ MeV}^{-1} \text{ sr}^{-1}$, respectively. These results establish the hydrogen jet technology as a viable source of laser-driven proton beams, with similar cutoff energies and particle numbers as accelerated from conventionally used metal foils. Comparison of experimental results with 2D3V PIC simulations revealed similar trends in angular proton emission characteristic for the different hydrogen jet geometries. This represents a direct consequence of the dominant proton acceleration mechanism, TNSA, which was consistently identified both from experimental and numerical signatures. As such, predictive capabilities of the presented PIC simulations were demonstrated for the given experimental environment.

In combination, the presented experimental and numerical studies set the stage for further investigation into the high-power laser target interaction. In particular, decreasing the jet thickness is expected to result in even higher proton energies, in case harmful pre-expansion of the jet is sufficiently suppressed, e.g. through contrast cleaning with plasma mirrors (ref. to chapter 3). Promising progress of recent target development efforts has resulted in planar jets of $\sim 40 \mu\text{m}$ lateral width and $< 1 \mu\text{m}$ thickness.^[342] Parallel improvements on the probe laser and diagnostics achieved suppression of the strong plasma self emission signal, which so far saturated the imaging system in the interaction region.^[225,337] This refined probing setup will allow observation of the ionization dynamics, reconstruction of the plasma density evolution in the transparent regions and derivation of plasma

scale lengths. Controlled pre-expansion of the jet with a variable prepulse (ref. to Fig. 4.9) constitutes a handle to manipulate the spatio-temporal plasma density profile and reach optimal interaction conditions.

Complementary studies investigate the development of magneto-hydro dynamic instabilities at the jet surface,^[343] the growth of Weibel-type instabilities in the rear surface preplasma^[51,344] and multi-species effects for hydrogen-deuterium mixed jets.^[70] Furthermore, both cylindrical and planar jets were recently deployed in a campaign at the Draco-PW stage at higher laser intensities, the results of which are currently evaluated and compared to correspondingly adapted simulations.^[345] The latter consistently predict an increasing influence of both RIT and front-side RPA on the overall acceleration mechanism.^[70]

In combination, these studies will deliver a more thorough perception of plasma processes on the microscopic level, as well as their influence on the observed proton beam parameters.

5 Single-pulse all-optical structuring of laser-accelerated proton beams

Due to extreme field gradients that can be sustained in a dense plasma, laser-driven proton acceleration represents the most compact method to generate proton and ion beams of high energy and brilliance.^[7,39] It is generally understood that the acceleration takes place on micrometer spatial scales within picoseconds after laser-target interaction.^[20] The acceleration phase is followed by ballistic propagation over millimeters to hundreds of centimeters to the particle detector or a proton target at a dedicated irradiation site.^[25,27] Space-charge effects during propagation are negligible leading to a high degree of beam laminarity. In combination with their broad exponential energy spectrum and point-source characteristic, laser-driven proton beams are regularly deployed as diagnostic tools for time-resolved radiography^[30] of transient electro-magnetic fields, that are often inherent to high energy density or warm dense matter phenomena.^[31-33]

This chapter presents the important discovery that, contrary to the above notion, the relevant laser-matter interaction leading to the final proton beam shape is in fact not limited to the few ten micrometer volume surrounding the focus. Remnant laser light, which is not absorbed into the target plasma but reflected or transmitted, can be of ionizing intensities up to much larger distances from the focus and, hence, significantly modify the millimeter scale environment of the acceleration. Air molecules, constituting the residual gas after establishing typical vacuum conditions in the experimental chamber, are ionized and a low-density plasma is formed along the remnant laser beam path. Similar to charge-separation fields in solid density plasmas, laser heating of the low-density plasma electrons leads to the formation of quasi-static electric fields. In case the experimental geometry allows for a spatial overlap of particle trajectories and low-density plasma regions, protons and ions accelerated at the target are deflected in these fields in a proton-radiography-like

manner. If the residual gas density and remnant laser intensity are high enough, macroscopic structures emerge in the detected proton beam profile, that resemble features of the collimated laser mode. Counter-intuitively, information transfer between the laser pulse and the substantially slower protons is hence enabled through spatial laser filtering in the focus, memorizing of the remnant laser profile in the residual gas and subsequent proton probing of the latter.

This finding substantially extends the relevant spatial and temporal scales of laser-driven proton acceleration from the micrometer to the millimeter scale and from few picoseconds to exceeding hundred picoseconds after main laser pulse-target interaction, with the following two main consequences. First, it demonstrates that proton profile modulations do not exclusively originate in the direct vicinity of the ultra-high laser-target interaction. The latter has, however, been the source of interpreting profile modulations as the result of filamentation instabilities in the target plasma^[40,51,75,216] (see section 2.2.3). Associated with non-optimal proton acceleration conditions, plasma instabilities potentially limit the scalability of TNSA and advanced proton acceleration schemes like RPA-LS to high proton energies.^[40] The results in this chapter demonstrate that post-acceleration all-optical beam structuring does not compromise the overall proton beam performance and, furthermore, can be switched off completely by improving the ambient vacuum conditions.

Second, substantial control over intentional structures in the proton beam profile at multi-MeV energies, decoupled from the initial laser-target interaction is provided, which could benefit potential applications of laser-driven proton sources. Particularly, blocking dose in certain areas across the proton beam could be of significant interest for those applications where inserting a metal mask into the particle beam as an alternative beam structuring method is unsuitable due to the generation of undesired secondary radiation. Manipulation of collective beam parameters like pointing and divergence can be achieved during the initial acceleration phase due to the principle of TNSA by altering the symmetry of the accelerating electron sheath. Variation of the surface topology has a distinct influence on proton emission characteristic, as was demonstrated in the previous chapter both by experimental and simulation results. Simulations predict an increase in proton cutoff energies when laterally confining target and electron sheath size, in agreement with previous work on reduced mass targets.^[41,55,65,131] Studies conducted in this regime report on additional improvements of the beam divergence^[41] as well as an influence on proton beam confinement by laser light leaking around the target.^[55] Other examples of electron sheath manipulation include shaping the focal spot,^[248,346,347] introducing a laser pulse front tilt,^[46] or micro-engineering the target surface.^[7,348-350] These approaches, while key to control proton beam propagation, are often difficult to realize in application-oriented experiments and, more importantly, do not allow tailoring of structures on the generated beam profile according to a specific design.

The chapter is structured as follows. The initial discovery of all-optical imprinting of laser near-field features to the proton beam profile is described in the first section. The working principle, as well as its experimental validation is presented in the second section, followed by the numerical modeling to derive quantitative parameters like the deflecting field strength in the strongly underdense plasma

Fig. 5.1. Schematic of experimental setup and example measurement. Obstacles were inserted in the collimated Draco laser beam before focusing it onto a micrometer-sized solid hydrogen jet target. An image of the laser focus (logarithmic color scale) is overlapped with a schematic image of the hydrogen jet ($5\ \mu\text{m}$ diameter) to visualize the amount of laser intensity present in the outer lobes of the focus. Proton beam profile measurements via radiochromic film (RCF) stacks (7 MeV layer displayed, zoom-in on obstacles with different gray scale to emphasize imprinted structures) and a scintillator at 12.5 cm (exemplary data shown in Fig. 5.2) clearly reproduce the shape of the inserted obstacles, namely pick-off mirror and triangle. Zemax simulations confirm the effect of spatial filtering in the laser focus on the transmitted light intensity distribution, that was measured by imaging a ceramic screen situated in front of the scintillator detector.

regions along the proton beam path in the third section. The final part of the chapter deals with the course of the field strength along the proton trajectory, as well as resolution restraints to the imprinted structures.

The results of this chapter have been previously published in reference^[351]. Therefore, substantial overlap exists in text and figures.

5.1 Structured proton beams from cryogenic hydrogen jet

All-optical structuring of laser-driven proton beam profiles was initially observed in an experiment dedicated to proton acceleration from a renewable micrometer sized cryogenic hydrogen jet^[73,74] at the Draco 150 TW laser, presented in the previous chapter. The experimental setup including the plasma mirror was introduced in sections 4.2.1 and 3.2.1. Radio-chromic film (RCF) stacks to diagnose the proton beam profile on a single shot basis were inserted on-demand along the laser propagation direction at a distance of 45 mm behind the target. In case no RCF-stack was irradiated, the transmitted laser light was recorded by means of a ceramic screen installed at a distance of 125 mm behind the target and imaged onto a CCD camera located outside the experimental chamber and equipped with an interference filter optimized to the Ti:sapphire wavelength spectrum ($800\ \text{nm} \pm 50\ \text{nm}$).

The recorded transmission values represent a lower limit, as self-phase modulation during laser-plasma interaction can shift the transmitted light to wavelengths beyond the filter range.^[238] Stacked behind the ceramic screen was a scintillator that detected protons with energies ≥ 9 MeV. Pre-expansion of the cylindrical jet with a controlled on-demand prepulse with variable delay was implemented with a small mirror (0.5 inch diameter), positioned closely to the surface of the last folding mirror before focusing, and inserted into the laser beam from the side. The prepulse spot size on target was 22 μm (FWHM) resulting in a peak intensity of $\sim 10^{16}$ W cm^{-2} .

In the experiment prominent features of the collimated drive laser beam, such as the shadow of obstacles inserted deliberately in the beam, were observed to clearly reappear in the accelerated proton beam profile (see Fig. 5.1). This observation is highly counter-intuitive for the following two reasons. First, such laser near-field intensity features do not express in the far-field, that is, the focus on the opaque target where hot electrons are generated. Including electron transport through the solid target, there is neither reason nor evidence for the formation of a correspondingly modulated sheath field. Simultaneous detection of the intensity distribution of the remnant laser light behind the target, enabled by the combined laser transmission and proton beam profile measurement, however, showed identical yet edge-contrast enhanced features. This remnant laser light will be called transmitted light in the following for simplicity although the target remains opaque* during laser interaction. Data from the transmitted light diagnostic reveals that at least 70 % of the laser light propagated around the 5 μm diameter cylindrical hydrogen jet. Blocking only the central area of a typical laser focus,^[352,353] indicated schematically in the inset in Fig. 5.1 (refer also to Fig. 3.2) with a high dynamic range Draco focus image, thus acts as an inverted Fourier-plane spatial filter, emphasizing high spatial frequency features as observed. This was confirmed in field propagation simulations that apply scalar diffraction theory to simulate the propagation of the laser field through space, in this case around obstacles in the collimated beam and the inverted filter in the laser focus^[354] (see Zemax calculation displayed in Fig. 5.1).

Utilizing the planar jet resulted in transmission values around 60 % and well defined imprint features in the proton beam up to energies of 18 MeV. Reducing the transmitted light by pre-expanding the the cylindrical jet with a controlled prepulse[†] predictably decreased the contrast of imprinted signatures (refer to Fig. 5.2).

Recent studies^[90,355] showed direct effects of the reflected or transmitted laser light co-propagating with relativistic electrons that originated in laser-solid interactions (see section 3.3.6). However, laser-accelerated proton bunches travel at velocities that are a fraction of the speed of light, which inherently precludes temporal overlap with the transmitted drive laser pulse when propagating away from the target. This breach of causality represents the second obstacle for an explanation of the measured proton features based on sheath field properties.

*Transparency^[187] is only expected for hydrogen targets thinner than 250 nm at the given laser peak intensity, refer to section 3.3.4.

[†]Transmitted light values indicate that the jet remains opaque during main pulse interaction, even for the largest prepulse delay applied.

Fig. 5.2. Pre-expanding the target (probe shadowgraphy images in top row) results in a reduction in both transmitted light and imprinted signatures (combined transmitted light and proton profile diagnostic in bottom row). No prepulse was applied in a). In b), c), d), and e), prepulse delays were 10 ps, 20 ps, 50 ps and 100 ps. Note that transmission values represent lower limits, as self-phase modulation during laser-plasma interaction can shift the transmitted light to wavelengths beyond the filter gap. Probing images of the jet expansion were recorded without the main laser pulse to mitigate probe diagnostic saturation due to plasma emission. Images of the proton beam profile were adjusted in grey scale between sub-figures for visibility. The lower detection limit of the proton profile diagnostic was 9 MeV.

The imprinting of laser intensity features in the proton beam profile at macroscopic distances from the focus region, despite the lack of temporal overlap, can be explained by laser-induced quasi-static electric fields in the background gas of the experimental interaction chamber. Induced by ionization of residual gas molecules through the transmitted laser pulse up to > 10 mm distances from the laser focus, these fields remain intact for tens of picoseconds, thereby serving as a memorizing structure to bridge the temporal gap until the arrival of protons that were accelerated at the target by TNSA-fields originating from the very same laser pulse. This forms the basic imprinting concept and is explained in detail in the following section.

5.2 Imprinting concept and validation experiment

The scheme explaining the observed imprint effect is schematically depicted in Figure 5.3a). Along the propagation axis of the transmitted laser pulse and the trailing proton bunch, three relevant regions are identified: region I contains the ultra-high intensity laser-target interaction, in this case TNSA, resulting in an accelerated proton bunch. Region II begins well beyond the focus and target region and reaches until the laser intensity has dropped, due to the beam divergence, below the ionization threshold of the residual gas molecules. The latter marks the transition to region III, in which no ionization takes place, hence is considered field-free.

Fig. 5.3. Imprinting concept and experimental validation. a) Schematic depiction of the imprint scenario, visualizing the transmitted laser path (red cone) and the accelerated proton bunch (green) along the propagation axis z . Between target and proton beam diagnostic, three main regions are identified and related to the transmitted laser intensity expressed via a_0 . In the quasi-neutral region II, transverse quasi-static electric fields between the plasma electrons and the remaining fixed ions are visualized via radiography with the accelerated protons as intrinsic probe. b) Transmitted laser intensity mode without (left) and with (right) a $10\ \mu\text{m}$ diameter tungsten wire positioned in the laser focus. The color scale for each picture was adjusted to ensure visibility of important features. c) Proton beam profiles (4.7 MeV layer displayed) at two different residual gas pressures in the experimental chamber. In the left image, structures corresponding to the obstacles inserted in the laser beam are observed, as well as features originating from fluctuations intrinsic to the laser beam profile. By decreasing the pressure, the imprint signature is substantially reduced (right image). The change in overall dose between both cases is within the range of shot-to-shot variations of the proton acceleration performance.

Spatial filtering of the laser pulse by the opaque target in the laser focus results in strong laser transmission in high spatial frequency areas of the beam profile, while low spatial frequencies are suppressed.* As a result, residual gas molecules across the transmitted laser beam are locally ionized in areas exhibiting high spatial laser frequencies, most prominently those inherent to diffraction of the laser at sharp edges of inserted obstacles in Figure 5.1. Note that the ionization rate of residual gas molecules by hot electrons escaping the target is only in the order of one event $\text{ms}^{-1}\ \text{cm}^{-3}$ and can therefore be omitted.^[356] As the transmitted laser pulse propagates through region II, which can reach up to $> 10\ \text{mm}$, depending on the given experimental parameters, these ionized areas extend to low-density plasma columns containing free electrons behind the laser pulse. The plasma electrons gain energy in the field of the transmitted laser pulse,^[15,19] while the ions can be considered predominantly fixed, given the laser intensity is sufficiently low,^[357,358]

*Pre-expansion of the target with a prepulse not only reduces the amount of transmitted light but also modifies the spatial frequency filter edges from sharp in the unexpanded (PM-enhanced contrast) case, to smoother due to the expanded electron density gradient. The effect of the change in spatial filter shape on the imprint signatures needs to be assessed in future studies.

which is the case for the experiments presented in this work.* Charge displacement of free electrons with respect to the fixed ions^[92] perpendicular to the laser and proton propagation axis, results in an electric potential that satisfies Poisson's equation $\Delta\Phi(r) \sim [n_e(r) - Z_i n_i(r)]$ where $Z_i n_i(r)$ and $n_e(r)$ are the respective 1-dimensional ion and electron charge distributions. The corresponding electric field $E_{\text{trans}}(r)$ is indeed quasi-static, as its persistence is only limited by the quasi-neutral plasma expansion^[137,139] and the energy loss of the plasma electrons through electron-ion collisions.^[80] Both become relevant on a time scale of ~ 10 ns, leaving sufficient time for TNSA protons generated at the target to probe E_{trans} . For illustration, a 7 MeV proton arrives at $z = 2$ mm after $\simeq 55$ ps. In the framework of laser-proton acceleration it can be assumed that the proton and laser beam divergence in the ionized areas in region II are sufficiently similar such that a proton experiences the deflecting fields of a single low-density plasma column over the length of region II, leading to the observed sharp features in the final proton beam profile.

For the conditions of the hydrogen jet experiment where the residual gas was dominated by hydrogen vapor, the upper boundary of region II can be derived to be ~ 15 mm up to which ionization of the residual gas molecules takes place, corresponding to the BSI appearance intensity $I_{\text{BSI,H}^+} = 1.37 \cdot 10^{14} \text{ W cm}^{-2}$ (refer to section 2.1.1). As measured transmitted light values only provide a lower transmission limit, region II could effectively extend to even larger distances from the focus. The lower boundary marking the transition to region I, while subject to ongoing investigations, is estimated heuristically: acknowledging that characteristic structures in the laser near-field intensity mode reappear in the recorded proton beam profiles, the imprinting effect has to occur at distances from the laser focus, clearly beyond the Fresnel region, where the laser profile has regained such features. As verified during the experiment, this only happens at a distance of roughly $500 \mu\text{m}$ behind the focus. Hence, region II extends over a minimum length of $14 - 15$ mm (refer to section 5.4 for further discussion). Along region II, the laser beam divergence dictates the decrease in intensity, which, given the experimental conditions, amounts to roughly one order of magnitude in terms of the laser field's dimensionless vector potential, a_0 (ref. to a_0 scale in Fig. 5.3a). A correspondingly moderate decay in field strength E_{trans} with increasing distance from the laser focus along the low-density plasma columns is expected.

A first estimate for the field strength E_{trans} is derived from the experimentally recorded proton beam profiles in the form of an example calculation. A proton with energy ϵ_p that propagates through the electric field \vec{E}_{trans} in region II with the field length L is deflected by the amount $r_{\text{def}} = e/4 \vec{E}_{\text{trans}} L^2 \epsilon_p^{-1}$, followed by ballistic propagation in region III until the detector. Proton beam distortions of few $100 \mu\text{m}$, as observed during the hydrogen jet experiment, require mean deflecting fields of $10^6 - 10^7 \text{ V m}^{-1}$ all along region II.

A dedicated experiment was conducted to validate the proposed scheme by un-

*At the given residual gas density, the transmitted laser power in region II was well below the critical power for self-focussing (see section 2.1.3). Therefore, propagation of the laser pulse through the largely underdense plasma led to no detectable change in lateral intensity distribution. This was verified by focusing the laser without target into the residual gas and monitoring the laser mode on the ceramic screen.

ambiguously demonstrating that said electro-static fields are induced by ionization of the background gas in the experimental chamber, resulting in the transfer of the laser intensity profile information to the proton beam. Instead of the hydrogen jet, causing an uncontrollable amount of hydrogen vapor around the target, tungsten wire targets of 10 μm thickness were irradiated while actively tuning the background gas density (mainly nitrogen), and hence plasma electron density n_e , with a precision air valve. For a chamber pressure of $1.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$ mbar, engineered laser beam profile modulations, in this case the letters "HZDR", reoccur as edge contrast enhanced imprints in the proton beam profile at the detector (ref. to Fig. 5.3b and c). While the overall amount of transmitted light is reduced by roughly a factor two, resulting from the use of a wider target, remarkable agreement with the hydrogen jet experiment is observed in the strong spatial filtering by the wire target in the laser focal plane. This expresses in the enhancement of the transmitted intensity of high spatial frequency contributions in the vicinity of the inserted letters, thereby defining the spatial intensity pattern for the ionization of the residual gas (see Fig. 5.3b). As a result, areas of strong laser light transmission correspond directly to areas of low proton dose across the proton beam profile, as is displayed in the left image of Fig. 5.3c). Reduction of the vacuum chamber pressure to $2.3 \cdot 10^{-5}$ mbar resulted in nearly smooth proton beam profiles exhibiting no distinct signs of imprinting. This verifies that the quasi-static electric field strength E_{trans} scales with the electron density n_e in the low-density plasma columns as was proposed above. The results of the tungsten wire experiment thereby confirm the important role of the residual background gas as a programmable medium for the laser intensity profile.

5.3 PIC simulation of low-density plasma region

Two-dimensional PIC simulations (2D3V PIC) were carried out with PIConGPU^[66] to investigate the emergence and evolution of electro-static fields over the course of tens of picoseconds after the propagation of a laser pulse through residual gas in region II. This allowed for the quantitative study of maximum field strengths and lateral distributions of E_{trans} , both expected to depend strongly on the local electron density distribution. The spatial grid resolution was 23.3 cells per laser wavelength of 800 nm in all dimensions with a resulting cell width of 34.375 nm and time step of 81 as. Particle-field interaction was modeled with second-order particle shape (triangular shape cloud, TSC) and two weighted, initially neutral hydrogen ions per cell. Ionization of the residual gas was included following the probabilistic ADK model^[359] with BSI cutoff^[77] (refer to section 2.1.1). The laser pulse was modeled as an analytical background field, polarized in the plane of the simulation with a pulse length of 30 fs. Periodic boundary conditions were applied for the transverse direction.

Two different gas settings utilizing hydrogen gas with densities roughly corresponding to the vacuum chamber pressures realized during the tungsten wire experiment were studied: $n_e = 10^{14} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and $n_e = 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, corresponding to chamber pressures $1.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$ mbar and $1.6 \cdot 10^{-5}$ mbar, respectively (assuming three to four-fold ionization of nitrogen molecules, refer to section 5.4.1 for details). Intensity modula-

Fig. 5.4. 2D3V PIC simulation results of transverse electric field maps in a single plasma column. The field distribution develops as an intensity modulated plane wave laser pulse travels along z through hydrogen gas of different densities. The peak intensity of $a_0 = 0.065$ resembles experimental laser conditions at a distance $z = 2$ mm after the laser focus. The laser pulse is initialized at the bottom of the simulation window at time $t = 0$. a) Laser intensity envelope (red) with a lateral size of $44 \mu\text{m}$ and line-outs of both electron (blue) and proton densities (gray) for the electron density case of $n_e = 10^{14} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ at time step 9.7 ps . Step-like ionization of hydrogen atoms occurs at the appearance intensity corresponding to $a_0 = 0.008$. Note that, while the proton density gradient appears to be rather sharp on the few $10 - 100 \mu\text{m}$ scale relevant to this study, it is in fact smooth when zooming in on μm distances, as is expected from a probabilistic ionization model such as ADK. b) and c): Electric field distribution in x -direction at time steps 9.7 ps and 40.5 ps respectively for electron densities $n_e = 10^{14} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ (top) and $n_e = 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ (bottom). Line-outs of the respective field distribution at $z = 3220 \mu\text{m}$ are overlaid as black solid and dashed curves, where the latter is scaled by a factor 10 for visibility.

tions on top of a plane wave laser mode were modeled with a sinusoidal function for simplicity, the period of which was adapted to roughly reproduce the characteristic size of the intensity modulation in the experiment, namely, ~ 1 mm at the position of the proton beam diagnostic and scaled along the laser axis according to the laser beam divergence. Several simulations varying a_0 and the feature size, thereby representing different distances from the focus, were performed. As the decrease in laser intensity according to experimental conditions is relatively slow within one simulation window, no laser divergence angle is included for the separate simulations.

Transverse electric field maps of a single plasma column at two different time steps are displayed in Fig. 5.4, illustrating the field evolution on a few 10 ps scale for both plasma density cases. The filament diameter and maximum laser intensity correspond to estimated experimental conditions at a distance 2 mm behind the laser focus. Sharp transverse electric fields are formed at the border between the ion population remaining immobile and the free electron plasma, with electron temperatures in the order of few hundred eV, that is distributed over a larger lateral area. Maximum electric field strengths are few times 10^6 V m⁻¹ for $n_e = 10^{14}$ cm⁻³ and roughly a factor 40 lower for $n_e = 10^{12}$ cm⁻³, agreeing well with estimated values in the previous section based on experimentally observed proton beam deflections. The orientation of the transverse electric fields are such that protons propagating along region II would be deflected radially outwards of the columns, resulting in low proton signal in areas of high transmitted light intensity, in agreement with experimental results (see Figures 5.3b and c).

Within the boundaries of region II that were estimated in the previous section, maximum field strengths are nearly constant along z (refer to the following section for details). Until the final time step at ~ 35 ps after the laser has left the simulation window, no decrease in field strength is observed. Therefore, it can be concluded that the fields remain present for considerably longer timescales, allowing for them to be probed by protons accelerated at the target.

5.4 Further analytical considerations

5.4.1 Course of E_{trans} along z in region II

The course of the electric field strength along z in region II is first estimated assuming a lateral exponential electron density gradient and using equation (2.18) to calculate front fields at the plasma-vacuum interface.^[92] The results are displayed in Fig. 5.5a) (solid lines) for the two residual gas density cases realized in the tungsten wire experiment. For a constant residual gas density, the field strength changes only roughly one order of magnitude over the course of ~ 8 mm for $z \geq 500$ μm . Changing the gas density by two orders of magnitude in the investigated density regime results in roughly a factor 10 in field strength. Steps in the course of the electric field strength correspond changes in ionization state (ref. to Fig. 5.6 for comparison) due to barrier suppression ionization (refer to section 2.1.1)^[77] by the transmitted laser beam, the intensity of which decreases according to the laser opening angle. Collisional ionization plays no role in this very low-density regime, as

Fig. 5.5. Course of the electric field strength along region II. a) Analytical calculation of the maximum field strength at the border of a low-density plasma column assuming an exponential electron density gradient.^[92] Solid lines correspond to residual gas pressures p realized in the tungsten wire experiments. For simplicity the residual gas is assumed to consist only of nitrogen. Dashed lines correspond to the respective hydrogen densities used for PIC simulations. Both nitrogen and hydrogen values agree reasonably well for a given density setting. b) Maximum field strengths E_{trans} from PIC simulations, varying laser conditions along z for two different residual gas electron densities. Every data point represents one simulation at 21 ps after initialization of the laser pulse in the respective window.

electron-ion collisions only occur at a maximum rate of 0.1 to 10 ms^{-1} at the given electron temperatures of 10 to few 100 eV .^[360]

The analytically deduced electric field strength was found to scale only weakly with ionization state along z . Therefore, simulations presented in section 5.3 were performed with hydrogen at a constant density corresponding to three to four-fold ionization of nitrogen at the two vacuum chamber pressure cases realized in the tungsten wire experiment. Calculated values of the electric field strength at the selected hydrogen gas densities (dashed lines in Fig. 5.5a) show a sufficiently similar course as those of the experimental residual gas settings (solid lines in Fig. 5.5a). Simulated maximum field strengths E_{trans} , oriented transversely to the proton propagation direction, are displayed in Fig. 5.5b). Apart from the region close to the target at $z < 500 \mu\text{m}$, values of E_{trans} are largely constant over a distance of several mm along z . Absolute field strength values differ from the analytical results, which is attributed to a significantly longer electron density gradient observed in simulations than the calculated Debye length. This deviation may be related to differing thermalization dynamics for this low-density, low-intensity regime as compared to relativistic laser-plasmas, which are usually described with the Debye length. The simulations and analytical calculations confirm the conception of fairly modest changes in $E_{\text{trans}}(z)$ along region II of the proton deflection scheme introduced in section 5.2.

5.4.2 Spatial resolution limits of imprinted structures

Provided the residual gas density and, consequently, the laser induced fields are high enough to allow for effective imprinting of laser intensity features in the proton

Fig. 5.6. Spatial resolution criterion of imprinted features. Displayed is the scaling of the lateral extent of the electron population to both sides of the low-density plasma column represented by $2 \cdot \lambda_D$ (blue line) versus exemplary feature diameters f (gray lines, annotated are the feature diameters at the position of radio-chromic film stacks positioned 45 mm downstream of the laser focus) scaled geometrically along the propagation length z and the corresponding laser vector potential a_0 . For reference, ionization states Z_i of nitrogen (dashed orange line) are given. Insets schematically depict electron and ion distributions leading to distinct (upper right) and blurred (lower left) electro-static field structures. Feature diameters larger than $2 \cdot \lambda_D$ (blue line) are resolvable and can be imprinted in the proton beam profile.

beam profile, limitations exist to the minimum size of these features. Distinct electro-static field structures that largely correspond to the laser intensity profile are only induced under the condition that the lateral electron density gradient at the border of a low-density plasma column is sufficiently short compared to the overall diameter of the column, approximately represented by the fixed ion population (ref. to insets in Fig. 5.6). The transverse extent of the latter results from the size of the ionizing intensity feature. If, however, electrons are distributed over a significantly larger area, the electro-static field pattern and the corresponding proton beam deflections are blurred. The lateral extent of the electron density gradient is dominated by the electron temperature, which depends on the laser intensity expressed via the dimensionless vector potential a_0 . Here, the plasma Debye length $\lambda_D(z)$ is used as a characteristic length of the electron density gradient to be compared with the size of intensity features as a function of the distance z from the target plane (depicted in Fig. 5.6). Note that, since simulations performed for this work indicate a systematically longer density gradient than the Debye length for the given laser and density parameters (refer to Fig. 5.4a), the comparison presented here can only serve to explore general trends. As displayed in Fig. 5.6, the laser beam diameter decreases when approaching the laser focus according to the beam divergence, the laser intensity increases and so does $\lambda_D \sim \sqrt{a_0}$. Once an intensity feature of diameter $f(z)$ along z becomes smaller than $2 \cdot \lambda_D(z)$ (accounting for electron density gradients on both sides of the 1-dimensional ion population), electro-static fields at the border between electron and ion population become less distinct, because electrons are distributed over a larger lateral area. As such, space-charge fields

become more and more dominated by the remaining ion population, which is expected to result in a different, less pronounced signature in the deflection of TNSA protons. This spatial resolution criterion for a clear projection of laser intensity features to sharp electric fields at the border of the ion population poses a lower limit for the field length L over which TNSA protons are subject to deflection during laser profile imprinting. As will need to be confirmed in future experiments, features that remain smaller than $2 \cdot \lambda_D(z)$ over the entire ionized region (with a minimum length of 14 – 15 mm for our laser conditions) therefore should not reappear in the proton beam profile. Longer electron density gradients are equivalent to an increase in the spatial resolution limit, such that only larger spatial intensity features can be imprinted in the proton beam profile.

5.5 Conclusion

The discovery of all-optical structuring of multi-MeV laser-accelerated proton bunches with a single laser pulse was presented. Independent from the initial acceleration process, asynchronous information transfer from the spatial profile of the high-power drive laser pulse to the proton bunch is possible via a memorizing medium at macroscopic distances from the laser focus. Numerical simulations confirmed that the memorizing medium expresses as drive laser-induced quasi-static field structures in the background gas of the vacuum chamber, capable of locally deflecting protons. Experimental variation of the residual gas pressure proved to control the proton beam structure in pressure ranges typically occurring in laser plasma experiments. The intense light required for the structured down-stream ionization of the background gas was identified to be leaking around finite sized targets. As such, the target represents a spatial frequency filter, very similar to the well-known Schlieren-imaging technique, that enhances the intensity contrast of obstacles intentionally placed in the original laser beam. The deflecting field structures extend significantly beyond the Rayleigh range of the focused laser beam and remain present at least until probed by protons originating in the laser-target interaction. This substantially extends the relevant spatial and temporal scales after the initial laser-target interaction, that need to be taken into account for the interpretation of observed laser-driven proton profiles.

Apart from utilizing laterally limited targets like the hydrogen jet, other scenarios can be considered where laser light reaches the proton propagation region behind the target. Naturally, this is the case for transparent targets, e.g. foils that are thinner than the skin depth of the evanescent laser wave in the plasma, or even for thicker targets due to the relativistic mass increase of the plasma electrons,^[187,240,262,361] often referred to as relativistic induced transparency (RIT, see chapter 3). There, the so far discussed inverted spatial filter function in the Fourier plane is inverted back to normal as the target turns transparent initially in the center,^[355,362] leading to a different transmitted light mode than when deploying opaque but laterally small targets.^[55] Notably, nonlinear plasma processes like filamentation instabilities, potentially occurring during the acceleration phase (region I in Fig. 5.3), may inherently modulate the proton beam profile and thereby superimpose or even

overwrite intentional imprint structures, engineered in region II. Examples include beam modulations observed to be generated in the ultra-high contrast laser-driven radiation-pressure dominated regime^[75,216] but also in the case of longer pre-plasma scale lengths^[40,51,254] (e.g. displayed in Figure 2.5). Distinguishing these effects from all-optical imprinting by the same laser driving the proton acceleration can be ambiguous when only proton beam profiles are evaluated. Conclusions that were derived from experimental beam profile modulations in past studies, detailing laser-plasma interaction parameters that lead to filamentation instabilities, may need to be revisited. However, simultaneous observation of the transmitted laser light and assessment of the influence of different residual gas concentrations will facilitate future interpretation. While under the presence of such instabilities proton beam quality control is challenging, programmable laser imprinting is easily controllable under standard experimental conditions.

The effect presented here can serve as a straightforward proton beam structuring method to a specific profile design. In this context, the spatio-temporal density distribution of small targets can be carefully shaped to serve as a tunable spatial frequency filter. The amount of transmitted light, residual gas density and constituents, as well as the particular shape of the incoming laser intensity mode and the tunable spatial frequency filter, represent straightforward, effective, and mostly independent tuning knobs to control the imprinted modulations in the proton beam. Strong masking of the incoming laser light will ultimately limit the proton acceleration performance, therefore clever mask geometries will be needed for efficient proton beam structuring. The required field maps for beam structuring could in principle be generated with a secondary laser-target interaction arrangement comparable to proton radiography measurements of transient electro-magnetic field structures.^[363,364] However, the complexity associated with the implementation and execution of such experiments largely exceeds requirements posed by the method presented here.

Future studies will explore the accessible parameter space of the all-optical proton beam structuring mechanism, based on the framework laid out in this chapter. Potential applications that would benefit from structured proton beams lie in laser-driven proton radio-oncology,^[25,26] ion implantation,^[365,366] stress testing of materials^[36] or isochoric heating in warm dense matter research.^[37] Further systematic studies that are concerned with shaping proton beam profiles to a customized target design are required to harness this beam structuring approach for applications.

6 Summary and outlook

The presented thesis explores viable routes to advance the properties of laser-accelerated proton beams for their application as medical proton sources. This endeavor is inherently linked to the exploration of microscopic processes unfolding during the acceleration, and how they are influenced by given realistic laser parameters. An important first step is to control temporal contrast conditions, the characteristics of which can prove decisive in reaching highest proton cutoff energies. This was demonstrated in the first study with enhanced temporal laser contrast at Draco, where temporal contrast cleaning with a plasma mirror was combined with novel on-shot contrast diagnostics via SRSI-ETE* and ultra-thin liquid crystal film targets for ion acceleration. Compared to shots without contrast cleaning, considerable improvement of accelerated proton beam properties was observed leading to maximum proton energies of 25 MeV at 2.65 J laser energy on those ultra-thin targets. As compared to previous studies in the field, a multitude of diagnostics was available to corroborate laser- and target conditions during the interaction. Among other results, this permitted to discern the onset of relativistic induced transparency (RIT) for film thicknesses below 30 nm.

Further studies in the target transparency regime are necessary to evaluate its capability in reliably enhancing the generated proton energies in view of medical applications. Numerical simulations play a crucial role in optimizing TNSA and exploring RIT and other advanced acceleration mechanisms as they allow insight into fs-short and μm -small processes in the overdense plasma that are not accessible with currently available diagnostics. Unfortunately, these simulations remain computationally very expensive for solid density targets like liquid crystal films, plastic and metal foils. A credible solution is provided by novel cryogenic hydrogen targets of low solid density, that feature reduced demands towards their numerical model and are beneficial in experiments for various reasons. The second part of the thesis therefore investigated the proton acceleration performance from hydrogen jets and ribbons. Two proof-of-concept experiments demonstrated their capability of delivering pure proton beams of comparable proton number and energy, as from optimized reference shots on foil targets. Furthermore, the high experimental versatility of these targets as opposed to conventional foils was explored, in particular

*Self-referenced spectral interferometry at extended time excursion^[247]

their geometrical advantage offering various diagnostic angles accessible e.g. to optical probing, as well as their suitability for controlled preplasma engineering via artificial prepulses resulting from their low solid density. Combined with numerical simulations that reproduced general experimental signatures, the ground work for further investigations into optimizing TNSA and other acceleration mechanism was laid.

The final part of this thesis introduced all-optical imprinting of laser intensity features onto the proton beam that was accelerated from a target of limited size. The effect was discovered in aforementioned experiments with the hydrogen jet, where spatial signatures inherent to the collimated laser beam were transferred to the profile of the proton bunch produced in the focus of the very same laser pulse. However, neither do said intensity signatures appear in the laser focus where the proton bunch is generated, nor is there a temporal overlap between the laser pulse and the proton bunch, travelling at largely differing velocities, to allow for appreciable information transfer of some kind. These two considerations rendered the initial observation of all-optical imprinting highly counter-intuitive. A follow-up experiment and PIC simulations revealed that the imprinting effect results from a substantial amount of laser light passing around or through the target, interacting with residual gas molecules up to millimeter distances behind the initial laser-target interaction. Laterally small targets like the hydrogen jet result in spatial filtering of the laser in the focus, such that mainly high spatial frequencies inherent to sharp features in the laser profile reach the half space behind the target. There, low-density plasma columns are induced by the remnant laser pulse that memorize these features in the form of an electro-static field map. Hence, information transfer between the laser pulse and the much slower proton bunch is possible through the deflection of protons in these fields, leading to the observed profile structuring. These results provide an alternative explication of structured proton beams apart from filamentation instabilities in the target plasma. The latter might represent a potential obstacle for scaling the energy of laser-driven proton beams to the medical regime. In particular, realizing enhanced proton acceleration mechanisms in experiments often requires the use of ultra-thin or low-density targets, which, deliberately or not, become transparent at some point during interaction with the laser pulse as observed in the first part of this thesis. In case transmitted laser and proton beam path overlap, proton beam modulations that were initially attributed to plasma instabilities could in fact result from all-optical imprinting, that is in contrast easily controllable through adjustments to the ambient vacuum conditions. First imprinting studies performed with ultra-thin plastic foils at Draco 150 TW under vacuum pressure variation resulted in detectable proton structuring in the lower energy range.

The presented studies are currently extended to Draco PW intensities where they serve as blueprints for newly implemented experimental arrangements. A similar recollimating single plasma mirror setup, including on-shot contrast measurement through SRSI-ETE, was implemented and applied for proton acceleration experiments with ultra-thin plastic foils at enhanced laser contrast. With that setup, a maximum proton energy of 50 MeV was reached with a laser energy of 12 J on target,

thereby extending the steep energy scaling observed at Draco 150 TW.

Based on the successful hydrogen target studies presented in this thesis, the cryogenic jet technology was transferred to the Draco PW target area, where promising results were acquired in first test experiments.^[345] Further targetry developments now allow for the production of planar jets of $> 40 \mu\text{m}$ width and $< 1 \mu\text{m}$ thickness at an improved operation stability during high-intensity laser shots due to mechanical cutting close to the jet source.^[342] Parallel improvements to an independent probe laser system^[225] have reduced the disruptive influence of plasma self emission and now allow for the observation of ionization dynamics and preplasma evolution. In combination with accordingly adapted numerical simulations, this represents a credible route to comprehend and optimize microscopic plasma processes towards medical laser-driven ion sources. Furthermore, tuning the target constituents to benefit from multi-species effects^[70] or producing helium jets to accelerate alpha particles for medical studies are envisioned in this setup.

All-optical imprinting is further investigated at PW laser powers with particular attention paid to manipulating the spatial filter function in the laser focus and exploring the resulting deflecting field map in the residual gas. Such properties may inherently be linked to temporal contrast conditions that determine the density distribution of the target plasma and, hence, the spatial filter function, during main pulse interaction.

In summary, the presented thesis improved the laser-driven proton accelerator in various aspects, stretching from nanometer thin targets to millimeter long deflecting field maps and from nanosecond long laser pulse pedestals to ultra-fast plasma mirror switching, with laser intensities that vary over many orders of magnitude. The influence of individual and combined plasma processes unfolding on such vast physical scales, their range growing continuously with increasing laser power, was demonstrated in a number of studies comprising extensive integrated diagnostic suites. As such, this thesis points out viable strategies to credibly advance PW laser-driven proton acceleration to a reliable source of medical proton beams.

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Erklärungen

Hiermit versichere ich, dass ich die vorliegende Arbeit ohne unzulässige Hilfe Dritter und ohne Benutzung anderer als der angegebenen Hilfsmittel angefertigt habe; die aus fremden Quellen direkt oder indirekt übernommenen Gedanken sind als solche kenntlich gemacht. Die Arbeit wurde bisher weder im Inland noch im Ausland in gleicher oder ähnlicher Form einer anderen Prüfungsbehörde vorgelegt.

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